

On the Establishment of Ethics in "Autonomous" Artificial Intelligence Systems

Dissertation

for the conferral of the doctorate in theology
at the Faculty of Theology of the University of Lucerne

submitted by

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Matriculation number: 17-455-320

Subject: Theological Ethics

Field: Social Ethics

Accepted on: 27.02.2024

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Institution: Institute of Social Ethics ISE

Year of Publication: 2025

Acknowledgement

The author is rather grateful for the fruitful discussions, concerning the topic herein presented, had with the participating members of the Lucerne Graduate School in Ethics LGSE and research staff of the Institute of Social Ethics ISE of the Theology Faculty of the University of Lucerne as well as with the participating members of SPT 2023.

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0.0 Introduction

0.1 The Question of Responsibility

Responsible use of technology is germane to human flourishing whether that “flourishing” is to be understood as pertaining to individuals or the collective.¹ This observation is borne out in the ongoing concerns for regulating digital transformation and the development and use of “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems both privately and publicly, respectively (De Haes et al., 2020; Wischmeyer & Rademacher 2020; Wong 2020; Kirchsclaeger 2021; Juliussen 2022).²

Focusing on the public usage of digital technologies and “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems; that is: “autonomous” artificial predictive systems³, (e.g.: self-driving

¹ The notion of “flourishing” here is meant in something like the broad-based Aristotelian sense of *eudaimonia*. For an expanded discussion on this matter see: Hursthouse, Rosalind and Glen Pettigrove. 2018. "Virtue Ethics", *The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy* (Winter Edition), Edward N. Zalta (ed.), URL = <https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/win2018/entries/ethics-virtue/>.

² The author puts scare quotes around ‘autonomous’ so as to signify that the term is being used in a non-standard way. As to in what way and why this usage is non-standard, however, is something that will be discussed in what follows, especially in the chapter of the present book entitled “Proof of Concept Testing”.

³ Some might question the phrase “‘autonomous’ artificial intelligence systems’: and in so doing, not just the term ‘autonomous’. Rather, such persons would question the compound term ‘artificial intelligence’, even setting it in scare quotes so as to signify this, and they wouldn’t be wrong to do so. For there is a question as to whether there is “artificial intelligence” or whether the term ‘intelligence’ – or any other term referring to human mental states or capacities – can really be coherently used in reference to machines or technical systems, *et cetera*, more broadly construed. As such, this would equally apply to the terms ‘prediction’ and ‘decision’. Nonetheless, use of the compound term ‘autonomous artificial predictive systems’ –setting aside for now the term ‘autonomous’ – does provide a measure of clarity as to what technical systems are doing in carrying out their functions. Though, due to its greater visibility, being more familiar to most readers, the term ‘artificial intelligence systems’ will be comparatively preferred throughout the course of the overall investigation of the current project. Furthermore, the author holds that it is important to question the merits of terms such as ‘intelligence’, ‘predictive’, and the like as applied to the domain of inquiry concerned with the technical systems in question, especially in light of the attributive use of language and the implications of various predicates used to describe such technical systems, and even the use of language more generally and its interpretive framing as applied to these technical systems within the history and philosophy of science and technology as well as machine ethics in the mid-to-late 20th century and early 21st century: much could be learned thereby about the relationship between hermeneutics, technology, narratives, and how all of this might relate to ethics. But that is not something being done within the current manuscript. Rather, this avenue of research is best left for another time, since pursuing it would take the current discussion in another, though fecund, direction which is not germane to the issues herein needing-to-be-addressed.

vehicles, drones [rescue or military]⁴, artificial assistants [artificial moral, artificial legal, and artificial institutional advisors]⁵, etc.), discussions concerning responsibility surround – and understandably so – the intersecting domains of governance and legality. Some examples of the sorts of issues touched upon here are, privacy and the use of personal data in a societal context (Todt 2019), sustainability and digital infrastructure (Ciocoiu 2011; Komarčević 2017, et.al.), distributive justice and access to digital resources (Kirchschlaeger 2021), discrimination in the digital sphere and by means of “autonomous” artificial institutional assistants (AAIAs) (Northpointe 2015; Haas 2017), violence and hate speech in the digital sphere (Olson 2020). The discussions and debates thereof yield many pertinent interrogatives and avenues of investigation, one of which being: ‘When behavior of an “autonomous” artificial intelligence system(s) leads to harm or death of someone, who is responsible?’

0.2 Varieties of Approach to an Answer and Their Commonality

There are, at least, a few ways this question can be answered: (1) governmental (2) legal (3) ethical.⁶ In the first, namely: governmental, the question is addressed by means of developing regulatory frameworks and tools, specific policies and policy recommendations as well as norms and standards. In the second, namely: legal, the question is addressed by means of developing a legal framework consisting, at the very least, of laws and ordinances that serve both a regulatory

⁴ For more on these types of technical systems, please see: Michael Carl Haas and Sophie-Charlotte Fischer. 2017. “The evolution of targeted killing practices: Autonomous weapons, future conflict, and the international order,” *Contemporary Security Policy* 38 (2): 281–306 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/13523260.2017.1336407> and D. C. Schedl et al. 2021. “An autonomous drone for search and rescue in forests using airborne optical sectioning,” *Science Robotics* 6 (55): 1–10. https://www.thetalkingmachines.com/sites/default/files/2021-06/eabg1188.full_.pdf.

⁵ For more on these types of artificial assistants, please see: Catherine Nunez. 2017. "Artificial intelligence and legal ethics: Whether AI lawyers can make ethical decisions." *Tulane Journal Technology & Intellectual Property* (20): 189–204 and Blay Whitby. 2011. “On Computable Morality: An Examination of Machines as Moral Advisors”, in *Machine Ethics*, Anderson, Michael and Anderson, Susan Leigh (eds.), 138–150. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.

⁶ These are intended to be classes of possible answers.

and protective function. In the third, namely: ethical, the relevant question is addressed by means either of assessing and laying bare explicit or implicit moral claims, attitudes, beliefs, actions, and the like, sometimes using explanatory models as well as providing known or possible justifications for such viewpoints regarding the nature of the good, what is right action, and how to be good, on the one hand (*descriptive ethics*); or critically examining and developing or redeveloping, as the case may be, moral frameworks concerning the nature of the good, what is right action, and how to be good so as to have a better understanding of how we should believe, act, and be, on the other hand (*normative ethics*).

It is with no surprise that whether one is dealing with descriptive or normative ethics, depending upon the nature of the inquiry, one must deal with metaethics, the latter of which being concerned with the metaphysical, epistemological, logical, and psychological assumptions, presuppositions, and commitments to various moral concepts, expressions, attitudes, and practices. As such, some of the sorts of issues addressed concern the relationship between values, reasons, action, and human motivation posing such questions as: ‘How do moral standards provide reasons for or against compliance with the demands of these standards?’ (Sayre-McCord 2014). This, in turn, highlights the inclusive and all-encompassing nature of metaethical inquiry, given its aforementioned domain(s) of inquiry, intersecting in matters of governance, legality, and ethics. Yet, metaethical inquiry is not the only commonality shared among matters of governance, legality, and ethics. There is a factor all three share in common – value.

All three aforementioned approaches to responsibility – governmental, legal, and ethical – have a common concern for and with value, value-based claims, and claims regarding value. Accordingly, what all three “range over” or have in the extension of their respective analyses is

axiology (Schroeder Fall 2021).⁷ Some instances of this fact can be seen in the governmental concern for operationally implementing certain norms of parliamentary governance as well as, in the case of law, norms regarding due process. Why norms? This is because norms are tied to certain values, e.g.: representative democracy *vis-à-vis* dictatorship, the former being considered as a more “correct” structure due to its greater respect for autonomy, which is held as a “good”. Furthermore, all discussions concerning correctness with respect to a norm (i.e., compliance with it) or correctness of a norm (i.e., whether it instantiates the Good or a good, expressing an account of right action, or is consistent or conducive to an adequate account of being good) ultimately lead to a discussion of values, which will be discussed at length in the following chapters. This is no different in the case of responsibility. Though, the specific species of responsibility that chiefly concerns the discussion herein is moral in nature.

0.3 The Primacy of Ethics in Questions of Responsibility

The rational motivation for focusing on the ethical dimensions is twofold: (1) perceived state of the relationship between ethics, morality, and “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems (2) the indispensability of morality for the governance and legal fields. In the first, the serious treatment, outside of literature (e.g., science fiction, etc.), of the relationship between ethics, morality and artificial intelligence systems has, up until recently (a little over a decade), been deemphasized, being treated as an afterthought or periphery matter except by a small number of scientists, engineers, and ethicists. Of course, it did receive some serious treatment beforehand, but the discourse had not reached a critical threshold in terms of frequency, variety,

⁷ One could say: that upon which their respective extensions intersect is value or that they have value in the intersection of their respective extensions, etc. In this regard, see also: Wenceslao J. Gonzalez. 2013. “Value Ladenness and the Value-Free Ideal in Scientific Research.” in: Luetge, Christoph. (eds), *Handbook of the Philosophical Foundations of Business Ethics*, 1503–1521. Berlin: Springer, Dordrecht. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-007-1494-6_78, for a more focused discussion on the relationship between value, axiology, and technology.

and scope of serious discussion until a decade or so ago (Pereira and Lopes 2020). Moreover, the majority of research and serious discussion concerning this relationship, for much of the 20th century, was relegated to topics concerning the social and political implications of the development and use of such technology (Franssen, et.al 2018). Nowadays, there is a plethora of research and serious discussion centrally focused on better understanding the relationship between ethics, morality, and artificial intelligence systems, not just with respect to the technology's social and political implications, but also to that of its scientific and engineering core concepts (How 2018). Furthermore, the relevant research, *et cetera*, is presently ongoing. So, the current research approaches and shifted priorities are important to this exciting domain of inquiry so as to assist in creating greater conceptual clarity concerning the relationship between ethics, morality, and artificial intelligence as well as better decision-making concerning development and usage of such technology. We have no less than the future quality of the life of human civilization and the environment of the planet at stake.

In the second, namely: the indispensability of morality for the governance and legal fields, starting with governance, policies, strategies, and regulations often utilize elements from the domain of ethics in order to develop content for regulations and policies as well as to determine which governance strategies to pursue. Some examples of this are public health and safety policies, democracy, and establishing regulations concerning the distinction between private and public spheres of human daily life. Some of the tenets of ethics (and morality) borrowed and championed here are protection and promotion of the public good by minimizing conditions that would lead to pain whilst simultaneously attempting to maximize conditions conducive to happiness.⁸

⁸ However all of this is to be understood, depends on a great many factors too numerous to discuss at length here.

Furthermore, with legality, one way better to understand the relationship between it, on the one hand, and ethics and morality, on the other hand, is to consider the Rule of Law. The gist of the Rule of Law, within a system of governance, consists in the elevation of law *in quantum huiusmodi* as well as that of legal institutions. As such, The Rule of Law comprises principles of a procedural and formal nature. At its core, the formal requirements that give The Rule of Law substance and shape are such that ethics and morality are germane to their rational basis (King 1957, 1963; Kālin 2004); this even extends to determining specific legal content. For example, laws regarding property rights, held in many Western societies, would make little sense were it not for pre-existing moral ideas regarding autonomy, rights, the act of possessing or status of possession, and their relationship to material goods.⁹

Additionally, there is a strong connection between governance, at least in its ideal forms, and legality that can be understood by means of The Rule of Law, the latter of which in its core concept requires that authorities, in a governance context, exercise power in a constrained manner within a well-defined framework including well-established and publicly available norms, rather than in a discretionary manner based on privately held preferences and ideological commitments or on an *ad hoc* basis. Yet even here, this connection between governance and legality is informed by moral notions of impartiality and fairplay.

0.4 The Relevance of Ethics for Artificial Intelligence Systems

The foregoing explains, or so it is hoped, why the focus of this discussion concerning matters of responsibility is that of morality, namely: due to the general importance of the ethical. Be that as it may, there are also specific reasons why the ethical dimension takes centerstage. An

⁹ This would include even abstract goods, as is so in the case of intellectual property and the like.

“autonomous” artificial intelligence system is a technical artifact. The understanding here of technical artifacts being adopted, though not uncritically, from Peter Kroes’s treatment of them in his work entitled *Technical Artefacts: Creations of Mind and Matter* (Kroes 2012).¹⁰ As such, it has two broad-based aspects to its nature: (1) function (2) materiality. In its functional aspects, it is designed by someone to do something by means of certain instructions. That which it is to do is its aim, which it fulfills by means of following its instructions. This is pretty straightforward. In its material aspects, it is made up of certain materials (e.g., silicon, metal, plastic, wood, etc.), and that material plays some sort of causal role. In this dual nature account, the function, being some practical aim, is fulfilled by means of the causal aspects configured according to the satisfaction conditions pertaining to the design characteristics of its function (Kroes 2012, 1–11). One example of this would be a pen. It is designed to write, which is its primary function, at least from the perspective of certain stakeholders: its designers.¹¹ But it achieves its aim by means of being constructed out of material in a certain way such that it meets the conditions of satisfaction of its design characteristics pertaining to its function (i.e., to write).

What of the moral significance of technical artifacts? Although it was a rather popular view that technology is value free, and thereby morally neutral, deriving value from human responses to it, as well as its moral significance from how such technology is regarded and used, in recent years it has been acknowledged that technology is both value-laden and not morally neutral (Kroes 2012; Gonzalez 2013, 2015). Whence, however, does the moral significance of a technical artifact, which an “autonomous” artificial intelligence system is, come? Addressing this question is germane to the project of this book; and as such, it will be answered through the

¹⁰ Reasons in favor of adopting Peter Kroes’ view of technical artifacts will become clear through the course of the overall discussion of this book.

¹¹ It can, of course, fulfill other functions: it can be used to mark a place in a book or to stab someone as well. But none of these are its primary function, at least not with respect to its designer.

course of the discussion of this book and the significance of that answer will be laid bare. For now, it is simply important to highlight the relevance context for the inquiry, the latter of whose solution will be pursued in what follows.

0.5 Aim of the Project of this Book

The aim, then, of this research project is to investigate whether ethics can be established “internally” within “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems in such a way so as to show that they are performing some type of ethical analysis in virtue of an internal set of instructions and architecture and by means of ethical design norms in addition to whatever engineering design norm requirements that need to be satisfied as well as to provide an explicit characterization of an ethically prospective approach to ethics of artificial intelligence, instead of an ethically retrospective “troubleshooting” approach. Moreover, it is hoped that some of the benefits that would result from this twofold aim are that the ethically prospective approach would also provide a way to optimize value-based engineering efforts, to assist in localizing or narrowing down the moral responsibility assessment to a clearly defined set of stakeholders, thereby providing an answer to the intuitive interrogative which began the mainstay inquiry of this project, all of which, or so it is hoped, and can strengthen policy recommendations regarding use of such systems in various social roles.

The upshot here being: in the project of this book, the author attempts to provide a systematic way to select from the class of all possible values a specific subset of values to be embedded and implemented, in the relevant sense, within “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems. It is hoped that this specific subset of values constitutes the value basis which simultaneously can be embedded and implemented, serving as a way to shore up the engineering

endeavors and the technological development lifecycle along even more ethically robust grounds than they are at present. In expressing this hope, the author is neither denying that previous efforts and endeavors ethically to regulate the relevant technology have merit nor is the author claiming or assuming that efforts in this regard are valid or effective only if they are “internal” in the relevant sense. Rather, the author has great respect and gratitude for previous efforts and endeavors ethically to regulate “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems as well as other relevant technology. Nevertheless, just as in child-rearing, a parent relies on both external and internal measures ethically to regulate one’s child’s moral behavior, so too the author attempts to develop rigorous and systematic internal measures ethically to regulate “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems. These measures, as is so in child-rearing, are not meant to replace external measures, but to complement them. Furthermore, as is also true in child-rearing, when inculcating values into one’s children, not just any moral values will do, no less is true for the relevant technical systems. Naturally, not just any internal measures will do, only a specific subset of well reasoned moral values will qualify.

The reason why this is important reflects a historical shift in concern regarding the ethical import of machines. From the beginning of the 21st century until the present, the discipline of machine ethics has picked up momentum (Anderson & Anderson 2011; Pereira and Lopes 2020). Of course, concern for the ethical dimensions of machines preceded the incipience of the field of machine ethics, this being something that is neither denied nor ignored in machine ethics. Yet, in machine ethics there were two important shifts in understanding that are relevant for this project.

The first shift in understanding involved wondering whether it was possible that a machine would be ethical in some internal sense, with the question being something like: ‘How

does one get a machine (e.g., an “autonomous” artificial intelligence system) to do ethics?’. This interrogative expressed something far different than a query concerning a machine’s output or behavior conforming to, say, norms of morality or moral norms; such a query would be about mere ethical compliance, a concern of which represents nothing new (Moor 2006). The enhanced inquiry expressed by the interrogative concerned whether a machine’s output could be ethically compliant by means of its own internal programming in such a way that insofar as it was, its programming was executing some form of ethical analysis from a defined set of ethical principles, maxims, and certain heuristics (Ibid.; Wallach 2008).

The second shift in understanding involved adoption of both of the aforementioned workstreams of philosophy of technology, namely: social and political implications and scientific and engineering aspects of technology. This can be seen in the concern not just for impartial and intelligible outputs of “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems, but with the very inner workings of such systems so as to better track the nature of the relationship between the science and engineering aspects, on the one hand, and the social and political implications of the development, upkeep, and deployment of such technological systems, on the other hand. This can also be seen in such movements, arguably, within machine ethics as well as “ethically aligned design”, and “value-based engineering”, and other prospective visions for the relationship between ethics and technology instead of the retrospective visions dominant in the 20th century (Gonzalez 2013; Franssen, et al. 2018; How 2018).

As a unit of analysis, however, the specific moral concept that will be the focus of investigation for the current discussion will be moral responsibility. The foregoing specifies some of the reasons for this, but this bears repeating and elaboration with respect to a larger set of reasons guiding this choice of focus on moral responsibility. The first reason is that it is rather

topical. That is to say, it is a current rather pressing issue nowadays. This, of course, explains why *responsibility* as a concept applied to technology is the focus. The second reason, which explains why *moral* responsibility is the focus, is due the primacy and relevance of moral inquiry, which was touched on above. The third reason is germane to the mainstay line of inquiry of this book, namely: that of attempting to provide strong reasons to believe that ethics can be established internally to “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems: a line of rational inquiry consistent with the sense of “in” meant by James Moor in his discussion of machine ethics (See: Moor 2006, 18–21). Accordingly, the investigation will focus on whether there is or can be developed a viable account of moral responsibility for “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems as well as to attempt to answer the question, namely: ‘What would ground such an account (i.e., provide the principled reasons in virtue of which such an account is viable)?’

The word ‘account’, however, can be rather ambivalent. Therefore, it is important to be clear on just what is meant insofar as this word plays a central role in communicating the aim of the current project. The ambivalence in question is due to the fact that in popular parlance it can mean either: (1) a particular description or narrative of an event, circumstance, or situation (2) an explanation of conduct to some form of authority.¹² However, the word in question is being used as a philosophical term; hence, not according to popular parlance. So, neither sense is exactly what is meant here by the word ‘account’ nor is the intended sense completely divorced from these two. To understand the intended sense of the word ‘account’ herein, consider that ‘account’ comes from the gerund ‘accounting’, as in the phrase ‘to give an accounting of’, which means to give an adequate explanation. Thus, the word ‘account’ is associated with the concept of explanation. Appropriately, then, the word ‘account’ is herein used synonymously with ‘model’,

¹²*Collins English Dictionary*, s.v. “Account,” accessed multiple times, last being: April 08, 2023, <https://www.dictionary.com/browse/account>.

because it is tied both to the explanatory function models perform (more on this in what follows) and the notion of explanation which underlies the popular meanings of the word ‘account’.

In fact, models play a crucial role in intellectual inquiry helping to facilitate it by adding such things as greater clarity, simplification of complex datasets, amelioration of difficulties with combinatorial *prima facie* complexity, rigor, ease-of-analysis, *et cetera*, as well as allowing for better comparison of relevant aspects for inquiry, along with facilitation of testing hypotheses and the like. Furthermore, models come in multifarious sorts. “*Probing models, phenomenological models, computational models, developmental models, explanatory models, impoverished models, testing models, idealized models, theoretical models, scale models, heuristic models, caricature models, exploratory models, didactic models, fantasy models, minimal models, toy models, imaginary models, mathematical models, mechanistic models, substitute models, iconic models, formal models, analogue models, and instrumental models* are but some of the notions that are used to categorize models (Frigg & Hartmann 2020).” Moreover, there can be hybrid models consisting of a blend of several categories of models, the composite of which possessing unique features. For this project, a hybrid model is intended. This is because this model is extrapolated from several factors. The multifaceted nature, relevance, and usefulness of such a model will become clearer throughout the course of this investigation.

With the importance of the topic, the paramountcy of the particular orientation to the topic adopted for the discussion contained within this book, namely: the focus on ethics, as well as the aim of this project having been laid bare, it is crucial to gain further clarity regarding key elements of this project. To this end, the relationship between metaethics, ethics, and morality, within the parameters of this discussion will next be clarified followed by a discussion of the approach of the project of this book.

0.6 Clarification of the Nature of the Domain: Metaethics, Ethics & Morality

Ethics, being its own domain of inquiry, lies at the heart of the discussion of this book. And whereas the concerns of metaethics, given the nature of its inquiry (see above), can focus on the very nature of ethics – including its relationship to the broader class of axiology¹³ – ethics is understood, broadly speaking, as the “science of morality”. Ethics so being, its inquiry into this domain need not only be formal, but empirical as well (2005 Musschenga). Moreover, within the Western tradition, the moral landscape is textured and shaped by certain priorities, issues, positions, and approaches. Without going into copious details thereof, as that falls outside the purview of the present discussion, there are three main guiding interrogatives which have driven ethical inquiry forward: (1) ‘What is the nature of the Good?’(2) ‘What is right action?’(3) ‘How can one be good?’¹⁴

In the first, namely: ‘What is the nature of the Good?’, this interrogative serves to designate the set of concerns regarding the Good. Some of these reflect queries regarding ontological matters concerning the Good, as the formulation of the designating interrogative would suggest. These queries would include addressing sortal questions with respect to the Good (Wiggins 2001).¹⁵ Some of these queries would concern related ontological inquiries about the Good, for example, “‘In virtue of what is the “Good” good?’, ‘How do we individuate the

¹³ One such question concerning the relationship between ethics and axiology more broadly understood would be: ‘What value does ethics itself have?’ and relatedly, ‘Why should anyone care about ethics?’. Yet, it also extends to such questions as, ‘Why should ethics constitute its own domain of inquiry?’. Moreover, an extended discussion concerning the nature of axiology and how it relates to both ethics and value will be featured in the next chapter of this book.

¹⁴ The author explores all three of these interrogatives of ethical inquiry in, “Racial Oppression and Violence: Right Action v. The Good.” *Violence - Protest - Inequality from an Ethical Perspective*, Zürich: TVZ (Forthcoming in December 2023). This portion of the current discussion relies on the ideas therein.

¹⁵ David Wiggins’s 2001 discusses the idea of a sortal in his, *Sameness and Substance Renewed*. Cambridge, England: Cambridge University Press. Therein, the word ‘sortal’ is used in the sense of the type of thing something is. In this way, providing the sortal of something is an answer to the ‘what is it?’ question for that thing.

Good?’ ‘What is the relationship between the “Good” and individual concrete goods (e.g., equal opportunity)?’” (Butler, Forthcoming in 2023, 9).¹⁶ Some would be epistemological in nature:

‘How do we come to know the Good as the Good?’

With the second, namely: ‘What is right action?’, this interrogative also designates a set of moral concerns. These concerns can be formulated as follows: ‘What is the right thing to do?’, ‘What are the right actions to take?’, ‘What constitutes wrong action?’, ‘When is inaction wrong?’, ‘What makes an action morally correct or incorrect?’, ‘How is right action to be determined?’, ‘How can we come to know what right or wrong action is?’

In the third, namely: ‘How can one be good?’, the interrogative, designating a class of moral concerns, focuses on such questions as: ‘What are mental states, behaviors, habits, and tendencies concomitant with the Good?’, ‘What is vice?’, ‘What is virtue?’, ‘What role (if any) does one’s environment play in the formation of moral character?’, ‘What role (if any) does one’s genetic make up play in the formation of moral character?’, ‘Are there things like moral character traits?’, ‘Is there any difference between moral and non-moral mental states?’, ‘How does one become better morally?’

Now, these interrogatives are not meant to be exhaustive of the types of issues, positions, priorities, preferences, and approaches, yet they remain useful for the intelligibility of this discussion as well as intuitive. They do so by representing three main groupings of dominant sets of concerns within the domain of ethics in the Western philosophical/theological tradition, and thus aid in characterizing the domain of inquiry in terms of some of its distinctive features. All the same, some theologians might take issue with being grouped together with philosophers in terms of a shared ethical outlook that can be called “Western”. If so, this would be, at the very least, undoubtedly due to the historical tensions existing between the two disciplines. Mutually,

¹⁶ The page number cited here is from the pre-published version of this article.

some philosophers might also resist this grouping or downplay its value. The *bona fide* differences in outlook, approach, *et cetera* notwithstanding, the value of these interrogatives is difficult to contest, as they are representative of the mainstay of shared concerns both disciplines have inherited as part of the Western intellectual preoccupation and lived-shared experience of their respective practitioners within the societal-cultural history of the West. Furthermore, these interrogatives are intuitively appealing insofar as they track the phenomenology of clusters of moral concerns of both professional philosophers and theologians as well as everyday persons, at least within and as influenced by Western cultural history, whilst simultaneously helping to organize the cluster of moral concerns based on discernable patterns.¹⁷

Despite this attempt clearly to characterize the domain of ethics for this discussion, some may take issue with this latter point, namely: that the aforementioned ethical interrogatives track and organize the phenomenology of moral concerns, objecting that individualistic phenomenological difference would mitigate the accuracy of this attempt to organize moral concerns, thereby the organizational schema would not clearly characterize ethics, as it was previously claimed, as the science of morality.

This objection, in its emphasis on subjective difference, misses, however, the intersubjective (Davidson 2001). Individuals share a social imaginary (Castoriadis 1987). This means that the individual phenomenology each has is, to a large extent, though not solely, shaped and structured by the social phenomenological matrix in which the individual resides: the intersubjective field of conscious experience and its concomitant signs, symbols, and artifacts. Consequently, this phenomenological matrix would provide a structure shaping conscious

¹⁷ The comments regarding “the West” and organization of moral concerns, *et cetera*, is not tantamount to or in any way suggesting that these ways of organizing moral concerns is peculiar to the West. The author makes no such ‘East vs. West’ generalizations here, and acknowledges that this taxonomy of moral concerns is not mutually exclusive with the philosophical and theological thought of the East broadly construed.

experience yielding a recognizable ordering which would include, but certainly not be limited to, moral concerns and the like. This would mitigate the aforementioned individualistic phenomenological difference in favor of a shared *Lebenswelt* that would shape lived experience including what types of value-based concerns are had (Keen 1975). Nonetheless, one might rejoin that reflection upon everyday social experience would uncover that even within a shared social imaginary there is enough individualistic phenomenological difference so as to weaken support from lived human experience in favor of organizing moral concerns in the manner in question.

In response to this rejoinder, it is important to note the conspicuous feature of one's everyday social experience, namely: that moral concerns, if emphasized at all, vary greatly between individuals. This is hard to deny. Yet, the variation is not unrestricted. Its limits are circumscribed by the culture and society in which individuals find themselves.¹⁸ This encultured society would have certain ways of collective and individual self-understanding, modes of life, and ways for seeing and interacting with its environment and for its members with respect to themselves and the world at large. From this would arise certain discernable patterns of activity and behavior with boundary conditions, sometimes hard to discern boundary conditions, but they are nonetheless present. Hence, there would indeed be both individualistic phenomenological differences and shared understanding and ways of being-in-the-world (Dreyfus 1990).

Furthermore, the thrust of the objection is a good one, namely: subjectivity; that is, if we are to base our conception of morality on conscious lived experience, to any extent, we must take human subjectivity seriously. All the same, due to the social dimensions of human life, if we are

¹⁸ These limits are also circumscribed by one's embodiment, a discussion of which falls outside the purview of the mainstay inquiry of this book. Nonetheless, for an illuminating discussion along these lines, see Joseph T.F. Roberts 2023 article entitled "Taking Embodiment Seriously in Ethics and Political Philosophy" *Journal of Value Inquiry*, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10790-023-09952-7>.

to take conscious lived experience seriously, we must take intersubjectivity seriously as well. A fine line needs to be walked here. For it is important not to endorse any sort of facile relativism, whilst simultaneously taking the perspectival nature – whether personal (i.e., subjective) or collective (i.e., intersubjective) – of this or that moral position seriously. The upshot here: it being prudent to acknowledge the dependent conditions (whether they be sufficiency, necessity, methodological soundness, relevance, fittingness, dynamic balance, practicability, pragmaticity, etc.) of a particular moral view in relation to its truth-conditions without endorsing some form of incoherence, the latter of which being exemplified by such claims, keeping in mind the universe of discourse here being ethics¹⁹, as “Everything is relative.” Such unrestricted relativism naturally provides its own *reductio ad absurdum* thereby trivially defeating itself. Though, its self-defeating nature is by no means trivial. As it points to the needful fine balance in question, and of which is recommended for this discussion (and more generally).

What of morality then? If ethics is the science of it, what is this target of investigation? To answer this question, it is tempting to start with a definition. For it is a straightforward and useful way to provide clarity and focus to a discussion of such complex topics as this one. Though, providing a definition of morality is no small task. This is because such an enterprise is fraught with substantial challenges. These substantial challenges are disunity and ambivalence, arbitrariness and scope of application, methodological circularity, and issues pertaining to the distinction between substantive/non-substantive²⁰. These difficulties will be addressed in turn.

Disunity and Ambivalence. Is the domain whose name is ‘morality’ unified enough to constitute a domain of inquiry? To this question, some would provide a negative answer, and it

¹⁹ Evaluating moral claims or positions based upon their truth-value may not always be appropriate. As such, “conditions of satisfaction” is likely the more appropriate evaluative criterion due to it being sufficiently general to be explicated either as truth-conditions or another relevant notion.

²⁰ This list is not meant to be exhaustive, rather only to capture some key difficulties both relevant for this discussion and illustrative of the problem of defining morality.

would not be entirely obvious that it would be incorrect to provide such an answer. This is because moral judgements, for example, suffer from a delimiting problem. This problem consists in a difficulty in individuating them from other types of judgements. The rub, here, is that if key members of this domain – judgements – cannot be well-individuated, then this would call into question the unity and uniqueness of morality as a domain of inquiry in its own right (Sinnott-Armstrong & Wheatley 2012; Gert & Gert 2020).

The delimiting problem is threefold: (1) by content (2) by neurobiology (3) by group-inclusion parameters (Ibid.). In the first, namely: by content, it is difficult to account for behaviors that are considered to be moral, when one attempts to isolate what judgements motivated the behavioral response. For example, one might consider it morally impermissible not to lie. But what is it about this judgment that makes it moral, *per se*, as opposed to simply prudent? The problem here with content is that the content of a moral judgment seems not to determine *in virtue of what* is the judgment moral. In the second, namely: by neurobiology, there does not seem to be neural correlate(s) of moral judgements, even if one holds the broad-based view that mental states supervene on brain states (Kim 2003).²¹ In the third, namely: by group-inclusion parameters, it is difficult to establish whether the judgements against the practice of lying are particularly moral in nature or simply sociological, namely: promoting group coherence, or prudent: to maintain credibility of its members (Sinnott-Armstrong & Wheatley 2012; Gert & Gert 2020).

Concerning ambivalence, there are two senses according to which one can understand morality: (1) descriptive (2) normative, which have their concomitant approaches and were

²¹ Recall that this doctrine holds that mental property, state, *et cetera*, A supervenes on physical property, state, *et cetera*, B just in case there can be no change in the mental property, state ... A without a change also in the physical property, state ... B. In the form of a slogan, “there cannot be an A-difference without a B-difference” (McLaughlin and Bennett 2021).

touched upon above. The problem of ambivalence here arises when a sense of morality and approach to it *prima facie* adopts one sense and approach, but really oscillates between both senses and their concomitant approaches. This can occur in cases where the author is not explicit in the beginning as to which sense is meant, etc (Gert & Gert 2020).

Arbitrariness and scope of application. The arising of the problem of arbitrariness and scope depend on which sense of morality one has in mind. If meant in the descriptive sense, one is vulnerable to arbitrariness unless one is able to justify why a particular extant moral code, or the like, is utilized as opposed to any other available. Relatedly, one would be vulnerable to having, in virtue of choosing an extant moral code, an understanding of morality that is too narrow in scope.

Methodological circularity. This can result when one understands morality in the normative sense, and can be seen upon considering the hallmark of a normative approach to morality, an approach focusing on broad-based rational features under certain conditions, namely: that “all rational persons, under certain specified conditions, would endorse it” (Ibid.). The problem, though, arises when one attempts to provide that which fits the criterion. For in doing so, what would one say? Universal rational consistency (a deontological approach)? Maximizing utility (a utilitarian approach)? Maximizing pleasures without corresponding pains (something akin to an epicurean approach)? Would it be to achieve some idea of virtuous living, however that is explicated (a virtue ethics approach)? Whatever one would choose would assume, or at the very least run the risk of assuming, the truth of an ethical theory. But without providing independent reasons why one should endorse such a theory’s claims, one would be assuming the truth of such claims and incorporating them into one’s normative sense of morality, which would, from a methodological standpoint, be circular.

Substantive/Non-Substantive. There is an outstanding issue, in terms of sense and approach to morality that has metaethical implications, namely: whether to understand ethics as there really being something to it, whether one is a realist or an antirealist, on the one hand, or understanding ethics as a way to identify and explain certain emotions or their expressions and certain behavioral or physiological responses (e.g., shame, blame, and praise), on the other hand. To view ethics in that latter sense is to view it as something non-substantive, which is not necessarily viewing it as an antirealist, but such views can go hand-in-hand.²² An anti-realist would not endorse the view that moral properties or structures exist mind-independently awaiting discovery by means of the correct methodology or the like. Rather, they would hold that they exist mind-dependently, like say: as a socially constructed reality. On this view, morality would not exist over and above the intersubjective field of human experience. Yet, such an anti-realist would not deny that there is any substance to morality. On the other hand, a non-substantive view of morality would view it as purely a means of explaining emotional, behavioral, or physiological responses, not properties, structures, entities, *et cetera*, actually grounded in the subjective or intersubjective field of human experience. Furthermore, the way such views could go hand-in-hand is to say that the non-substantive view is a species of anti-realism concerning morality. Of course, the substantive view would be the negation of the non-substantive view.

Non-substantive views present a problem for defining morality in that they depart wildly from one's lived experience with respect to moral concerns, preferences, and even intentions. From this lived perspective, what one understands by 'morality' is more than just explaining emotional, behavioral, or physiological responses. But with a substantive view, one must explain

²² There is a lack of consensus concerning what realism and antirealism consists in, so some may disagree with how the author understands how either relates to morality. This is all well and good, and as it should be. For more on some of this, the author encourages the reader to consider Richard Joyce's 2022 publication, "Moral Anti-Realism", *The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy* (Winter Edition), Edward N. Zalta & Uri Nodelman (eds.), URL = <<https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/win2022/entries/moral-anti-realism/>>.

what grounds the semantic content of moral claims or what the conditions of satisfaction criteria are for propositional attitudes concerning morality and the like, all of which are fraught with, at the very least, the other three aforementioned problems (challenges) of delimitation.

0.7 Conceptual Tools and Approach of the Project of this Book

In an effort to avoid all of the aforementioned problems, a characterization of morality designed to function as a broad-based template for patterns of moral concerns, preferences, specific judgements, and the like is put forth. This characterization is posited so as to avoid referential vagueness and semantic ambivalence in order to provide some substance to the domain of inquiry possessing the name ‘morality’; or so it is hoped. This characterization is intended to be workable; that is, it is not intended to define morality, not intended to be an exhaustive treatment, nor to constitute a pivotal feature of a grand unified ethical theory pertaining to “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems. Rather, it is intended to be a useful conceptual tool. Simultaneously, this template is to balance both descriptive and normative senses of morality and their respective concomitant approaches, being a middle-ground between the two. The nature of the template in question is constructed as follows. It consists of four parameters: (1) benevolence (2) impartiality and intelligibility (3) respect for personhood and self-representationality (4) substitutional accountability. Each parameter will be treated in turn.

Benevolence. This parameter is rather straightforward. One way to appreciate its relevance is to consider one expression as to why ethics matters in dealing with “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems, “Ethics is important. We want machines to treat us well” (Moor 2006, 21). Moreover, for the type of machine in question to be counted as treating humans well,

it must at least not be harmful, and even promote human wellness and wellbeing: not detract, but promote human flourishing.

This parameter seems without little to contest its inclusion, though it would benefit from a brief historical contextualization so as to promote understanding. As aforementioned, from the mid-20th century until the present, philosophy of technology has consisted of two workstreams: (1) that which focused on the scientific and engineering aspects of technology and (2) that which focused on the social and political implications of the development, maintenance, and use of technology (Franssen, et al. 2018). With the second focus, the concern for the social and political implications of technology was, quite naturally, connected to human flourishing.

Impartiality and intelligibility. This parameter is to promote unbiased judgements that make sense to those affected by them. Moreover, it would mean that outputs of an “autonomous” artificial intelligence system utilized to assist, or even replace, the judgements of a human person in some social situation are not unduly favoring the interests of any particular group, not motivated out of a prejudice concerning the person or persons affected by the decision(s), nor favoring some unjustified ideological commitment or idiosyncrasy of those responsible for the judgment (e.g., in determinations concerning recidivism, see: Haas 2017 and Northpointe 2015).²³ Yet, it would also mean that the judgements are clear and make sense: explainable.

As such, opacity would need to be controlled for or ideally ruled out entirely. This is a problem with “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems, especially with those of blackboxed “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems. Though blackboxed systems of the relevant sort are not the only ones that need be concerned with opacity, it is a peculiarly nasty problem for such

²³ In many ways, the requirements here are reminiscent of those associated with good governance touched on above, namely: exercising of power in a constrained manner within a well-defined framework including well-established and publicly available norms, rather than in a discretionary manner based on privately held preferences and ideological commitments or on an *ad hoc* basis.

systems. These sorts of systems, as well as others, will be discussed at greater length later in the current discussion.

As was true of the parameter of benevolence, this parameter would also benefit from historical contextualization so as to promote understanding. From the beginning of the 21st century until the present, the discipline of machine ethics has picked up momentum (Anderson & Anderson 2011; Pereira & Lopes 2020). Of course, concern for the ethical dimensions of machines preceded the incipience of the field of machine ethics, this being something that is neither denied nor ignored in machine ethics. Yet, in machine ethics there were two important shifts in understanding that are relevant for this project.

The first shift in understanding involved wondering whether it was possible that a machine would be ethical in some *internal sense*, with the question being something like: ‘How does one get a machine (e.g., an “autonomous” artificial intelligence system) to do ethics?’. This interrogative expressed something far different than a query concerning a machine’s output or behavior conforming to, say, norms of morality or moral norms; this would be mere ethical compliance, a concern of which represents nothing new (Moor 2006). The enhanced inquiry expressed by the interrogative concerned whether a machine’s output could be ethically compliant by means of its own internal programming in such a way that insofar as it was, its programming was executing some form of ethical analysis from a defined set of ethical principles, maxims, and certain heuristics (Ibid.; Wallach 2008).

The second shift in understanding involved adoption of both of the aforementioned workstreams of philosophy of technology, namely: social and political implications and scientific and engineering aspects of technology. This can be seen in the concern not just for impartial and intelligible outputs of “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems, but with the very inner

workings of such systems so as to better track the nature of the relationship between the science and engineering aspects, on the one hand, and the social and political implications of the development, upkeep, and deployment of such technological systems, on the other hand. This can also be seen in such movements, arguably, within machine ethics as well as “ethically aligned design”²⁴ initiatives and prospective visions for the relationship between ethics and technology instead of the retrospective visions dominant in the 20th century (Gonzalez 2013; Franssen, et al. 2018; How 2018).

Respect for personhood and self-representationality. The heart of this parameter is rooted in autonomy. This sense of ‘autonomy’ comes from philosophy, and refers to the capacity to provide one’s own customs, norms, rules, and laws for oneself, all of which are based on the ability to think of and select freely which of these one wishes to follow (EGESNT 2018). Having and exercising such autonomy requires certain cognitive processes which were traditionally thought to facilitate and enable this, namely: rationality, freewill, and self-awareness (Ibid; Levine 2004). Moreover, autonomy in this sense is traditionally thought to be the cornerstone of what makes us, in the fullest sense, dignified human persons. It is in virtue of this sense of autonomy, possessed of human persons, that respect for personhood and how a human person self-represents (and self-understands) is to be respected.

All of this becomes peculiarly relevant in dealing with “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems. For there are two key questions to consider in this regard which have great implications for moral responsibility: Is the sense of ‘autonomous’, here, identical? What are the implications of a positive or negative answer to the preceding question? In virtue of these

²⁴ The IEEE Global Initiative on Ethics of Autonomous and Intelligent Systems .2019. “Ethically Aligned Design: A Vision for Prioritizing Human Well-being with Autonomous and Intelligent Systems.” *IEEE Advancing Technology for Humanity*, available online: https://standards.ieee.org/content/dam/ieee-standards/standards/web/documents/other/ead_v2.pdf (accessed 01.06.2022).

considerations, the parameter of the template in question takes on special significance within the context of moral responsibility and the establishment of ethics in “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems. This significance will be explored further through the course of the discussion of this book.

Substitutional accountability. The basic idea behind this parameter can be seen in the concept of oversight. In a context of oversight, for example: within that of an organization, there is someone to whom another must answer or provide a response to regarding one’s judgements and behavior. This idea of oversight as understood in an organizational context is, in its basecase context, social in nature. As such, it constitutes one of many social requirements. Moreover, this idea of oversight lies at the heart of the concept underpinning the parameter in question: accountability.

Accordingly, any person in a social role must fulfill the social requirements of that role, and one of these requirements is moral accountability.²⁵ Furthermore, any entity, for example: an “autonomous” artificial intelligence system (e.g., an “autonomous” artificial institutional adviser), filling a traditionally human role in the public space must fulfill the social requirements of that role, one of which just is moral accountability (Bostrom and Yudkowsky 2014, 316–334).

Additionally, two things are noteworthy. The first is that this requirement, bespoken of by the parameter of *substitutional accountability*, draws its merit in the current discussion by referring directly to the problem for “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems of enforceability. The problem can be expressed well in asking: ‘How can moral accountability be enforced for an “autonomous” artificial intelligence system?’. In the second and closely connect

²⁵ Even if a case can be made that the relevant species of accountability be organizational, for example: in accordance with the constitution or bylaws of a particular organization, the content of the constitution or bylaws would not be determinable apart from moral accountability, as was the case with governmental or legal forms of responsibility. This, of course, would not necessarily mean that the content of those bylaws or constitutional statements would need to be overtly moral, namely: making explicit moral claims. It is enough that they implicitly rely on moral claims for the relevance of moral accountability.

to the first, the concepts of moral accountability and moral responsibility need to be brought into dialogue so as to discern the difference between (if any). For whether they are the same or not influences how we are to understand some of the significant implications of whether ethics can be established as an internal feature of “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems. This is latter justification will, it is hoped, become clearer through the course of this overall discussion.

Now the reader may have noticed that there is a peculiar isomorphism that exists between the domains of metaethics, ethics, and morality in terms of approach. As is true in approaches to modern metaphysics, so too in modern metaethics: there are descriptive approaches and revisionary approaches. In the former, we take the structure of human thought and language as a given, expressing some basic indispensable conceptual scheme, and attempt to account for the phenomena and experiences of the world around us in terms of first-principles and fundamental structures therefrom. In the latter, we seek to find a better conceptual scheme to account for the phenomena and experiences of the world around us in terms of first-principles and fundamental structures based on this superior conceptual scheme. In the first, the task is descriptive in nature, in the second normative in nature (Strawson 1959; Snowdon and Gomes 2019). Moreover, what is true in the case of metaphysics, more broadly understood, and in the case of metaethics, is true for ethics and morality: there are both descriptive and normative approaches in defining their content and in pursuit of their research projects, respectively.

In review, the aforementioned template is intended to be workable; that is, it is not intended to define morality, not intended to be an exhaustive treatment, nor to constitute a pivotal feature of a grand unified ethical theory pertaining to “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems. Rather, it is intended to be a useful conceptual tool. Additionally, it is to balance both descriptive and normative senses of morality and their respective concomitant approaches, being

a middle-ground between the two, whilst being sensitive towards and dynamic in the face of this isomorphism that exists between the domains of metaethics, ethics, and morality (more on this later).

Mention of the enforceability issue brings, quite naturally, the concept of moral responsibility into sharper focus. In line with this, the author acknowledges that moral responsibility and moral accountability are not selfsame. As to just what is meant by ‘moral responsibility’ and ‘moral accountability’ as well as the precise nature of the relationship between the two concepts within the overall discussion of this book is something that will be clarified in *Conceptual Tools I: 1.5.3*. It suffices for now to state the following. Moral responsibility is herein understood in such a way that assigning it to an agent A involves attributing to A certain capacities (e.g., to speak) and powers (e.g., the freedom to do otherwise) along with viewing A’s actions as issuing forth from those powers and capacities in the right way such that those actions are a result of exercising those powers and capacities possessed by A. Accordingly, the understanding of moral responsibility adopted for this project is structural in nature: focusing on whether some entity of a certain sort has the right relationship to its actions (or inactions), and not in terms of obligations and duties that this entity has. The benefit of such an approach is that it bodes to have greater generalizability based on class membership (i.e., being a certain sort of entity). It is hoped this generalizability along with other factors related to justification, explanation, methodology, and logic would control for question begging with respect to the sorts of entities of which moral responsibility is predicated as well as ward off various chauvinistic answers and approaches to the relationship between moral responsibility and “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems.

With this structural understanding of moral responsibility in mind, then, the author will attempt to establish ethics as an internal feature of “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems. What this means as well as how this effort relates to moral responsibility is as follows. In the first, it means that the author will attempt to develop a moral framework that can be embedded into an “autonomous” artificial intelligence system and that can simultaneously shape and govern the design, development, and deployment (i.e., utilization in society)²⁶ of this class of technical systems. In the second, moral responsibility is a premiere concept within ethics as a domain of inquiry and a most topical moral concept for “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems nowadays. As such, it is an ideal unit of analysis and candidate to utilize in an effort to develop a basis for the establishment of ethics as an internal feature, in the relevant sense, of these technical systems. To put it simply: if it can be shown that moral responsibility can be assigned to “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems in virtue of those entities having certain powers and capacities standing in the right relationship to their behavioral outcomes such that it can be said that they are morally responsible for such behavioral outcomes, then this would go a long way towards the establishment of properties, moral properties, *et cetera*, – whose purview is ethics – as something internal to such technical systems. Accordingly, this would also go a long way towards addressing the enhanced inquiry presented by machine ethics, namely: “... whether you can put ethics into a machine. Can a computer operate ethically because it’s internally ethical in some way?” (Moor 2006, 19).

As an aid in this pursuit, the author will attempt to address the following research questions: Is there a viable account or model whereby and through which ethics can be established as an internal feature of artificial intelligence systems? Should it turn out that moral

²⁶ ‘Deployment’ in the English language is often associated with military matters. The author doesn’t intend such a narrow usage, hence the parenthetical note. Moreover, the author prefers usage of this word due to it aiding in creating an alliteration. This alliteration is preferred, as it is a rather useful memory aid.

responsibility cannot be attributed to “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems, then the work presented within the parameters of this project would not be null and void; but rather, at least would have laid bear a viable theoretical basis for the implementation of a moral framework and key moral values as design norms, along with accepted engineering design norms (Wallach & Allen 2008), for the creation of “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems governed by a prospective approach concerning ethics, rather than a retrospective “troubleshooting-ad-hoc” approach and for the optimization of regulating technology development along similar lines as well as for shoring up technology public policy geared towards regulating “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems. Furthermore, the author will address the question, namely: How would such an account be justified? From a metalogical perspective with respect to argument strategies, the mainstay justification in support of establishing ethics as an internal feature of “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems is a proof by construction. Accordingly, both a practice-oriented conceptual framework and model will be constructed and contextualized, being brought under scrutiny for viability, and implications discussed; or so the author will attempt.

Now for this project, along with the aforementioned ethical template, the use of a choice methodology are germane to its execution this methodology is that of philosophical analysis, and it will be employed in its more general contours as well as in its more specific forms, namely: metaethical and ethical analysis, both of which in terms of their usage within this project are subspecies of philosophical analysis. But what makes an analysis philosophical in the sense relevant for this project? Moreover, what are ethical and metaethical analysis? These are rather complex issues. But one way to begin to address these questions is to consider one indispensable feature of philosophical analysis. Philosophical analysis is first-principle-based, providing *the reasons in virtue of which X, for some X, is the case*. For example, providing what would justify

in terms of first-principle-based considerations or considerations derivative of a first-principle-based approach a putative viable moral framework and model whereby one can, at the very least, establish ethics as an internal feature of an “autonomous” artificial intelligence system or at most correctly attribute moral responsibility to such technical systems. Moreover, philosophical analysis, in providing such justifications, grounding, or other endeavors, would utilize conceptual analysis in its ideal forms. In fact, the mainstay of philosophical analysis elucidates what makes ethical analysis distinctive.

Ethical analysis is the application of conceptual analysis broadly construed in its idealized forms, namely: its methods, techniques, strategies, principles, heuristics, rules-of-thumb, *et cetera*, to morality as a domain of inquiry. For instance, consider typology: recalling that it is, broadly construed, the study of classification according to general types (Rescher 2007, 69–84). Typology is used in various disciplines, the latter of which using various parameters for their respective systems of classification; and as such, applying general principles of typology indexed to the peculiarities and demands of each discipline in which typology has gained purchase as a worthwhile method or methodology.²⁷ So too, typology gains purchase in a treatment of morality as a domain of inquiry. This was evidenced above by the discussion concerning the interrogative classes that traditional moral concerns may be classified. In fact, much of the foregoing material in this very introduction is an example of ethical analysis: attempting to show and not merely tell what ethical analysis is by means of not only defining it, or at the very least characterizing ethical analysis, but more importantly demonstrating its shape and contours. Furthermore, what is true of ethical analysis applies *mutatis mutandis* to metaethical analysis. Lastly, and some of this bears repeating for emphasis and clarity: within the

²⁷ The soundness of the general characterization of typology notwithstanding, of course, there can be disagreements regarding typology’s usefulness for this or that discipline or even as to how well it is applied within a given discipline.

parameters of the overall discussion of this book, philosophical analysis overlaps by and large with both ethical and metaethical analysis, the latter two being subspecies of the former and having a more narrow focus in terms of domain of inquiry, whereas philosophical analysis has a much wider domain of inquiry and application.

In the service of accomplishing the aim of this project, the work needing-to-be-done will be executed over three phases. In the first, the problematic and its relevant context are articulated; and in so doing, the following intuitive question, namely: ‘When behavior of an “autonomous” artificial intelligence system(s) leads to harm or death of someone, who is responsible?’, is used as a stepping off point for the inquiry herein (*Introduction*). In the second, a practice-oriented conceptual framework and model, the union of which constitutes the theoretical basis whose viability will be assessed, is developed (*Conceptual Tools I & II*). These efforts are motivated out of the insight that models are not created in a vacuum, but rather out of one’s total understanding of how the world works. In the third, the model with its conceptual framework is tested as a “proof of concept” against three key challenges to any attempt to establish ethics as an internal feature of “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems or account of moral responsibility for such technical systems in question, namely: the autonomy problem, the opacity problem, and the enforceability problem (*Proof of Concept Testing*). It is hoped in so doing, that the “proof of concept” testing would establish that the theoretical basis in question would adequately address the research questions germane to this project and simultaneously be a way through which and a basis whereby key moral values can be implemented at all three fundamental phases of the technology lifecycle: design, development, and deployment (i.e., utilization in society) for the relevant technical systems. Some of the benefits of the proposed research are as follows: (1) provision of an explicit characterization of an ethically prospective

approach to ethics of artificial intelligence, instead of an ethically retrospective “troubleshooting-ad-hoc” approach as well as a way to optimize such a prospective approach (2) provision of a concrete way to optimize machine ethics and related endeavors (e.g., value-based engineering and ethically aligned design, etc.) (3) localization or narrowing of moral responsibility assessment to a clearly defined set of stakeholders, thereby providing an answer to the intuitive interrogative which began the mainstay inquiry of this project, namely: ‘When behavior of an “autonomous” artificial intelligence system(s) leads to harm or death of someone, who is responsible?’, all of which, or so it is hoped, can strengthen policy recommendations regarding use of such technical systems in various social roles.

With this introduction in mind, the discussion turns forthwith to the construction, explanation, and justification of the practice-oriented conceptual framework employed in this investigation.

1.0 Conceptual Tools I

1.1 Social Imaginaries, Ethical Module, and Metaphors (S.E.M.): An Introduction

As conveyed in the previous section, the current discussion lies at the intersection of the domains of inquiry of models, ethics, and artificial intelligence systems. Moreover, this bears repeating: the aim herein is twofold. In the first, it is to establish ethics as an internal feature of “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems in such a way so as to show that they are performing some type of ethical analysis in virtue of an internal set of instructions and

architecture as well as by means of ethical design norms in addition to whatever engineering design norm requirements that need to be satisfied. Moreover, as a means of executing the first part of the twofold aim of this project, the author investigates whether there can be an account (i.e., a model) able to explain and justify the embedding of ethics as an internal feature, in the relevant sense, of an “autonomous” artificial intelligence system. Yet, as was discussed in the previous chapter, ethics is the “science of morality”; and as such, it’s a domain of inquiry whose members are moral concepts, sentiments, behaviors, and the like.²⁸ In light of this and so as to effect greater specificity, the author investigates whether a premiere moral concept such as moral responsibility can apply to such technical systems in such a way that they can be held morally responsible for their behavior and to provide the principled reasons in virtue of a positive or negative answer in this regard. Again, should it turn out that such a premiere moral concept cannot be correctly predicated of them, then it is hoped that the work done would at least demonstrate how a moral framework can be embedded, again in the relevant sense articulated above, into “autonomous” artificial intelligence system. In the second, the author attempts to develop a theoretical foundation that can be used as a basis for policy recommendations concerning regulation of technological development at all three crucial phases of the technology lifecycle – design, development²⁹, and deployment (i.e., utilization in society) – of the relevant technical systems (at the very least) along more ethically prospective workstreams.³⁰ It is hoped by the author that the model presented would accomplish both subsidiary goals of the aforementioned twofold aim, thereby, as the English language idiom goes: “killing two birds

²⁸ For more on this, please see the previous chapter.

²⁹ The author acknowledges the use of ‘development’ equivocally, pointing out that it is used in two senses here: (1) as a general reference to technological development regardless of this or that particular phase (2) as a specific phase of technological development wherein ideas are taken from an initial design phase and grown into full-fledged engineering technical artifacts.

³⁰ Due to the connection between ethics and both governance and legal spheres, respectively, it is hoped that whatever benefits engendered to policy recommendations towards a more ethically prospective workstream, *et cetera*, would carry over to those latter two spheres, *mutatis mutandis*.

with one stone”. Integral to the work needing-to-be-done so as to accomplish this aim is construction of the relevant model. Yet this work will not be solely pursued for reasons that, or so it is hoped, will become clear forthwith.

All technological and scientific understanding and practice are historically embedded³¹, something which can also be said of both philosophical and theological understanding and practice. As such, the former pair would co-occur with the prevailing theological and philosophical wisdom of the day whilst being enveloped by and wedded to or rather imbued with the existing worldview(s) of the particular time period. Though, some might say that any observed connections between technological or scientific understanding, methods, and overall knowledge-base, on the one hand, and theological and philosophical wisdom of a given historical period, on the other hand, are cosmetic instead of thematic or structural. In reply, it would be sensible to note that despite the discipline-relevant pressures to specialize, as the progression of Western history can attest to, there are deep thematic and structural connections between, for example, the medieval philosophical and theological debates concerning the relationship between universals and particulars, on the one hand; and on the other hand, the relationship between unobservables and observables in debates concerning realism in the history of physics.³² For the discipline of physics is, for a given time period, rife with a collection of interlocking

³¹ This applies, *mutatis mutandis*, to pre-scientific and pre-technological practice and understanding. It is easier to understand what is referred to by the term ‘pre-scientific’. One can cite ostensible examples thereof, the likes of things as alchemy (e.g., coming out of Alexandria Egypt between the 1st and the 3rd century of the common era) which is viewed as an expression of proto-chemistry (LaPort 2015; Rasmussen 2015). Moreover, one can view these things as pre-scientific in that they are before the formation of the scientific method. The situation becomes more difficult when attempting to make sense of the term ‘pre-technological’. Would the term apply to the primitive distillation equipment invented in the 3rd century by Zosimos of Panopolis (Linden 2014)? Would flint used among primitive hunter-gatherers so as to start a fire also count as an example of pre-technology? What of the stick that a chimpanzee uses to gather ants so as to eat them? Is there something like a technological method such that everything before its formation is pre-technological? Perhaps, there is no dividing line to which one can refer and claim that everything before this line is pre-technology, whereas everything after it is technology; but rather, only ostensible examples of each class.

³² Please see D.M. Armstrong’s volumes, namely: *Nominalism and Realism: Universals and Scientific Realism. Vol. I.* and *Universals and Scientific Realism: A Theory of Universals. Vol. II.* Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, November 28, 1980.

technological practices that form the concrete practical substructure, whereas the dominant scientific lore (e.g., scientific method, principles of scientific epistemology, etc.), models, and theories form the theoretical superstructure.³³ Moreover, both superstructure and substructure are, as noted above, enveloped by and imbued with a worldview.³⁴ The content of this worldview, however, is mediated by the prevailing theological and philosophical wisdom, at least in part; one might even go so far as to say, “in large part”.³⁵ This observation suggests several inquiries, pursuit of any of which would take this discussion too far afield. Nonetheless, this observation is also in line with an additional intuitive observation that *we generate our models of explanation drawing from resources that are framed (and thereby partially informed) by our total understanding of the world*; and as such, an explanation of this or that phenomena or event in the world is a product of our “fundamental framing”.

But what is a “fundamental framing”? In order to understand what this is, a diagnostic approach may prove useful. This is so because in understanding when “frames” break down or prove to be problematic in some way or other, one can in an effort to restore or revise them garner greater understanding as to their nature. Accordingly, the nature of a “framing problem” is best illustrated through a thought experiment. Imagine a group of carpenters showing up to a

³³ The author is grateful for this distinction borrowed from the work of Edward Conze, namely: *Buddhist Thought in India*, 17–30. London: George Allen & Unwin Ltd, 1962.

³⁴ It might be tempting to use the word ‘circumscribed’ instead of ‘enveloped’, as in “circumscribed by and imbued with a worldview”, but the connotation of this phrase would be potentially misleading. For ‘circumscribed’ has the connotation of being limited to, yet the substructure is what can bridge incommensurable superstructures relegated to this or that worldview. Hence, they would not be limited in the relevant sense. Wherefore, use of the word ‘enveloped’ strikes the needful fine balance here in that it both acknowledges influence of this or that worldview and even scientific paradigm on a substructure and that a substructure may, nevertheless, supersede it.

³⁵ Some examples are noteworthy. The medieval theologically relevant philosophical debates concerning realism informs how we, today, adjudicate the relationship between that which is concrete and that which is abstract (Armstrong 1980; Falguera et al. 2022). This can be seen in the modern metaphysical debates concerning concrete and abstract “objects” as well as debates within scientific realism concerning the nature of theoretical entities and observed phenomena (Falguera et al. 2022; Lyons and Vickers 2021). But it does not end there; the realism-relevant issues also come to the fore in debates concerning metaphysics of persons (e.g., the soul-body causal pairing problem) and concerning divine causation (e.g., the God-World causal pairing problem) (Kim 2001, 2005; Bailey et al. 2011).

construction job with all the tools believed to be relevant, necessary, and sufficient to complete the job. However, the job needing-to-be-done is a plumbing job and the tools brought are either irrelevant or unnecessary or insufficient to complete the job. Thus, a “framing problem”, in the relevant sense, occurs when: (1) there is belief in, at the very least, the relevance and, at the very most, necessity and sufficiency of certain tools to address the philosophical issue(s) in question (2) these tools are in fact either not relevant or not necessary or not sufficient to address the philosophical issue(s) in question. Thus, at the heart of a “framing problem” is a misunderstanding of the nature of the problem in need of solving.

Wherefore, one may characterize, if not define, a “fundamental framing” as a basic understanding of X, for any X, such that intelligibility of/for X draws on elements or structures of fundamental categories (e.g., ontological, epistemological, logical, axiological, etc.) forming a picture (often holistic in nature) of what something is or what needs to be done (or what one needs to do). Moreover, some of these elements or structures of fundamental categories might for instance be: (1) *ontological* – the relationship between humanity and nature: that humans are distinct and are in some sense in an antagonistic relationship with nature; the relationship between the class of *abstracta* and causation: abstract objects have no causal powers (2) *epistemological* – conditions for reliable knowledge and choice of methods regarding securing it: clear and distinct idea correspondence or fittingness (even if only asymptotically), in the former, and scientific method as opposed to tarot readings or channeling in the latter (3) *logical* – consistent vs. paraconsistent logic³⁶: assumptions as to which is adequate or sufficiently powerful to make sense of everyday experience as well as science and technological progress (4) *axiological* – understanding of the role values play based on distinctions, like for example,

³⁶ In this regard, please see: Priest, Graham, Koji Tanaka, and Zach Weber. 2022. "Paraconsistent Logic", *The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy* (Spring Edition), Edward N. Zalta (ed.), URL = <<https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/spr2022/entries/logic-paraconsistent/>>.

between persons and objects or between sentient and insentient. Furthermore, the sense in which the term ‘fundamental framing’ is intended is akin, *mutatis mutandis*, to the sense in which Ludwig Wittgenstein meant by, “*Ein Bild hielt uns gefangen.*”³⁷

The above considerations, thus, highlight the need for not only a model, but a way to frame this model properly, or at least to be transparent as to which “fundamental framing” is employed for a given model. As such, the work to be done in this section is development, explanation, and justification of a practice-oriented conceptual framework. Admittedly, certain aspects of a “fundamental framing” are not easily accessible, despite their ongoing influence in the workflow of making sense of things. These aspects may show themselves as tacit assumptions, certain preconceptual coping skills, and the like. Nevertheless, the framework is a way to access as much of this “fundamental framing” as possible in a way that is amenable to analysis and value-based engineering practice.

In line with the foregoing, the remainder of this chapter will introduce the relevant practice-oriented conceptual framework, *S.E.M.*, the acronym being apropos for what the framework consists of, namely: (1) a social imaginary (2) an ethical module (3) a conception on metaphor relevant for this overall discussion. The discussion of this chapter will be followed by some considerations on models from a metaperspective that are germane to the overall discussion and the subsequent work on models. Each of these will be discussed in turn followed by a summary discussion fleshing out more of the conceptual connection between the specific practice-oriented conceptual framework, *S.E.M.*, and the model to be constructed (M.) in the following chapter.

³⁷ Please see Ludwig Wittgenstein’s. 1953. *Philosophical Investigations*, 48 paragraph 115, trans. G.E.M. Anscombe .1997. Oxford: Blackwell.

1.2 Social Imaginaries

A social imaginary is a general understanding of how the world works, which includes but is not limited to, one's social reality. With respect to the latter, namely: one's social reality, this includes how one conceives of social practices and institutions, the fundamental principles upon which society is based, and what collection of norms it consists of whose fulfillment drives it (Taylor 2004, 6–8; 23–30). Moreover, it consists of multifarious features in dynamic relationships interwoven like threads forming a tapestry of immersion: one is no mere spectator to one's social imaginary, rather one is an actor living one's social imaginary. Nonetheless, these features, though interwoven, can be classified under, at least, five aspects.³⁸ These five aspects are: (1) hermeneutics (2) moral order (3) practices (4) background know-how (5) social constructs.

In the first, namely: hermeneutics, we have the general way one conceives and frames – keeping in mind that by “frames”, the author means something akin to, *mutatis mutandis*, the sense meant by Ludwig Wittgenstein, namely: “*Ein Bild hielt uns gefangen*” (Wittgenstein 1953, paragraph 48) – one's social environment yielding a general understanding of one's social reality.³⁹ This includes one's place in it, one's relationship to others, what historically embedded

³⁸ In contrasting the concept of “interwoven” with the concept of “classified”, I am alluding to David Hume's distinction between separable and distinguishable, though without whole-hog adoption of his principle of inseparability. See David Hume's 1739, *A Treatise of Human Nature (Oxford Philosophical Texts)*, Norton, D.F. and Norton, M.J. (eds.), 153, 160–161. The way this applies to social imaginaries is as follows. The differing features that make up a social imaginary are likely not separable from the whole a social imaginary constitutes, at least not without violence done to the social imaginary itself yet these features are distinguishable, much like the two halves of a differently shaded circle that has been bisected, say horizontally, into two semicircular regions of equal proportion. The two regions would be distinguishable, though not separable from the circle. Their separability being quite impossible. For were it possible, the circle must need remain in existence. Yet, with the creation of two semicircles, the persistence conditions of the circle are violated: it ceases to exist.

³⁹ See also Hubert Dreyfus's and Charles Taylor's 2015 book entitled *Retrieving Realism*, 1–26. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press, Charles Taylor's 2004, *Modern Social Imaginaries*, 3–12. Durham, NC: Duke University Press and Cornelius Castoriadis' 1987, *The Imaginary Institution of Society*. Cambridge, MA: MIT Press.

conditions one takes for granted, what one perceives as to what society is unfolding into or what one understands the overall goal (or goals) of society to be.

In the second, namely: moral order, we have, borrowing from Charles Taylor, the “modern moral order” also known as “MMO” (Taylor 2007, 294). We start with his conception, because this tracks well the moral order, in the relevant sense, which is operative in the 21st century: the “new vision of moral order”(Taylor 2007, 159). Charles Taylor’s account of moral order, at its core, is an idealization regarding human personhood formulated in terms of rights, autonomy, and mutual service (Taylor 2007, 170).⁴⁰

As such, the scope of the modern moral order (MMO) includes an evaluative framework, prescriptions, and an ontology wherein the interplay of rights with their concomitant obligations elucidate the contours of this evaluative framework, the status of such rights being unassailable, comprehensive, and in some way pertaining to the very nature of the right-bearer (Taylor 2007, 11–12). Some examples of the sorts of relevant 21st-century rights are a right to a life with human dignity, right to freedom, and right to conditions promoting human well-being or flourishing. Additionally, in history, “these rights, and the seriousness with which their role in the modern life of the West⁴¹ are conceived, find their collective wellspring in the political philosophies of both John Locke and Grotius” (Butler 2015, 11–12).⁴² As history can attest, “the full-fledged version of these rights that exists today in the West have gone through a series of redactions and expansions since the time of both Grotius and Locke” (Ibid).⁴³

⁴⁰ In this subsection, I am borrowing from a previously unpublished paper I wrote concerning Charles Taylor’s social ontology: much of my take on Charles Taylor’s modern moral order (MMO) comes from this unpublished work, “On the Viability of Charles Taylor’s Social Ontology as a Model for Interreligious Dialogue.” Leuven: *Katholieke Universitaet Leuven*, 2015 [unpublished].

⁴¹ By reference to these values in the West, this is not meant to be contrastive to, say: the East. No such position regarding the universality or particular nature of such values in terms of East and West.

⁴² See also Charles Taylor’s 1989, *Sources of the Self: The Making of the Modern Identity*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press, 11, 12.

⁴³ See also Charles Taylor’s 2004, *Modern Social Imaginaries*. Durham, NC: Duke University Press, 3 – 12.

The rights alluded to above, which elucidate the contours of the aforementioned evaluative framework, also provide epistemic access to the dimensions of mutual service and metaphysics of persons that jointly constitute the MMO (Ibid. 2015). As was previously stated, the conception of rights of the MMO is such that it has a concomitant conception of obligations (Ibid). The nature, however, of the relationship between rights and obligations, even as conceived of within the parameters of the MMO, is by no means obvious and uncontroversial. Be that all as it may, a protracted discussion concerning the nature of the relationship between rights and obligations falls outside the purview of the current discussion. But this need poses no significant problem here, for we needn't take a stand on the exact nature of the relationship in question in order to have a basic, useful understanding of this relationship applicable to the current discussion. Accordingly, within the MMO, at least for Taylor's conception of it being used herein, "along with a right on the part of an individual to, say, life, [such an individual has] certain obligations of mutual service" (Ibid. 2015). In fact, the obligation towards mutual service draws on J.S. Mill's harm principle for some of its content (Taylor 2007, 79–92).⁴⁴ In respect to this, one such obligation, which would be concomitant with the right to life, would be not to inflict harm on another person through either action or inaction. Moreover, this obligation accomplishes, at the very least, two tasks: (1) promoting and ensuring conditions conducive to human flourishing (2) providing a basis for the development of ways and means of active "participation on the part of right-bearers in protecting their rights" (Butler 2015).⁴⁵ The aggregate effect therefrom creates a regulated public life where constitutive of that life are explicit laws and policies as well as implicit practices and lived-understandings of mutual

⁴⁴ See also John Stuart Mill's, *On Liberty* (Oxford, England: Oxford University, 1859, I 12; III 1; IV 3, 10, 12; V 5 [referred to by chapter and paragraph]). For an expanded discussion of Mill's harm principle, see also, David Brink's 2022, "Mill's Moral and Political Philosophy", *The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy* (Spring Edition), Edward N. Zalta (ed.), forthcoming URL = <<https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/spr2022/entries/mill-moral-political/>>.

⁴⁵ See also Charles Taylor's 1989, *Sources of the Self: The Making of the Modern Identity*, Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press, 11.

benevolence geared towards promoting and preserving the right to life for (ideally) all participating members, the right to life being taken even as part and parcel of an ethical minimum standard of human living conditions accepted internationally and conducive towards individuals availing themselves of this right as a basic assumption of human living (Kirchschlaeger 2021, 146–190, 333–355).

The rights in question, being considered natural, inalienable, and universal, precipitated and made intelligible a reconsideration of the place of the individual in Western society (Taylor 1989, 11–13). This reconsideration held that the individual is autonomous yet under law (Taylor 1989, 11–12):

Whilst the autonomous character of the individual constituted a dislodgement of the individual person from a larger and all encompassing cosmic order, the natural rights possessed by the individual placed her, nevertheless, in some such ordering.⁴⁶ Admittedly, this new ordering was not that of the grand cosmic orderings evidenced among pre-modern societies.⁴⁷ This ordering, nonetheless, commanded respect and allegiance. Moreover, in contrast to the pre-modern conceptions, this new vision of moral order: (1) set the seat of ordering internal to the individual, instead of “out there” in the cosmos (2) cashed itself out in terms of human life and welfare promoting moral values.⁴⁸

The contrast to the ordering being “out there” does not mean that the order was somehow conceived as being only internal to autonomous individuals, although this definitely

⁴⁶ See also Charles Taylor’s 2007, *A Secular Age*, Cambridge, MA: the Belknap Press of Harvard University Press, 2007, 146–158.

⁴⁷ See also Charles Taylor’s 2004, *Modern Social Imaginaries*, Durham, NC: Duke University Press, 8 – 12.

⁴⁸ See also Charles Taylor’s 2007, *A Secular Age*, Cambridge, MA: the Belknap Press of Harvard University Press, 2007, 270–295 as well as his *Sources of the Self: The Making of the Modern Identity* (Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press, 1989), 11–14.

became part of some depictions of the new moral order.⁴⁹ Yet, the crux of the change of the locus of ordering was that it is now immanent to human life and human affairs, vis-à-vis something which is part of some grand design separate from human affairs to which the latter must in some way be conformed (Butler 2015, 12–13).

The upshot here being: that within the MMO, the conception of the metaphysics of persons concomitant with its conception of rights (and corresponding obligations) is such that human persons are now conceived as “buffered disciplined selves” (Taylor 2007, 171), namely: autonomous individuals who possesses rights (and corresponding obligations) who are independent of any sort of onto-teleo-axiological ordering of cosmic proportions.⁵⁰ Additionally, this new ordering would be that imposed upon each individual by the community of individuals *qua* participation in the life of the community of individuals of that ilk, namely: autonomous.⁵¹ Much more will be said about such individuals in two upcoming sections within this chapter (*Conceptual Tools I: 1.5.2* and *Conceptual Tools I: 1.5.3*).

Naturally, the MMO informs the aspect of hermeneutics as seen by its conception of rights and human personhood. This shows the axiological nature of how we understand our social reality and the world which encompasses it and with which it is interwoven. So, too, with our practices: the evaluative framework of the aspect of moral order, especially in its conception

⁴⁹ For a salient example of this, see Ralph Waldo Emerson’s 1908 essay entitled, *Self-Reliance*. East Aurora, New York: The Roycrofters.

⁵⁰ I wax a bit poetic by using the phrase “ordering of cosmic proportions”; nonetheless, the meaning is clear. This new metaphysics envisions human persons as not part of some *scala naturae* (Brake 2009), but rather as a bilateral taxonomy of causally related things, a plane of being or *planities naturae* whose members are, at least presumably, not onto-teleo-axiologically circumscribed and bound to some final aim, but rather related by causal interactions and principles governing these interactions, possessed of a design yet with no designer.

⁵¹ The phrase “the community of individuals” is meant to be a definite description, namely: something of the form: $\exists x \exists y (Ix \ \& \ Cy \ \& \ \forall z (Cz \rightarrow z=y) \ \& \ Nxy)$; where: ‘I’: “x is an individual” ‘C’: “y is a community”, and ‘N’ “x is in y.”; and as such, applies *mutatis mutandis* to any community of humans, of course *ceteris paribus*, as conceived by Chales Taylor’s “modern moral order” or “MMO” presented in his 2007, *A Secular Age* Cambridge, MA: the Belknap Press of Harvard University Press, 159.

of human personhood as well as the aspect of hermeneutics in its broad-sweeping scope, inclusive of one's social reality and surrounding world integral to it, in turn shape our conception of practices.

By the third, namely: practices, we have linguistic communication and enforceability of responsibility. Let's start with enforceability.⁵² This core understanding of enforceability also has, broadly-speaking, three *termina* of preoccupation: (1) designation (2) encouraging compliance (3) punishing non-compliance. In the first, namely: designation, this concerns determining the focus of enforceability: the subject upon which enforcement actions are to apply, the degree to which they apply, and the scope of application. In the second, namely: encouraging compliance, the mainstay concern here is that of incentives to comply with whatever relevant standard and the like whose satisfaction is in question. In the third, namely: punishing non-compliance, the bulwark against invalidating the standard is requital for failing to satisfy the standard through infringement by means of action or inaction.

In essence, "enforceability" is the capacity to enforce compliance with the content of some assertion or injunction, which itself is constituted by preferences, norms, policies, rules, laws, and the like. But one can view all of these as expressions of a core understanding. It is the geometry of that core understanding that is of interest here, for it bespeaks of the role a social imaginary plays, telling us something about its nature as well as the dynamic relationship of its constitutive aspects by means of their interplay.

This core can be explicated and understood in terms of, broadly-speaking, two currents. The first being a presupposition concerning reality that goes beyond mere facticity. That human life, mankind and its place in the world, is not just about what events occur, but rather what

⁵² I shall have much more to say regarding "enforceability" in the chapter of this book in which I shall test the model under scrutiny in this book.

events *ought to occur*. There is not just the bare fact of human activity, but a concern for what human activity *should be*.⁵³ Along with this sense for what ought to occur and what human activity should be is an aesthetic sense manifested in a lived-experience of harmony (“things making sense”) and disharmony. This lived-experience of harmony/disharmony, naturally, informs the second current.

This current in terms of which the core understanding of the notion of enforceability can also be explicated and understood is that of restoration. When the axiological order is disturbed, there is strong motivation to attempt to restore this order. These attempts have differing orientations providing glimpses into what is perceived as necessary and expeditious for the restoration of this value-laden order. One such orientation is that of retribution and atonement. That is, the restoration of order requires requital according to merit and demerit. This may even go so far as positing that rewards and punishments be distributed in the form of some future state either later in life or in an afterlife. The concomitant notion would be atonement. The two notions working in tandem would result in, for example, punishment for failing to do what one should be doing or for creating circumstances that ought not occur along with injunctions for making amends (e.g., in the case of reckless driving of a motor vehicle leading to the death of a pedestrian). The other orientation is that of rehabilitation and healing. This orientation frames restoration, not in terms of punishments, rewards, and making amends. But rather, it frames restoration as healing and a return to a state of health, both of the individual wrong-doer and the community of which wrong-doer is a part. Thereby, the one failing to do what one should be doing or who has brought about circumstances that ought not occur must be healed and brought

⁵³ One can see this echoed in the words of Søren Kierkegaard, “What I really need is to get clear about what I must do, not what I must know, except insofar as knowledge must precede every act.” (*Kierkegaard's Journals and Notebooks, Volume 11, Part 1: Loose Papers, 1830-1843*, ed. Niels Jørgen Cappelørn, et.al, New Jersey: Princeton University Press, Journal entry, August 1, 1835).

back in “good standing” (however this is conceived) for the sake of the individual and the health of the “body politic.”⁵⁴

What is common to both currents, demonstrating what is germane to enforceability itself, is value. An axiological understanding of human life is paramount. Value lies at the root of human existence, rather than being an outgrowth or by product of a largely animalistic existence. Much more could be said of this, but for now I finish with observing that this axiological orientation connects with the MMO in the latter’s rights-oriented conception of human personhood. Similarly, the axiological orientation connects with hermeneutics in its very outlook: shaping humanity’s self-understanding and grasp of its place in the world.⁵⁵

With the fourth, namely: background understandings and skills, we have the sort of phenomena that are non-representational. As such, they are not mental states possessed of intentionality, but rather aid in the formation and functioning of intentional states. For example, one may see an apple, desire it, and form the intention to eat it. All of these are intentional states in the relevant sense in that they are mental states with a directedness about them, they are about or represent “things, properties, or state of affairs” outside themselves (Jacob 2019). To get a better understanding of these, it is helpful to look at the work of John R. Searle.

The *Background* is a body of non-intentional mental capacities; and as such, not part of the collection of, as Searle puts it, the “Network” of intentional states (Searle 1983, 141–142). Moreover, these capacities, being logically prior, are required for the operation of the “Network”.⁵⁶ In fact, the *Background* serves as the pre-condition for intentional states or

⁵⁴ See Rollo-Koster, Joëlle. "body politic". *Encyclopedia Britannica*, 2 Oct. 2017, <https://www.britannica.com/topic/body-politic>. Accessed 1 February 2022.

⁵⁵ The latter, of course, is a by-product of the former, namely: humanity’s self-understanding yields its understanding of a world, even that there is one separate from itself, and humanity’s place in it.

⁵⁶ They may, in fact, be ontologically prior, although Searle, at least in the book entitled *Intentionality* (Searle 1987, 141–159), does not take up this position. The *Background’s* logical priority is granted insofar as certain intentional states or collection of intentional states operate in a way such that these non-intentional mental capacities would have to be in place for the intentional states to even get off the ground.

collections thereof within the “Network” (Searle 1983, 143–144), and it consists of both general non-representational “knowings-how” and “knowings-that” (Searle 1983, 144, 150–153).⁵⁷ For example, one may have the intention to walk through a door in order to leave a room, but the formation and operative role this intention plays in producing behavior is only made possible by a collection of non-intentional background understandings and skills. For one to behave in a way that demonstrates a certain sort of embodied lived-experience one would have to have an understanding that objects like doors are solid objects, one cannot simply pass through them, this being “knowings-that”. One would also need the “knowings-how” so as to cross the threshold of the door knowing that this action is how to leave, as opposed to simply waiting at the threshold for something to happen. One would also need to have, in case the door is closed, the “knowings-how” to open the door. All of this would need to be prior, at least logically and operatively, so as to serve as the condition or backdrop out of which the intention to leave the room by means of going through the door emerges into the foreground as an explicit intentional act. Hence, the impetus even to call this type of “knowing” and skill possession a “background”: it is the “background” out of which intentional action or mental states possessed of intentionality emerge into the “foreground”.

All of this becomes relevant when attempting to understand a social imaginary. For background understandings and skills have different operative spheres. Searle calls them the “deep background” and the “local background” (Searl 1983, 144). The idea is straightforward enough. The “deep background” includes rudimentary physics, like: understanding that objects are solid, basic understanding of fluids, basic understanding of gravity (water pours down not up), grasping, pulling, pushing on things, dragging and rolling, forward movement, backwards

⁵⁷ I intend scare quotes by use of “knowings-how” and “knowings-that”, as Searle himself does not use these terms, but rather related terms, namely: “know-how” and “know-that”. Nevertheless, I cite his work in this connection due the fundamental ideas underlying either pair of terms.

movement, jumping, walking, and the like (Searle 1983, 142, 150–153). Whereas the “local background” is more shaped by one’s cultural and societal milieu. This includes what to do at a cocktail party, how loud or quiet to speak, and what to do with certain technical artifacts. For the 21st century social imaginary includes a technosocial imaginary, or at the least has something to say about technology such that a modern human wouldn’t think a smartphone to be a type of funny-looking brick, whereas someone from the 15th century Europe might very well do so; and a modern human would not think a smartphone ran on steam power, whereas someone from the 18th century might. Moreover, no modern human in a developed society would think a fully charged smartphone operated by magic unless in being hyperbolic, whereas someone from the 12th century likely would. These contrasts are illuminating, because they show that, despite cultural differences, there is indeed a 21st century social imaginary co-mediated by certain technologies that social imaginaries of the past were not (Verbeek 2011). And part of what makes this possible is the digital-technology-co-mediated collection of (local) background understandings and skills. Its “co-mediation” (Verbeek 2011) is due to humanity’s value-laden self-understanding and understanding of the world at large, in progressive steps, sometimes in starts and fits, which gave rise to technological predecessors to such technology, and as humanity changed, so too the technology, and so forth. This mutual shaping and forging of humanity and its technology quite naturally shaped and was shaped by our hermeneutics, our MMO, our practices – no more the “demon haunted world” (Sagan 1997), no more the enchanted devices (Taylor 2007), but rather a natural order amenable to rational inquiry, understood, controlled and mastered for humanity’s welfare by our tools of ever greater technical sophistication and power.

In the fifth, namely: social constructs, a simple example can illustrate these. Take a large shared office of an institute. It is tempting to say that the office is in a room in a building.

Although this is true, the office is not itself the same as the room, and the room is not the same as the spatial subregion of the building. The latter is a physical space within a physical space (e.g., the spatial region of the entire building) and thereby physical in nature. Yet, the office and room are not identical to these physical spaces. There are other types of objects, social constructs, that are coincident with the physical space.⁵⁸ The office and the room are social constructs. Even the institute, of which the office is a part, is a social construct. The existence of all of which hang on collective intentionality. A community brings them into existence by means of regarding them a certain way, by imagining them to be (Castoriadis 1987). This may even involve declaratives whereby we bring something into being by speech act (Austin 1962; Searle 1970), which of course is only possible within a matrix of collective intentionality (Searle 1995).

This aspect of a social imaginary is illustrative of the immersive world-making dynamic power of a social imaginary. For we create social constructs out of the dynamic interplay between our hermeneutics, our MMO, our practices, our background understandings and skills, and out of our power of collective intentionality through language and symbols. Ultimately, these 5 aspects are in dynamic interplay constituting and forming into the dynamic, robust and pervading nature of a social imaginary. The ubiquity of a social imaginary is something that will play a pivotal role in the current discussion. As to how this contributes to the current inquiry into whether there can be a viable model, on the basis of which ethics can be established as an internal feature of “autonomous artificial intelligence, systems is something that will be, or so the author hopes, ever clearer through the course of this discussion. In fact, we now turn to a fundamental feature of a social imaginary, namely: value.

⁵⁸ On this point concerning coinciding entities, see David Wiggins’s 2002, *Sameness and Substances Renewed* Cambridge, England: Cambridge University Press.

1.3 Value, Axiology, and the Needful Tool, Rightly Understood

Value pervades a social imaginary; if a social imaginary is a tapestry, value would be the color and design which pervades it: both being constituted by the unique contribution of the individual threads which make up the tapestry as well as the whole thereby constituted. The value that pervades a social imaginary is multifarious. Its varieties include aesthetics (e.g., ‘What is beauty?’), moral (e.g., ‘What is the right thing to do?’), attitudinal and sentimental (e.g., ‘For what should one be grateful?’, ‘What is loathsome?’, etc.), prudential (e.g., ‘What redounds to one’s benefit?’), and existential (e.g., ‘What is a life worth living?’).⁵⁹

Axiology is the study of the nature of value. Just what this means is a bit of a matter of debate. Some portion of received learned opinion holds that axiology is primarily concerned with classifying as to what is good and how such things are so (Schroeder 2021). This is a view of axiology that is associated with traditional concerns within this domain of inquiry, namely: what grounds the classification of an object of value as good: Is it a psychological state(s) or a feature(s) of the world? — the subjectivist and objectivist views, respectively —, regarding the grounding problem for value (Ibid; Smith and Thomas 2022). By contrast, ‘value theory’, at least in its broadest sense, has been used as a general way of referring to all branches of political and social philosophy, along with aesthetic and moral philosophy as well as, at times, philosophy of religion and feminist philosophy (Schroeder 2021). The common denominator that serves as a basis for the classification implied by the use of the term ‘value theory’ as a catch-all label, is an

⁵⁹ Naturally, there are items that are of a hybrid variety. For example, existential values that are prudential, namely: an examined life or life of philosophical reflection being both existential and prudential. For it provides, in ‘humanity’s search for meaning’ (Frankl 1947), a solution that simultaneously redounds to the human person’s benefit. Furthermore, it is tempting to think that existential and prudential values are selfsame. Yet, one can see how nihilism, being a position concerning existential value that itself is an existential-value position, would not be conducive to the well-being of human persons, precipitating depression, violence, and suicide among various and sundry other woes.

“evaluative aspect” (Ibid). Furthermore, the narrowest sense in which the term ‘value theory’ is used overlaps with axiology in that its focus is “normative ethical theory” (Schroeder 2021).

However, this way of viewing axiology, namely: (1) as a domain solely focused on classification concerning the good (2) as a domain solely focused on normative ethics, is not herein adopted. This is largely for reasons that are both methodological and pragmatic. The first reason is parsimony. One can simply analyze all the relevant phenomena whilst assuming a smaller set of categories or subcategories as well as a smaller set of semantic variations by simply fixing the meaning and application of “axiology” such that it encompasses “value theory” in both its broadest and narrowest senses, as well as being both about the business of classifying what and how things are good and investigating normative ethical theories. The second is robustness. Such a view of axiology makes it sufficiently powerful and dynamic to investigate multifarious forms of value and domains of inquiry with evaluative aspects. And the third and final methodological and pragmatic reason is that one gets a tighter-fitting typology; that is, such a view of axiology makes it uniform with the following other categories: epistemology, ontology, logic, and hermeneutics, which in turn boosts clarity and rigor of analysis and better secures explanatory adequacy in virtue of this greater taxonomic uniformity.

In contradistinction, herein, axiology will be used in the broadest sense possible with no diminishment to a fine-grained analysis of its objects. As such, this domain of inquiry is concerned with both theoretical and practical questions and investigations concerning value. This includes all the aforementioned varieties and as such is not limited to just moral value. That having been said, a preoccupation with moral value is a predominant part of the discourse concerning axiology, a domain of inquiry possessed of many subdomains, each of which has a central item of investigation; hence, there is a subdomain that inquires into aesthetics, a

subdomain that inquires into morality, a subdomain that inquires into existential concerns (e.g., the search for meaning), and so forth. Nonetheless, these subdomains share a common focus, which serves as the wellspring of rationality for their respective investigations as well as that which allows them to be classified under the same general category, providing yet again some of the methodological and pragmatic benefits referenced above. This common focus can be discerned by considering the very name of the category — and this provides an additional etymological rationale for the view of axiology herein adopted — the word ‘axiology’ being a compound of two Greek words, namely: *axios* and *logos*: *axios* meaning “worthy” and *logos* meaning “study of” or “science of”.⁶⁰ The concept of “worthy” or “worthiness” implies value. Naturally, then, this common focus, which is also of the nature of the objects of this category or class, is value.

The pervasiveness of value as well as its nature might motivate one to conclude that axiology or moral considerations are an outgrowth of a social imaginary. Though, as I hope will become clear in what follows, such views are problematic, and thereby are not herein endorsed. The problem with the first claim, namely: that axiology is an outgrowth of a social imaginary, is vagueness or a category error. For either such a description says something, but only inchoately or it missapplies the category of axiology at the level of the objects it ranges over, or viewing it as a set, the objects it contains, on the one hand; or it misunderstands that the "study of value", axiology, is not so much an outgrowth of a social imaginary, but really a response of critical self-understanding of those immersed in a social imaginary, on the other hand. Yet, for axiology to be an "outgrowth" in the relevant sense, it would have to flow naturally from a social imaginary, but this would be tantamount to saying being critically self-aware is an outgrowth of a

⁶⁰Britannica, T. Editors of Encyclopaedia. "axiology." *Encyclopedia Britannica*, June 10, 2015. <https://www.britannica.com/topic/axiology>.

social imaginary, which the author thinks has little justification in its favor. For a community can be fully immersed in a social imaginary and never become critically self-aware of it, *et cetera*. Furthermore, although the author grants that the better part of discussions concerning value are centered on moral considerations, the problem with the second claim, namely: that moral considerations are an outgrowth of a social imaginary, is that no *particular* moral consideration flows as an outgrowth of a social imaginary, since *several* are consistent with it. But in the subsequent section, the author is trying to develop a *particular* set of ethical tools or instruments for the ethical analysis that is germane to the central inquiry of this book. So, regarding moral considerations thusly is not conducive to developing such tools or instruments on pain of arbitrariness. Admittedly, a concern with value is, indeed, endemic to a social imaginary affecting all things within it; this includes, but is not limited to, technical artifacts (Kroes 2012). In fact, the value-ladenness of technology is, by now, well-known and accepted (Gonzalez 2013, 2015; How 2018).⁶¹

It is pivotal, then, to have a way of accessing the value features of technology. Accordingly, a set of tools or instruments are needed in order to accomplish this task. This tool set will, or so it is hoped, facilitate epistemic access to the value features of technical artifacts, aiding in analyzing them from an axiological perspective, in particular an ethical perspective. Such a set of tools or instruments would work along with full acknowledgement of the significance of a social imaginary for technology. The significance here being that we build our models, scientific or otherwise, out of our social imaginary. , the rationale behind this being intuitive: we build our models, scientific or otherwise, out of our total understanding of how the world works. This, of course, highlights that our total understanding of how the world works is

⁶¹ For a short discussion of approaches in this regard, see the 2008 article by Wendell Wallach and Colin Allen, “Machine Morality: Bottom-up and Top-down Approaches for Modeling Human Moral Faculties”, in *AI & Society* 22 (4): 565–582.

value-laden. Furthermore, the aforementioned tool set is meant to work in tandem with a social imaginary, functioning as an ethical analysis tool set module. This tool set module acknowledges and reflects that our total understanding of the world is value-laden as well as, as was already mentioned, is designed so as to facilitate greater access to (at least some of) these value features. The components of this ethical module are extrapolated both from the contours of our social imaginary and in a way fitting to the technical artifact in question and its application. Though, this should come as no surprise, as there are precedents for this. For certain safety-critical principles, norms, and standards are developed out of or on the basis of the resources afforded from one's social imaginary, the nature of the technical artifact, and its application. Consider, for example, the case of an automated chef. The relevant safety-critical principles, norms, and standards that regulate the design, development, and deployment of such a technical artifact are such that they reflect, for example, the harm principle aspect of the MMO (see above) of a social imaginary in, say, having design norms which prevent use of dish soap as frying oil.⁶², and with respect to the technical artifact's application, its technical development life-cycle also reflects (or at the very least is consistent with) the intent to have food prepared for public consumption. But what is this ethical analysis tool set module?

1.4 Ethical Analysis Tool Set Module: How not to Proceed

The ethical analysis tool set module (henceforth: ethical module) consists in the function of assessing the quality of the value-aspect of technology⁶³, whilst consisting of parameters

⁶² Something else that is clear is that principles, norms, and standards can be seen as extrapolations, at least indirectly, from one's social imaginary by means of being tailored to satisfy certain conditions. These conditions of satisfaction, too, would be extrapolations, but of a proximate nature, from one's social imaginary, whereas the principles, norms, and standards would be distal extrapolations from one's social imaginary.

⁶³ The very phrase, namely: "value-aspect of technology" is used synonymously with the phrase "evaluative aspect of technology", and the key point being that a "value-aspect" and evaluative-aspect" are different ways of

whose members are: (1) an ethical template (2) a metaphysics of human persons (3) a conception of responsibility (4) an ontology of technical artifacts, all these being considered to be individually necessary and jointly sufficient for the performance of the ethical module’s function. The author will take each in turn, but first a caveat needs to be discussed concerning how to regard this ethical module.

It is rather tempting, for sake of rigor of argumentation and clarity, to explicate the ethical module in question in an analytic manner, regarding it as an analytical tool; namely, something of the following form:

$$F^{\text{em}_X} = (M^n, Q^v)$$

Where ‘em’ stands for “ethical module”, thereby specifying the class to which the function belongs, and ‘F^{em}’ is the symbol of the relevant function that takes inputs, the type of which are attributes and characteristics of a technical artifact; and according to certain instructions, yields a pair of outputs whose first member is trivalent in nature, namely: (1) having a value of ‘1’, if the attribute inputted is evaluative (2) having a value of ‘0’, if the attribute inputted is not evaluative (3) having a value of ‘F^{em_x} ↓’⁶⁴, if undefined. This latter value for ‘Mⁿ’ is to signify that the answer to the inquiry for an evaluative aspect is avoided by means of not being relevant or

expressing the same idea. Nonetheless, ‘value-aspect’ suggests that there is some entity or thing being referenced (e.g., an aspect). Were such an entity to exist and be referred to by such a phrase, then how is a value-aspect explicated? Put differently: What would this aspect consist in? Would this be some kind of state, property, or the like; and if so, what are its persistence conditions, causal histories, and individuation conditions? Need a value-aspect be a specific and distinct property of something? Musings in this direction could lead to a discussion, hoary for some, profound and riveting for others, that would nonetheless take the overall conversation too far afield. Nonetheless, some working conception is needful, and will be provided through the unfolding of the discussion of this book.

⁶⁴ I have adopted this notation from Herbert B. Enderton’s 2011 book, *Computability: An Introduction to Recursion Theory*. 2011. Elseveier, 3–6.

unanswerable. Furthermore, the superscript of ‘n’ denotes that the values of ‘M’ are numerical or undefined. The second member of the pair, ‘Q^v’, denotes an evaluative-aspect of a certain type, where ‘Q’ denotes a result of a qualitative nature being of the axios-class (i.e., axiological or value class) and the superscript ‘v’ denoting what subdomain, namely: ethics, and its member of the axiological or value class.⁶⁵ But what are the instructions by which the function is governed?

The function’s internal instructions are the parameters of: (1) an ethical template (2) a metaphysics of human persons (3) a conception of responsibility and justice (4) an ontology of technical artifacts, all of which constitute conditions of satisfaction. When all conditions are satisfied, the function yields an output of (1, Q^v) meaning both “true” and the presence of some evaluative-aspect of a certain type.⁶⁶ Strictly speaking, the result of ‘Q^v’ could be the entire domain or class of axiology or any of its subdomains. For instance, the result could be “Aesthetic Principle: Organic Unity” or “Ethical Principle: Truthfulness”, etc. Moreover, as an example of the complete output of such a function, consider that with the aforementioned automated chef, the output assigned to that case by the function in question would be (1, “Ethical Principle: Do no harm.”). For the function would return the result of “true” for the presence of an evaluative-aspect and some linguistic formulation articulating the type of evaluative-aspect.⁶⁷

Admittedly, the evaluative aspect needn’t be in the form of an injunction, as there are alternative ways of expressing the relevant evaluative aspect, should there be one at all.

⁶⁵ Philosophico-linguistic issues notwithstanding, the author shall use ‘axios-class’ and ‘value class’ interchangeably.

⁶⁶ Strictly speaking, the result of ‘Q^v’ could be the entire domain or class of axiology or any of its subdomains. For instance, the result could be “Aesthetic Principle: Organic Unity” or “Ethical Principle: Truthfulness”, etc.

⁶⁷ Note that this linguistic expression, ‘Ethical Principle: Do no harm’, is a simplified version of the result, namely: $(1, EP \ni \square \forall x[Ax \rightarrow \sim Hx])$: where ‘1’ denotes the presence of an evaluative aspect, ‘ \square ’ denotes obligation (‘ \diamond ’ denoting permission), ‘Ax’ denotes “x is an action.” and ‘Hx’ denotes “x is a harm.”, and the remaining rudiments of the formula being standard usage from set theory and first-order predicate logic (see both: Halmos P.R. 2017. *Naive Set Theory*. Dover Publications; Reprint Edition, New York, and Bessie, J. and Glennan, S. 2000. *Elements of Deductive Inference*. Cengage Learning; 1. Edition, Boston, MA). The simplified version in the natural language of English being, for the sake of clarity, preferable *qua* its simplicity, not *qua* being in English. Should there be an equally simple way of expressing the same semantic content in another natural language, this would be perfectly acceptable.

There are at least three benefits of this analytical approach. The first is that it aids clarity and adds analytic rigor to axiological inquiries into technical artifacts. The second is that it establishes a computational relationship between attributes of a technical artifact and an assessment of its putative evaluative aspects, namely: for an attribute of a technical artifact X, there is some rule-governed relationship (e.g., in the form of a causal mechanism, correlation, predictable pattern propagation, etc.) connecting this attribute to some value assessment (Y, Z) and ultimately to some value Z (i.e., an evaluative aspect). The third benefit, and this is closely related to the second, is that this approach is programmable; that is, the computational relationship established by such an approach is amenable to being turned into a programmable algorithm. Moreover, all three of these benefits speak in favor of this approach's usefulness in the life-cycle of technology used in the public space. For it holds promise of being parsimonious, robust, and scalable. As such, it would play a pivotal role in value-based engineering⁶⁸ and in an ethics-by-design or ethically-aligned design⁶⁹ model of technological development; wherein among the design norms needing-to-be-satisfied, ethical norms factor centrally among them. These benefits notwithstanding, this approach has at least two significant problems.

The first is that the function lacks sufficient power to analyze the relevant domain. For it is not fine-grained enough to detect degrees of viability between values. The upshot here: individual moral values, clusters of moral values, *et cetera*, are not all equal. And although there may be no univocal account in favor of one moral value (i.e., one right answer to the inquiry as to which moral value is best), there are certainly better or worse arguments in favor of this or that

⁶⁸ Spiekermann, Sarah and Winkler, Till, Value-based Engineering for Ethics by Design (May 12, 2020). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3598911> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3598911>.

⁶⁹ The IEEE Global Initiative on Ethics of Autonomous and Intelligent Systems (2019) "Ethically Aligned Design: A Vision for Prioritizing Human Well-being with Autonomous and Intelligent Systems." *IEEE Advancing Technology for Humanity*, available online: https://standards.ieee.org/content/dam/ieee-standards/standards/web/documents/other/ead_v2.pdf (accessed 01.06.2022) as well as Wallach, Wendell, et al. 2008 "Machine Morality: Bottom-up and Top-down Approaches for Modeling Human Moral Faculties", in *AI & Society* Vol. 22, Issue 4, 565–582.

moral value as well as better or worse moral values. The function in question, however, only detects the presence or absence of an evaluative aspect; and granted, individual moral values, cluster of moral values, and the like, regardless of their viability with respect to one another, are all classified as evaluative aspects, and as such would be detected as “present”, when present (assuming there are no issues with the mechanics of the function), the gradation of viability between them, however, would not be detectable by the function in question. Looking askance, however, one could remark that the inability of the function to handle differences of degree, thus making it not fine-grained enough, is merely a result of it not being constructed to handle such inputs. Something that can be easily fixed by means of modifying the function.

Yet, suppose that the function were redesigned, as the objection suggests, such that it accepted the relevant inputs. It would, then, provide numerical assignments for M^n such that these numerical assignments must signify a real difference in quantity of an attribute. Hence, these assignments must signify a countable difference in the attribute in question ($A_n - A_{n-1}$). Thus, these assignments must signify a real difference on a clearly definable scale. Thus, the numerical assignments must be non-arbitrary. But one can, of course, assign numbers to anything. Nonetheless, for those number-assignments to be meaningful, these must signify a real difference. For example, the numerical assignments of the *Richter Magnitude Scale* or *Richter Scale* (for short) quantify the amount of seismic energy released by an earthquake, and the scale is logarithmic. Hence, the scale is countable. Moreover, a comparison between numerical assignments signifies a difference in magnitude – a real difference in the relevant sense – using a clearly defined scale. Thus, the numerical assignments are non-arbitrary. But what would be the corresponding difference in quality or viability of moral values? It can’t be magnitude, for this option is not available for the category of quality, by the very nature of that category. So, what

would the numerical assignments refer to exactly, and what non-arbitrary difference would a comparison of the assignments yield?

The author could go on, but he thinks the point is clear – and this brings us to the second significant problem with this approach – the upshot here being: the differences between moral values, and the like, *though discernable, are not quantifiable*. This follows as a corollary of a fundamental fact about the category of axiology, namely: the subdomain of axiology consisting of moral values *is fundamentally not quantifiable; that is, quantifiability is not an attribute of this subdomain*. Hence, the slogan “Ethics is not quantifiable” draws its meaning. Sure, we can assign numbers in this category, and we can even talk in terms of comparisons, even in terms of inequalities like utilitarians often do. But all this talk is a bit hand-wavy or at least suggestive of a discernible difference, which is fundamentally not quantifiable or if it is quantifiable, we would be using numbers in a very different way, and thereby the category of quantification in a very different way, if we intend our pronouncements to be more than just suggestive ways to refer to a discernible difference or non-metaphorical.⁷⁰

Despite the unworkability of explicating the ethical module formally as something formal (i.e., a hybrid mathematical function) that is simultaneously amenable to being expressed and operationalized computationally, being something that can be easily (or at all) convertible to an algorithm, the prospect of a non-formal solution, nonetheless, bodes well. This is because such a solution has three key virtues in its favor: (1) being better suited to handle unquantifiability (2) being better suited to handle “fuzzy factors” (3) being more dynamic.

These key virtues of a non-formal solution can be appreciated from the following considerations. The first virtue of a non-formal solution, namely: being better able to handle

⁷⁰ For an interesting discussion along these lines consider James H. Moor’s 1995 article entitled (“Is Ethics Computable?”), In *Metaphilosophy* vol. 26, No. ½, Wiley, Hoboken, NJ, 1–21).

unquantifiability, is such that a non-formal solution is better able to deal with a domain of inquiry possessing phenomena that are unquantifiable. This is simply because a non-formal solution needn't require quantification of any kind, so unquantifiability poses no special problem here. The second virtue, namely: being better able to handle “fuzzy” factors, means that a non-formal solution bodes better to account for features that are unique to ethics. Some of these features are being open-textured⁷¹, being vaguely bordered⁷², being holistic and multidimensional⁷³, and being tacit⁷⁴.⁷⁵ This results from the fact of a non-formal solution not needing to rely on the strictures of a system closed under some truth-preserving parameter nor possessed of the principle of decidability.

To see this, one must bear in mind that a formal solution would utilize some structure(s) of a formal system (e.g. formula or formulae); and by ‘formal system’, the author means a set of sentences “closed under provability”⁷⁶; that is, a set of sentences of some language that contains

⁷¹ In this connection, please see: (1) Joost Jacob Vecht .2020. Open texture clarified, *Inquiry*, DOI: 10.1080/0020174X.2020.1787222 (2) Waismann, Friedrich. 1945. “Verifiability.” *Proceedings of the Aristotelian Society, Supplementary Volumes* 19: 100–164.

⁷² Please see the following selections in this regard: (1) Gert, Bernard and Joshua Gert. 2020. "The Definition of Morality", esp: §1.0. *The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy* (Fall Edition), Edward N. Zalta (ed.), URL = <<https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/fall2020/entries/morality-definition/>> (2) Sorensen, Roy. 2022. "Vagueness", *The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy* (Summer Edition), Edward N. Zalta (ed.), URL = <<https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/sum2022/entries/vagueness/>> (3) Varzi, Achille. 2015. "Boundary", esp: §1.3. *The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy* (Winter Edition), Edward N. Zalta (ed.), URL = <<https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/win2015/entries/boundary/>>. (4) Rosanna Keefe & Peter Smith (eds.). 1996. *Vagueness: A Reader*. MIT Press.

⁷³ Accordingly, please see: Andrés Soria Ruiz & Federico L.G. Faroldi .2022. Moral adjectives, judge-dependency and holistic multidimensionality, *Inquiry*, 65:7, 887-916, DOI: 10.1080/0020174X.2020.1855241.

⁷⁴ In respect to this attribute, especially as it connects to the concept of “tacit knowledge”, please see Michael Polyani’s 1962 book entitled *Personal Knowledge: Towards a Post-Critical Philosophy*, London: Routledge & Kegan Paul Ltd.

⁷⁵ Moreover, this list is not intended to be exhaustive. There may be other peculiar features of ethics for which a non-formal solution would be better. The list, however, provides a means of explaining some of the peculiar features which speak in favor of a non-formal solution, and in turn, explicating the ethical module as something non-formal.

⁷⁶ The author is indebted to the work of Peter Vranas for his rather informative and insightful handouts (*Philosophy* 511: Symbol Logic, “Handouts” [Fall Semester, 2021], available online at: <https://vranas.website/teaching.htm> [accessed 13 June 2022]). Moreover, for an expanded discussion of this topic, please see the following works: (A) Boolos, George. 1995. *The Logic of Provability* Cambridge University Press. (B) Williamson, T. 1996. Logics of Provability [Review of *The Logic of Provability*, by G. Boolos]. *The Philosophical Quarterly* (1950-), 46 (182), 110–116. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2956313>. (C) Buehler, R.J. 2014. *The Logic of Provability: Notes by R.J. Buehler Based on the Logic of Provability by George Boolos*. UCB Mathematics University of California Press, available online at: <https://math.berkeley.edu/~buehler/The%20Logic%20of%20Provability.pdf> [accessed 24 June 2022]. (D)

every sentence of that language provable from that set. This means that if a set is closed under provability, then if there is a proof that a sentence follows from such a set, then the sentence is in the set in question. Within the context of mathematical logic, the term ‘formal system’ is synonymous with ‘theory’; and as such, a theory means “a set of sentences that contains all sentences of its language that are provable from it. Thus, the theorems of a theory are just the sentences in T , and $\vdash_T B$ and $B \in T$ are two ways of writing the same thing.” (Boolos, et al. 2007, 191). An example of this is in order:

All men are mortal.
 Socrates is a man.
 \therefore Socrates is mortal.

This example is instructive insofar as it demonstrates certain key features that result from the notion expressed in the locution “closed under provability.” Two things are noteworthy here. The first is that the example is that of a deductive argument, which is arguably the gold standard of the family of reliable arguments. The second is that for these types of arguments – and this speaks to the demonstrable features of the example – they instantiate necessary inferences. A necessary inference is such that: necessarily, if all the premises are true, then the conclusion is true.⁷⁷ Some relevant corollaries which follow from this are: (1) if all the premises are true, it is

Verbrugge, Rineke L.C. 2017. "Provability Logic", *The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy* (Fall Edition), Edward N. Zalta (ed.), URL = <<https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/fall2017/entries/logic-provability/>>.

⁷⁷ Often, this idea is expressed thusly: “if p is true, q must be true”. Yet, such a way of expression is ambiguous between the idea of the *necessity of the consequent* ($p \rightarrow \Box q$) and the *necessity of the consequence* ($\Box [p \rightarrow q]$). **But it is the latter idea which expresses the same idea of necessary inference and necessary logical consequence. To reiterate: formally, this idea is expressed in terms of sentential logic, namely: $\Box (p \rightarrow q)$.** There are, however, more fine-grained ways of expressing this notion, for example, in terms of first-order predicate modal logic, descriptor logic, etc. Nonetheless, as this is not a discussion in the finer points of metalogic or

impossible for the conclusion to be false (2) the truth of the premises guarantees the truth of the conclusion. Moreover, upon reflection one can clearly see that the conclusion says nothing over and above the premises. Relatedly, the content of the conclusion can be viewed as already implicit in the premises: the conclusion being an explicit expression of this content.

Another way to understand this point is in terms of “truth-functional mechanics” (if the author may use such a turn of phrase); that is to say: the conclusion is a tautological consequence of the premises. A tautology is a sentence that is true under every interpretation. In terms of sentential logic⁷⁸, one straightforward way to see this is to consider a simple truth-table for such a sentence:

Principle of Excluded Middle

A	$\neg A$	$A \vee \neg A$
T	F	T
T	F	T
F	T	T
F	T	T

Table 1.

different systems of logic, much time spent discussing finer-grained expressions of the concept in question would take the current discussion too far afield.

⁷⁸ For a clear, systematic, and insightful explanation of sentential logic, see Bessie, J. and Glennan, S. 2000. *Elements of Deductive Inference*. Cengage Learning; 1. Edition, Boston, MA).

As the name suggests, this is the truth table for the principle of excluded middle or the principle of bivalence, the latter being a principle of logic, sometimes regarded as a principle of thought itself⁷⁹, that holds that for every proposition either that proposition or its negation are true.⁸⁰ Moreover, the last column of the truth-table shows that this principle is true under all possible truth assignments of its sentence letters.⁸¹ And given that there are only two sentences required to explicate this principle, there are only four possible interpretations. Note, however, that they are all true. And were there more sentences with concomitant increase in possible interpretations, they all would be true due to the truth-functional nature of the tautology, of which the principle of excluded middle is an example. Furthermore, its tautological nature makes it necessarily true. Again much more can be said here, but the key point to draw from all of this is that the *logical consequence is necessary*. Furthermore, all of this is consistent with the above definition of a formal system or theory, and illustrative of the logical power of being “closed under provability”. The upshot from all of this being: we want our arguments to bring us from truth to truth, not truth to falsity⁸², and the notion of a necessary logical consequence is a surefire way to get this done.

⁷⁹ Please see, "Laws of thought". *Encyclopedia Britannica*. Retrieved 20 March 2021, available online at, <https://www.britannica.com/topic/laws-of-thought#ref180926>.

⁸⁰Please see Jairo Jose da Silva's. 2011. "On the Principle of Excluded Middle.", *Principia: An International Journal of Epistemology* 15 (2):333–347.

⁸¹ Before proceeding, some terminological clarification would be advantageous. The reader may have noticed a shift in terminology from ‘proposition’ to ‘sentence letters’, indicating a not-so-slight shift in reference, both terms being germane to sentential logic, along with a shift in noun phrases from ‘under every interpretation’ to ‘under all possible truth assignments’. In the first case, namely: a shift in terminology from ‘proposition’ to ‘sentence letters’, *et cetera*, there is a rather complicated story behind why such an equivocation of reference poses no problem here, but in order to avoid unnecessary confusion or an *excursus* into logic and metalogic, or even into the ontological status of propositions, the terms ‘sentence’, ‘proposition’, and ‘sentence letters’ are used interchangeably to refer to a sentence of some natural human language. In the second case, the noun phrase ‘under all possible truth assignments’ is used subsequently and interchangeably with ‘under every interpretation’ so as to add explanatory clarity, namely: that interpretation is meant in a rather restricted sense of truth-functional semantics in the service of explanatory adequacy regarding the matters of logic currently under discussion. This is right and proper to keep in mind simply for clarity’s sake and so as neither to conflate with nor minimize the relevance of a deeper exploration into such terms as ‘interpretation’ within the field of hermeneutics.

⁸² Herein, I do not wish to endorse colloquialisms regarding properties that arguments possess by playing fast-and-loose with my terminology. It is often said, speaking loosely, that an argument is true or false. Strictly speaking, however, truth and falsity are, within the context of logic, properties of propositions (or to simply: sentences). Whereas, soundness, validity, cogency, and the like, are, in most contexts, properties of arguments. This

In the aforementioned, two things are noteworthy. The first being that, within the context of mathematical logic – the context that is relevant here – a formal system is synonymous with a theory. This is important because it relates to the principle of decidability above mentioned. This principle, as it applies to a theory, is as follows:

A theory is decidable exactly if there is an effective procedure for determining, for every sentence, whether or not it is in the theory (Vranas 2007).

As such, being open-textured, an aforesaid feature of the domain of ethics, creates indeterminacy with respect to semantic content or extension of the relevant concepts which in turn runs counter to having an effective procedure for making the sort of determination the principle in question requires. This, in turn, would be a problem for a formal solution: a solution heavily reliant on a theory or formal way of explicating the ethical module under discussion. Of course, one could just have a formal solution, in the relevant sense, that is not decidable. This, however, would undermine one of the major benefits of a formal solution: analytical rigor of the sort that is axiomatizable, and thereby convertible into a computable algorithm (something highly relevant for the current topic). And even if one forgoes having a formal solution in the form of a computable algorithm, the feature of being open-textured would still mitigate the analytical rigor of the sort of formal solution in question.

The second noteworthy item is that the notion of “closed under provability” is a type of truth-preserving parameter used for deductive arguments. As such, this parameter ensures that

latter claim must also be understood properly. For there is a conception of validity for a sentence, namely: But even here it is semantically a slightly different notion related to its cousin-conception applied to arguments forms.

we have argument forms and therefrom arguments, which are instantiations of argument forms⁸³, that are rigorous and maximally reliable; and insofar as our patterns of inference-making conform to these argument forms, we also have rigorous and maximally reliable patterns of inference. This, however, comes at a cost due to the nature of tautological consequence, namely: deduction does not bring us to truly novel conclusions. However, deduction, as a class of reliable inference with its rigorous logical argument forms, is not the only class of reliable inference. There are also induction and abduction.

Bearing in mind that this is not meant to be a discussion about mathematical or philosophical logic, we shall start with abduction. In so doing, an extensive explanation and comparison of induction with abduction is not intended: just enough for the relevant comparison to deduction in the service of making the points necessary and expeditious to discuss the prospects of the formal way of explicating the ethical module under examination. Starting with abduction, then, this class of reliable inference is the most common of the aforementioned three classes, and in many ways the most intuitive. In fact, abductive inferences are the bread and butter of daily human reasoning. Some common sense examples can illustrate this.

Jim comes home from work to find that the window in the kitchen is open, although he does not remember opening it before work in the morning. Though, Jim aired out the kitchen yesterday evening after cooking some fish. After reflecting on the fact that he lives alone and that no one could have come into his apartment, with both the main door and the kitchen door locked, whilst he was away, Jim concludes that he must have forgotten to close the window from the previous evening. A second example is as follows: two friends, John and Carl live together. John has a car, Carl does not. One evening, they discuss the need to pick up a couch for the

⁸³ The author, again, am indebted to the work of Peter Vranas for his rather informative and insightful handouts (Philosophy 511: Symbol Logic, “Handouts” [Fall Semester, 2021], available online at: <https://vranas.website/teaching.htm> [accessed 13 June 2022]).

living room that is currently on sale, but make no definitive plans as to when or how they are going to pick up the new couch. The next morning, John awakes to find his car and car keys missing. (He does not benefit from the message that was sent to his phone, due to his phone's battery being dead. John surmises, correctly, that Carl has borrowed his car so as to pick up the couch. A third and last example, is one taken from the history of science – the discovery of the planet Neptune:

At the beginning of the nineteenth century, it was discovered that the orbit of Uranus, one of the seven planets known at the time, departed from the orbit as predicted on the basis of Isaac Newton's theory of universal gravitation and the auxiliary assumption that there were no further planets in the solar system. One possible explanation was, of course, that Newton's theory is false. Given its great empirical successes for (then) more than two centuries, that did not appear to be a very good explanation. Two astronomers, John Couch Adams and Urbain Leverrier, instead suggested (independently of each other but almost simultaneously) that there was an eighth, as yet undiscovered planet in the solar system; that, they thought, provided the best explanation of Uranus' deviating orbit. Not much later, this planet, which is now known as "Neptune," was discovered (Douven 2021).

As these examples illustrate, and they are not unusual in any way, abductive reasoning is an integral part of human reasoning from the most mundane circumstances of one's own environment, to one's conspecifics, and even right up to contexts of scientific discovery. In fact, many such examples can be, *mutatis mutandis*, generated illustrating the ubiquity of abductive

reasoning. Furthermore, were there something like a default stance towards the world⁸⁴, abductive inferences would be one key way in which it is negotiated, maintained, and expressed. But what is abduction?

Abduction is a type of explanatory reasoning. In the modern sense of the term ‘abduction’, it is explanatory reasoning used to justify selection of hypotheses; and as such, it is also referred to as “Inference to the Best Explanation” (Lipton 1991; Douven 2021). Historically, abduction was understood – the term having been coined by Charles Sanders Peirce – as a type of explanatory reasoning used in generating hypotheses (Douven 2021). Although the exact form and normative status of abductive inference is still a matter of debate, there are certain well understood and generally accepted aspects of it (Ibid.). It is a species of non-necessary inferences. This means that if all the premises are true, then it *is possible* for the conclusion to be false. Hence, the truth of the premises *does not guarantee* the truth of the conclusion. Moreover, abduction is ampliative: the content of the conclusion goes over and above the premises, the conclusion being an expression of novel content. Furthermore, abductive inference is non-monotonic; it violates monotonicity, which means that it is possible abductively to infer from a subset of premises S something that cannot be deductively inferred from the set S as a

⁸⁴ David Papineau, (Ed.) .2001. “The Natural Ontological Attitude” (Arthur Fine), “NOA’s Ark — Fine for Realism” (Alan Musgrave) *Oxford Readings in The Philosophy of Science*, New York, NY: Oxford University Press Inc, 21–44; 45–60.

whole.

Figure 1.

Using the example of John and Carl above, John would not be rationally warranted to infer from the fact that his car and car keys are missing, along with the previous conversation with Carl, that Carl borrowed his car so as to pick up the new couch, if he also knew that his ex-girlfriend, with whom he had a non-amicable break up, hates him and still has a copy of his car keys. By contrast, deductive inference does not violate monotonicity.

Yet, what is induction? As Igor Douven indicates in his *Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy* article on abduction:

Inductive inferences form a somewhat heterogeneous class, but for present purposes they may be characterized as those inferences that are based purely on statistical data, such as observed frequencies of occurrences of a particular feature in a given population (Douven 2021).

Suitably, then, an example of this sort of inference would be as follows:

According to a structural survey entitled Religion 2018–2020 conducted by the Swiss Federal Statistics Office and focused on permanent residents : (1) 34.4 % are Roman Catholic (2) 22.5 % are Protestant (3) 29.4 % have no religious affiliation (4) 5.4 % are members or are associated with “Muslim and Islamic” communities (5) 7.2 % identify as other (6) 1.1% are of unknown religious affiliation.

Claudia is a permanent resident of Switzerland.

Therefore, Claudia is Roman Catholic.

Yet, some inductive arguments, though relying on statistical data, may not make explicit mention of such data in their premises or conclusion. For example:

Most people living in Orange County, CA are affluent.

Sebastian lives in Orange County, CA.

Therefore, Sebastian is affluent.

This argument is well-understood to rely on statistical data, this data being only vaguely referred to by a qualitative adverb notwithstanding. It must be noted, however, that simply because an inference relies on statistical data *does not in and of itself* make such an inference inductive.

Consider the following example: Michael has observed many black ravens and no white ravens.

From this, he concludes that all ravens are black. (This, of course, is not so, since there are albino

ravens.) He draws his conclusion because this, or so he thinks, *best explains* his observations. But this would make his inference a case of abductive inference.⁸⁵

What, then, distinguishes inductive inference (respectively: induction) from abductive inference (respectively: abduction), and how are we to tell them apart?⁸⁶ Both species of inference are non-necessary, ampliative, and violate monotonicity. Despite the shared properties of abductive and inductive inference, they are not the same. For they do not share all their properties in common. Inductive inference relies *only* on statistical data; whereas abductive inference relies both on statistical data *and* certain explanatory considerations (Ibid).

Additionally, much more could be said about all three forms of inference. However, such a discussion would take us too far from the central points needing-to-be-made here, namely: points concerning the dire prospects of a formal explication of (or formal solution to) the ethical module in question. As may already be discerned, the point of discussing these forms of inference is to provide a relevance context for the greater discussion regarding the aforementioned prospects of a formal explication of the ethical module, the latter of which playing a pivotal role in the development of the conceptual tools necessary in developing or discussing the development of a model whereby and through which ethics can be established as an internal feature of artificial intelligence systems. So, in contrast to a protracted discussion regarding the aforementioned types of inference in and of themselves, the following table will suffice as a summary⁸⁷ of key features of such inferences:

⁸⁵ This example is an adaptation from Igor Douven's rather good article from 2021 on the subject of abduction, namely: "Abduction", *The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy* (Summer Edition), Edward N. Zalta (ed.), URL = <<https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/sum2021/entries/abduction/>>.

⁸⁶A related question of interest would be: How, then, are we to understand the relationship between inductive inference (respectively: induction) and abductive inference (respectively: abduction)? The answer is a matter of debate within the literature on abduction. For example, Gilbert Harman holds that abduction is a type of inductive inference (Harman 1965, 88–95). Much more can be said about this, but that discussion must be pushed off to another time, because it is not germane to addressing the issues central to the current book.

⁸⁷ The summary below serves as an overview so as to bolster a more comprehensive understanding. To it, however, an additional point, in the spirit of fostering greater understanding, may prove useful, namely: all utilize some

Deductive	Inductive	Abductive
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Necessary inference ● Closed under provability ● Monotonic ● Inferences rely on tautological consequence and argument form 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Non-necessary inference ● Ampliative ● Non-monotonic ● Inferences appeal only to statistical data 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Non-necessary inference ● Ampliative ● Non-monotonic ● Inferences appeal to statistical data and explanatory considerations

Table 2.

Now, a formal system of any of the above classes of logical inference is unable to deal well with a domain of inquiry whose members are of the type of “fuzzy factors” mentioned above. This is because – taking deduction first – these factors heavily involve non-necessary

truth-preserving parameter; that is, some way of controlling for the risk of making the transition from truth to falsity. In the case of deduction, the aforementioned parameter is explicated as the notion of “closed under provability”; whereas, in the case of induction and abduction, it is explicated in terms of statistical data (induction) and explanatory considerations (abduction).

inferences. Hence, the mechanics of deduction are not suitable or potentially misleading as to the relevance and role these factors play. With induction, we fare no better. For this class of logical inference, insofar as it relies on statistical features and frequency of occurrence of a state, property and the like, remains not fine-grained enough or too wrongly focused in its orientation towards relevant features to deal well with the aforementioned “fuzzy factors”. This is because these “fuzzy factors” are not inherently statistical in nature nor need they incidentally involve statistical features nor are about frequency of the occurrence of a state, property, or the like. Abduction, likewise, leaves us wanting; for it provides little to gain purchase on these “fuzzy factors”: though this needs to be understood aright.

The modern take on abduction as a form of explanatory reasoning used to justify selection of hypotheses and, *mutatis mutandis*, more broadly used to justify selection of best *explanans* for a given *explanandum* so long as the former satisfies certain criteria of explanatory adequacy as well as concomitant methodological virtues (e.g., simplicity, parsimony, robustness, elegance)⁸⁸ is – taking a metaperspective on the current discussion – being utilized throughout the course of this discussion, even to argue against *certain forms of its application*. Accordingly, it is formalized abductive reasoning which is not well suited to handle these “fuzzy factors”. For these factors share certain attributes intractable to formalized abductive reasoning. Some of these factors are: (1) indeterminacy as to application (e.g., due to being open-textured) (2) non-distinctiveness (e.g., as a result of being vaguely bordered,) (3) endemically and irrevocably intertwined multifariousness (e.g, by virtue of being holistic and multidimensional) (4) implicit (e.g., owing to being tacit).

⁸⁸ Some have used these features as a means of explicating abduction. (Forster, M. and Sober, E., 1994. “How to Tell when Simpler, More Unified, or Less *Ad Hoc*, Theories will Provide More Accurate Predictions,” *British Journal for the Philosophy of Science*, 45: 1–36.; Li, M. and Vitanyi, P., 1997. *An Introduction to Kolmogorov Complexity and its Applications*, New York: Springer.; Sober, E., 2015. *Ockham’s Razor: A User’s Manual*, Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.)

Formalization, even of abductive reasoning, regarding items and events in the world requires designation by some features of the formalization (e.g., constants, variables, etc.); and for these designations to be correct and sensible, they must “lock onto” non-spurious regularities.⁸⁹ Thus, there need be a measure of determinacy as to the nature of the phenomena needing-to-be-designated, at least enough to make designation practicable. But being open-textured is precisely one of these “fuzzy factors” which makes getting a designation of the sort in question off the ground difficult in the first place. Moreover, if something is vaguely bordered, then this runs counter to the distinctiveness necessary for precise enough reference whereby one can formalize. This being due to the phenomena (in virtue of its properties) running counter to the distinctiveness needed for formalization, unless this phenomena is sharply bordered. The sort of non-distinctiveness in question is similar to tactile illusions, say: when one immerses their own hand in still water of the same temperature. After some time, one loses proprioception of one's hand as a distinct object apart from the water. The sense of unity this illusion engenders runs counter to the distinctiveness of the feeling of one's own hand. Hence, without this sharp bordering of the feeling of one's own hand, due to this peculiar immersion effect, this is sufficient to produce the feeling of non-distinctiveness in question. So too, a phenomena being vaguely bordered is sufficient to yield non-distinctiveness, in the relevant sense, which in turn blocks securing precise enough reference necessary for formalization. Furthermore, formalization of the sort in question requires analysis. But analysis, by its very nature, often requires breaking down something to its clear and distinct parts.⁹⁰ This is because

⁸⁹ For an expanded discussion on the relevance of non-spurious regularities for logic and epistemology, the author directs the reader to the following works as a way into the topic: Goodman, Nelson, 1955, *Fact, Fiction and Forecast*, Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press and Hacking, Ian. 1994. “Entrenchment” in *Grue! The New Riddle of Induction*, Douglas Stalker (ed.), Chicago, IL: Open Court Publishing Company, 193–224.

⁹⁰ This, of course, assumes that something has parts, proper or otherwise. But for sufficiently simple things that are partless, analysis of such a thing at the very least requires clear and rigorous explanations and justifications regarding why they are simple and partless, what function or role they play (if any), their causal histories, persistence conditions (if relevant), what they consist in, etc.

analysis is often reductive in nature. Though, for something holistic, this can often not be done without violence done to the very thing in need of analysis; and even if it could, this would likely not yield the correct desired understanding. This is, at least partly, due to the fact that something holistic often has a deep background structure that gives rise to and accounts for its holism (e.g., the physical universe). So we must be careful here as to the fecundity, scope, and type of analysis employed.⁹¹ Lastly, formalization, of the sort in question, requires explicit descriptions. But that which is tacit is implicit. The implicit can, nonetheless, be made explicit (e.g., the tacit rule of thumb: don't call a service hotline for a company ten minutes before they close, if you want decent service), though not always without difficulty. Some of these difficulties are knowing what to make explicit or even how much to make explicit. The difficulties of the former are a bit more obvious, the latter less so. With the latter one thing that quickly becomes clear is that the more one makes explicit the greater the risk of exponential complexity and combinatorial explosion: the descriptions quickly become so complex they are simply unwieldy. Additionally, not everything really can be made explicit (e.g., the *Background*).⁹²

To be certain abductive reasoning is still an expedient methodology used herein as a means or conceptual tool for this overall discussion concerning establishing ethics as an internal feature of autonomous artificial intelligence systems. Thankfully, though, a non-formal solution is more dynamic in that it suffers from none of the above restrictions of formalized abduction. Besides, such a solution leaves room for the operation of creative problem-solving and exploratory forms of reasoning giving due attention to features of aesthetic argumentation.⁹³ This latter sort of reasoning has a holistic thrust providing reasons to believe a claim or view based on

⁹¹ Nevertheless, it must be admitted that certain forms of analysis are obviously helpful, namely: again, taking a metaperspective on the current discussion, that which is being employed by the author.

⁹² See Searle's 1987 book entitled *Intentionality* New York: Cambridge University Press, 141–159.

⁹³ In this connection, please see Charles Taylor's 1985, *Human Agency and Language: Philosophical Papers 1* and *Human Agency and Language: Philosophical Papers 2* Cambridge: Harvard University Press.

an all-things-considered assessment of how well the view proposed fits into an overall cogent conceptual mosaic not necessarily in an effort to find the best explanation. Some of the relevant features here being such things as fittingness, coherence, and dynamic equilibrium. All of this supplies a non-formal solution (and approach) with a subtleness, flexibility, and fecundity sorely needed to address the mainstay queries driving this discussion.

Now, with the concerns that the formal explication of the ethical module is the best way to proceed in responding to the issues needing-to-be-addressed laid to rest, or so the author hopes, we move forthwith to articulating and explicating the needful and fervently sought-after non-formal explication of the ethical module.

1.5.0 Ethical Analysis Tool Set Module: How to Proceed

As stated in the previous section, the ethical module consists in the function of assessing the quality of the value-aspect of technology and consists of the following parameters: (1) an ethical template (2) a metaphysics of human persons (3) a conception of responsibility (4) an ontology of technical artifacts, all these being individually necessary and jointly sufficient for the functionality of the ethical module. With this brief overview in mind, let us now turn to the explication of this module forthwith.

1.5.1 Ethical Template

We begin with the ethical template. The reader may recall from the *Introduction* (1–3; 17–23)⁹⁴, that this consists in a characterization of morality designed to function as a broad-based template for patterns of moral concerns, preferences, specific judgements, and the like. This characterization is posited in order to avoid referential vagueness and semantic ambivalence so

⁹⁴ In fact, the following is recapitulated from the introduction and herein elaborated upon further.

as to provide some substance to the domain of inquiry possessing the name ‘morality’; or so it is hoped. Again, this characterization is not intended to define morality, not intended to be an exhaustive treatment, nor to constitute a pivotal feature of a grand unified ethical theory pertaining to “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems. Rather, it is intended to be workable: a useful conceptual tool. Simultaneously, this template, being a middle-ground between both descriptive and normative senses of morality and their respective concomitant approaches (see *Introduction*), is to balance the two. The nature of the template in question is constructed as follows. It consists of four parameters: (1) benevolence (2) impartiality and intelligibility (3) respect for personhood and self-representationality (4) substitutional accountability, each of which are individually necessary and jointly sufficient for the ethical template and will in turn be considered.

Benevolence. The relevance of the parameter is rather straightforward. One way to appreciate this is to consider one expression as to why ethics matters in dealing with “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems, “Ethics is important. We want machines to treat us well” (Moor 2006, 21). Moreover, for the type of machine in question to be counted as treating humans well, they must at least not be harmful, and preferably even redound to the benefit of humanity: promoting human wellness and wellbeing, not detracting from it. Additionally, this parameter seems without little to contest its inclusion, though it would benefit from historical contextualization so as to promote understanding. From the mid-20th century until the present, philosophy of technology has consisted of two workstreams: (1) that which focused on the scientific and engineering aspects of technology and (2) that which focused on the social and political implications of the development, maintenance, and use of technology (Franssen, et al.

2018). With the second focus, concern for the social and political implications of technology was, quite naturally, connected to human flourishing.

Impartiality and intelligibility. This parameter is to promote unbiased judgements that make sense to those affected by them. Moreover, it would mean that outputs of an “autonomous” artificial intelligence system utilized to assist, or even replace, the judgements of a human person in some social situation are not unduly favoring the interests of any particular group, not motivated out of a prejudice concerning the person or persons affected by the decision(s), nor favoring some unjustified ideological commitment or idiosyncrasy of those responsible for the judgment, for example: in determinations concerning recidivism (Northpointe 2015; Haas 2017)⁹⁵. Yet, it would also mean that the judgements are clear and make sense: explainable.

As such, opacity would need to be controlled for or ideally ruled out entirely. This is a problem which “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems face, especially those of a blackboxed architecture. Though blackboxed systems of the relevant sort are not the only ones that need be concerned with opacity; it is, nonetheless, a peculiarly nasty problem for such systems. Moreover, the crux of the opacity problem is this: the challenge of making intelligible the relationship between such a system’s functionality in terms of the content of its algorithm(s) and its outputs given its inputs: traceability. Furthermore, there are two types of opacity problems for “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems. A fuller discussion of all of this with respect to blackboxed “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems as well as those systems of alternative architectures will take place at greater length in the second part of the overall discussion wherein the model whereby and through which ethics can be established as an internal feature of “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems will be evaluated for viability with respect to the

⁹⁵ See also: Anne-Sophie Mayer, Franz Strich, and Marina Fiedler. 2020. "Unintended Consequences of Introducing AI Systems for Decision Making." *MIS Quarterly Executive* 19 (4): 239–257.

aforementioned three key challenges of the autonomy problem, enforceability problem, and opacity problem.

Now, the parameter in question, like the previous one, would benefit from historical contextualization in order to promote understanding. From the beginning of the 21st century until the present, the discipline of machine ethics has picked up momentum (Anderson and Anderson 2011; Pereira and Lopes 2020). Of course, concern for the ethical dimensions of machines preceded the incipience of the field of machine ethics, which is something neither denied nor ignored in machine ethics. Yet, in machine ethics there were two important shifts in understanding that are relevant for this project.

The first shift in understanding involved wondering whether it was possible that a machine would be ethical in some internal sense, with the question being something like: ‘How does one get a machine (e.g., an “autonomous” artificial intelligence system) to do ethics?’. This interrogative expressed something far different than a query concerning a machine’s output or behavior conforming to, say, norms of morality or moral norms; this would be mere ethical compliance, a concern of which represents nothing new (Moor 2006). The enhanced inquiry expressed by the interrogative concerned whether a machine’s output could be ethically compliant by means of its own internal programming in such a way that insofar as it was, its programming was executing some form of ethical analysis from a defined set of ethical principles, maxims, and certain heuristics or is following ethical design norms in addition to whatever engineering design norms in the generation of its outputs (Ibid; Wallach 2008).

The second shift in understanding involved adoption of both of the aforementioned workstreams of philosophy of technology, namely: social and political implications and scientific and engineering aspects of technology. This can be seen in the concern not just for impartial and

intelligible outputs of “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems, but with the very inner-workings of such systems so as to better track the nature of the relationship between the science and engineering aspects, on the one hand, and the social and political implications of the development, deployment, and upkeep of such technological systems, on the other hand. This can also be seen in such movements, arguably, within machine ethics as well as “ethically aligned design”⁹⁶ initiatives and prospective visions for the relationship between ethics and technology instead of the retrospective visions dominant in the 20th century (Gonzalez 2013; Franssen, et al. 2018; How 2018).

Respect for personhood and self-representationality. The heart of this parameter is, at the very least, rooted in autonomy. This sense of ‘autonomy’ comes from philosophy, and refers to the capacity to provide one’s own customs, norms, rules, and laws for oneself, all of which are based on the ability to think of and select freely which of these one wishes to follow (EGESNT 2018). Having and exercising such autonomy requires certain cognitive processes which were traditionally thought to facilitate and enable this, namely: rationality, freewill, and self-awareness (Ibid; Levine 2004). Moreover, autonomy in this sense is traditionally thought to be the cornerstone of what makes us, in the fullest sense, dignified human persons. It is in virtue of this sense of autonomy, possessed of human persons, that respect for personhood and how a human person self-represents (and self-understands) is to be respected.

All of this becomes peculiarly relevant in dealing with “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems. For in this regard, there are two key questions to consider which have great implications for moral responsibility: Is the sense of ‘autonomous’, here, identical? What are the

⁹⁶ The IEEE Global Initiative on Ethics of Autonomous and Intelligent Systems .2019. “Ethically Aligned Design: A Vision for Prioritizing Human Well-being with Autonomous and Intelligent Systems.” *IEEE Advancing Technology for Humanity*, available online: https://standards.ieee.org/content/dam/ieee-standards/standards/web/documents/other/ead_v2.pdf (accessed 01.06.2022).

implications of a positive or negative answer to the preceding question? In virtue of these considerations, the parameter in question takes on special significance within the intersection of moral responsibility and “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems.

Substitutional accountability. The basic idea behind this parameter can be seen in the concept of oversight. In such a context, for example: within that of an organization, there is someone to which another must answer or provide a response to regarding one’s judgements and behavior. This idea of oversight as understood in an organizational context is, in its basecase context, social in nature. As such, it constitutes one of many social requirements. Moreover, this idea of oversight lies at the heart of the concept underpinning the parameter in question: accountability.

Accordingly, any person in a social role must fulfill the social requirements of that role, and one of these requirements is moral accountability.⁹⁷ Furthermore, any entity, for example: an “autonomous” artificial intelligence system (e.g., an “autonomous” artificial institutional adviser), filling a traditionally human role in the public space must fulfill the social requirements pertaining to that role, one of which just is moral accountability (Bostrom and Yudkowsky 2014, 316–334).⁹⁸

This requirement, bespoken of by the parameter of *substitutional accountability*, draws its merit in the current discussion by referring directly to the problem of enforceability for

⁹⁷ Even if a case can be made that the relevant species of accountability be organizational, for example: in accordance with the constitution or bylaws of a particular organization, the content of the constitution or bylaws would not be determinable apart from moral accountability, as was the case with governmental or legal forms of responsibility. This, of course, would not necessarily mean that the content of those bylaws or constitutional statements would need to be overtly moral, namely: making explicit moral claims. It is enough that they implicitly rely on moral claims for the relevance of moral accountability.

⁹⁸ More will be written about the concept of moral accountability later in the overall discussion of this book; and in so doing, this concept will be distinguished from the concept of moral responsibility.

“autonomous” artificial intelligence systems. The problem can be expressed well in asking: ‘How can moral accountability be enforced for an “autonomous” artificial intelligence system?’⁹⁹

Having read the above explication of the ethical template in terms of its own parameters, even if one were immediately to appreciate the sensibleness behind inclusion of the ethical template itself as a parameter of the ethical module, the query as to why it is a necessary condition for this module remains open. With a view to addressing this query, the following considerations are provided. For the ethical module to perform its function, which consists in assessing the quality of the value aspect of technology, it must be of sufficient versatility and robustness to address each of the points of concern regarding the human-technology relationship. This is because the human-technology relationship is not a straightforward generative relationship wherein humans simply produce some artifact or other and then subsequently stand in a passive divested relationship to their product. Rather, the nature of the relation R between humans and technology is one of co-mediation.

The term ‘co-mediation’ is borrowed from the work of Peter-Paul Verbeek. In his contribution, “Subject to technology: On autonomic computing and human autonomy”, in the volume entitled *Law, Human Agency and Autonomic Computing: The Philosophy of Law Meets the Philosophy of Technology*¹⁰⁰, he uses the term to express an idea central to his analysis of sociotechnology, namely: that humans produce technology in such a way that we determine its nature, purpose, instrumentality, and the like, in a comprehensive, yet not totalizing manner; for we do so at the level of design, development, and deployment; yet nonetheless, not in a unidirectional way. The technical artifacts we produce also shape our conception of what can and

⁹⁹ We will return to an expanded discussion of the concept of enforceability in the third chapter of the current book.

¹⁰⁰ Verbeek, Peter-Paul. 2011. “Subjects to technology: on autonomic computing and human autonomy.” in Hildebrandt, M. and Rouvroy, A.(eds.), *Law, Human Agency and Autonomic Computing: The Philosophy of Law Meets The Philosophy of Technology*, 27–45. New York: Routledge.

needs to be produced, our lived-self-understanding as well as our comportment in the world, all of which in turn confects our interests and preferences, at the very least, which in turn engenders new vistas and avenues of approach to technological investigation and development. Thereupon, the direction of influence is both ways human-to-technology and technology-to-human. Hence, the conception of human technological production is not totalizing in that it remains fundamentally open in both directions such that the relation R (henceforth: R_{CM}) is one of mutual transformative articulation: we bring technical artifacts into being forged out of mind and matter which in turn shapes our own being-in-the-world and concomitant technological aspirations and activities constituting a new dialogue of mutual shaping capable of not only transforming our phenomenology and hermeneutics, but potentially our ontological categories¹⁰¹, epistemology¹⁰², axiology¹⁰³, and even the existential structure¹⁰⁴ of our lives.

Accordingly, any assessment of technology from an ethical perspective must take this relationship into account in a serious way, due to the bidirectionality of the relationship and the scope of the influence for both *relata*. Hence, we need a way to make sense of this dynamic

¹⁰¹ In this regard, please see both Muhammad Ali Khalidi's 2013 (*Natural Categories and Human Kinds*, New York: Cambridge University Press) and Julia R.S. Bursten's 2020, *Perspectives On Classification in Synthetic Sciences: Unnatural Kinds*, New York: Routledge, Taylor & Francis.

¹⁰² Please see: Langley, Christelle, et al. *Frontiers in Artificial Intelligence*. Apr 05, 2022 as well as Manchingal, Shireen Kudukkil and Cuzzolin, Fabio. Presented at ICML 2022 Workshop on Distribution-free Uncertainty Quantification. Jul 23, 2022.

¹⁰³ In this connection, please see: Anderson, Michael and Anderson, Susan Leigh (eds.) *Machine Ethics*, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, 21–27, Allen, Colin and Wallach, Wendell .2014. "Moral Machines: Contradiction in Terms or Abdication of Human Responsibility?" in Lin Patrick, Abney, Keith and Bekey, George A. (eds.), *Robot Ethics: The Ethical and Social Implications of Robotics*, MIT Press, Cambridge, MA, 55–68, and Floridi, Luciano. 2011. "On the Morality of Artificial Agents", in Anderson, Michael and Anderson, Susan Leigh (eds.), *Machine Ethics*, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, 184–212.

¹⁰⁴ Regarding this possibility, please consider the following: Bostrom, Nick. 2012 "The Superintelligent Will: Motivation and Instrumental Rationality in Advanced Artificial Agents", *Minds & Machines*, 22: 71, available online: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11023-012-9281-3>, Warwick, K. 2014. The Cyborg Revolution. *Nanoethics* 8, 263–273. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11569-014-0212-z>, Warwick, K., Shah, H. 2016. Passing the Turing Test Does Not Mean the End of Humanity. *Cogn Comput* 8, 409–419. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12559-015-9372-6>, and Bostrom, Nick. 2017. "The ethical issues of advanced artificial intelligence.", Paper presented at the IAS 2003, Baden Baden, DE. In Smit, S., Wallach, W., and Lasker, L. (eds.) *Cognitive, Emotive and Ethical Aspects of Decision Making in Humans and in Artificial Intelligence*, vol. 11, IAS, 12–17, all of which taken together, or so it is hoped, provide a nuanced assessment on the potential effect of co-mediation between humanity and our "autonomous" artificial intelligence systems for the existential structure of human life.

relationship between humans and their technology, and thereby technical artifacts like “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems. The ethical template is precisely the sort of tool to do this. This is because it has features conducive to making sense of the relation R_{CM} .

The relation R_{CM} is such that it instantiates as different possible tokens of the relation-type R_{CM} :

$$R_{CM}^T: \{ \diamond R_{CM}^1, \diamond R_{CM}^2, \diamond R_{CM}^3, \dots, \diamond R_{CM}^N \}$$

Moreover, the ethical template’s parameters, and thereby the ethical template itself, are sensitively calibrated and multidimensional such that they allow access to key aspects of the relation R_{CM} with respect to technical artifacts, including “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems. ‘Access’ is here understood as “makes intelligible and enters into the performance stream” of the interactive dynamic that obtains between the *relata* of the relation R_{CM} so as to guide selection of the possible tokens thereof from an ethical perspective. This thus makes the ethical template itself a key component of the ethical module providing it with resources to function as part of the conceptual framework tool which serves as the context within which and whence ethical models regarding the technical artifacts, “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems or otherwise, are generated. To see the efficaciousness of the ethical template’s parameters in this regard, each parameter in turn shall be further elaborated upon in relation to both the relation R_{CM} and “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems in particular.

Taking the parameter of *benevolence*, the co-mediative relationship between humans and “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems is one that can either redound to the benefit or detriment of humanity. Due to its potential to go either way, which in turn is due to the dynamism of this relationship, it is important to ensure and promote human well-being and

wellness at all stages of the technology life cycle: design, development, and deployment.¹⁰⁵ One way to illustrate the importance of the benevolent outlook in question as it relates to the aforementioned dynamism, is to consider that technological development is non-linear: its growth output *Z* is greater than its growth input *Y*. As such, its development can proceed at an astonishing rate leading to a large proliferation of technical artifacts and systems in society. In light of this, it is important, from the outset, to have a firm commitment to pursue technological innovation or production that is not only compliant with the strong preference that, “Ethics is important. We want machines to treat us well” (Moor 2006, 21), but positively promoting technological production and innovation that implements principles based on this strong preference in the form of a condition of satisfaction needing-to-be-met throughout the entire life cycle of technical artifacts and systems used either privately or publicly. This would mean a prospective outlook towards incorporation of principles grounded in a premium put on benevolence, instead of the modern predominant outlook which is largely retrospective and concerned with *ad hoc* “ethical fixes and patchwork”.

One might inveigh, however, that this is all well and good, but redundant nonetheless. For we already have a practicable set of principles grounded in the content that serves as the explication of the aforementioned parameter, namely: safety critical principles. What is more, we even have proposed norms and standards that aid in the prioritization and implementation of these principles¹⁰⁶. In response to this objection, it must be noted that the safety critical principles

¹⁰⁵ The first two stages are obvious, but the latter may not be. What is meant by ‘deployment’ is the utilization of such systems in society, either privately or publicly. This includes, but is not limited to, release of such systems in their various versions. It also includes upkeep, maintenance, and retooling. Furthermore, the use of the alliteration in the formulation of ‘design, development, and deployment’ serves as a good memory device as well as illustrates the close association of ideas which is meant to track the close association to one another of each phase of the technological life cycle of the relevant technology.

¹⁰⁶ European Commission. 2019. *European Commission, Directorate-General for Communications Networks, Content and Technology, Ethics guidelines for trustworthy AI*. 2019. Publications Office <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2759/346720>.

and the concomitant practices in question have protecting profit margins, protecting of company reputation, and avoiding lawsuits as the primary motivation, not benevolence in the relevant sense. As a rejoinder, one might point out two things. First, it is not possible to determine whether benevolence is not among the motivations for safety critical principles and their implementation strategies. This is because such internal motivations are not determinable with certainty. Second, it seems a bit pessimistic and unfair – insofar as the benefit of doubt not having been extended – to claim that benevolence is not among the rational motivations behind the current safety critical principles and implementation practices thereof. For admittedly, the other aforementioned motivations are not unreasonable, and simply because those are present doesn't mean that benevolence, in the relevant sense, is not also present as a rational motivation. In rebuttal, it must be noted that: (1) if benevolence, in the relevant sense, is not determinable with any certainty as a rational motivation for the current safety critical principles and implementation practices, then although there may be no basis to deny its presence, there is also no basis to assert its presence among the aforementioned rational motivations; and were the parameter *benevolence* under debate brought to the forefront and made an explicit principled basis for safety critical principles and their implementation, we could be certain that benevolence is one of the rational motivations grounding such principles or chief among any set of safety critical principles and implementation practices (2) conflicts of interest rooted in a desire for profit (however defined), desire to protect or promote one's own reputation, and the like run orthogonal to and even positively counter to motivations rooted in moral concerns are not unheard; in fact, they are commonplace, which provides sufficient reason for concern about this, making the latter not overly pessimistic or unfair. Therefrom, there are on the whole better reasons in favor of the parameter *benevolence*.

But how is this parameter a necessary condition for the ethical template? It is so in virtue of rational practice. That is, it is required to make intelligible the co-mediated relationship between humans and “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems that ultimately redounds to the benefit of humanity. Moreover, it is also required to guide optimization of the viability of this relationship toward beneficial outcomes for humanity, or at the very least not harmful ones. This guidance includes explicating what “redound to humanity’s benefit” would even consists in, individuating the nature of the relationship in terms of what possible co-mediated *Gestaltung* must obtain that would be consistent with the characterization of what “redound to humanity’s benefit” consists in, determining the goal of a relationship that redounds to the benefit of humanity, what the conditions of satisfaction are that need be met so as to reach this goal, the instrumentality needing-to-be-employed so as to reach this goal, the diagnostic means and methods for recognizing when this goal has not been met, a way forward so as to get back on track should the trajectory of that relationship go astray, as well as how to fix the relationship should things fall apart.

Now, the crux of the parameter *impartiality and intelligibility* is to ensure that any “autonomous” artificial intelligence system fulfills the social requirements of whatever role in which it substitutes for or assists a human being in carrying out a social function. This is absolutely crucial because just as with human persons, it is expected and even needed that a measure of fairness and traceability regarding activities within the social (or private, for that matter) sphere exists and is maintained. Specifically, this would mean the content or functionality of the algorithm not reflecting an undue favoring of the interests of any particular group, not reflecting a motivation out of a prejudice concerning the person or persons affected by the decision(s), nor reflecting an arbitrary favoring or favoring in an unjustified manner of some

ideological commitment or idiosyncrasy of those responsible for the judgment, on the one hand; and illuminatory of the chain of justification or explanation – demonstrating sufficient reason for each element in the chain – resulting in some decision, behavior, or the like, on the other hand. This parameter, then, would provide the conditions of satisfaction needing-to-be-met as well as guide the selection of the concrete relationship compliant with these conditions of satisfaction that would obtain between humans and “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems such that such systems in terms of their design norms and corresponding architecture would be consistent with principles of fairness, fairplay and transparency.

It might be considered to be common sense and even redundant to hold that we need such a parameter as the aforementioned. For of course we want “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems that are consistent with fairness, fairplay and transparent in their renderings. And there is no need to have a parameter to ensure what is already known to be needed or strongly desired. Moreover, we already have in development protocols to ensure transparency, for example data and algorithm auditing procedures as ways of fighting against lack of transparency, fairness, and fairplay. Furthermore, if it is well-known that we want such systems, then there is no need to have a parameter to ensure we have what we already know we should have only if it is common sense. Additionally, the parameter under examination would be novel only if such measures were lacking or even lacking in development, which they are not.

This objection fails to appreciate, but is admittedly poignant withal, the implementation dimensions of the problem herein being addressed. For even if the efficacy of the argumentation and its conclusion, namely: that the parameter *impartiality and intelligibility* is granted, it doesn't address the issue of implementation in question. The parameter under examination is germane to addressing the implementation problem in that, as was already stated, the point of each parameter

is to guide selection of possible relational configurations between “autonomous” artificial intelligence system and humanity such that, at least in the case of the parameter in question, fairness, fairplay and transparency are not only obvious and even to some extent normative as troubleshooting mechanisms, but prospective and extant.

In rejoinder, it might be noted that as long as there are efforts in this direction, then the proposed parameter of the ethical template adds nothing new to ongoing research and development (i.e., R&D) and engineering practice – even if the latter is at its incipiency. Hence, progress in R&D and engineering practice would not be maintained. But innovation is required. In fact, innovation is required, unless progress in R&D and engineering practice is not maintained. Thus, if progress in R&D and engineering practice is to be maintained, then innovation is required. Yet, in rebuttal, one could grant the point espoused in the conclusion of the rejoinder acknowledging the force of the conditional whilst holding that the parameter of the ethical template in question satisfies the requirement of innovation. For it aids R&D and engineering practice in that it provides a novel design feature which bodes to improve implementation of ethical design norms through providing its own condition of satisfaction needing-to-be-met, along with that provided by the other parameters of the ethical template, such that the best possible relational configuration (i.e., concrete token of R^T_{CM}) between humanity and “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems obtains. This is all the more so with engineering practice precisely insofar as it is in its incipiency.¹⁰⁷ Adding to this sort of progress is certainly not unheard of or untoward.

¹⁰⁷ Keeping in mind that value-based engineering and ethically-aligned design initiatives are, though appropriately prospective and possessed of many of the virtues for which it is presupposed that the ethical template’s parameters, especially the one in question, would add, in their incipient phases. It must be emphasized, however, that drawing attention to the early phase of such endeavors is not in any way meant to be pejorative.

But how is this parameter a necessary condition for the ethical template? The key to it being so is discernible from our interests, desires, and goals. Broadly speaking, we want to optimize our technology, making it ever better – “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems being no exception in this regard. This centrally involves, though is not limited to, making it more suitable for the sorts of creatures we are: rational, social animals whose rationality is not disentangleable from axiological commitments. This is especially so in light of a clear desire to use such technical systems in social settings (e.g., self-driving vehicles, drones, artificial moral, legal, or institutional advisors, etc.), and in a way that is driven by the impetus of optimization and innovation. This, of course, must meet the social requirements peculiar to the social setting in which “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems are to be utilized. Accordingly, the implementation of such systems not only need to be in line with endeavors of technological optimization and innovation as well as our interests, desires, and goals, but must meet the appropriate social requirements peculiar to the setting in which they are to be implemented. Hence, the parameter in question is a pragmatic necessity for the relevant implementation, since it is what needs to be in place for the service of our aspirations.

Turning now to the third parameter of the ethical template, namely: *Respect for personhood and self-representationality*, the crux of this parameter is to show due recognition to what is distinctive about humanity, namely: personhood and subjectivity; that is, the peculiar nature of these two. Human personhood, as traditionally conceived, is tightly wedded to the concept of autonomy such that it is a defining feature of human personhood. The sense of ‘autonomy’ meant here is characterized above, but bears repeating: the capacity to provide one’s own customs, norms, rules, and laws for oneself, all of which are based on the ability to think of and select freely which of these one wishes to follow (EGESNT 2018). Moreover, the moral

dimensions of human personhood and the moral weight it carries is, at least in part, rooted in the sense of autonomy operative here (Edwards 2018), autonomy in this sense being traditionally thought to be the cornerstone of what makes us, in the fullest sense, dignified human persons.¹⁰⁸

Subjectivity, namely: the peculiar form of subjectivity that is an integral part of the human condition, shaping and informing this condition's richness – the epistemic dimensions thereof, which inform our understanding of consciousness¹⁰⁹, its structure, which informs existential concerns and priorities¹¹⁰, and even its kind-defining import for personhood itself¹¹¹, is similarly important. This is because its dynamic structure affords for the peculiar nature of human mental life. In fact, having and exercising the aforementioned autonomy requires cognitive processes, endemic to human subjectivity, which were traditionally thought to facilitate and enable subjectivity (as well as autonomy), namely: rationality, freewill, and self-awareness (Ibid; Levine 2004). As such, the concept of the autonomous person and the peculiar nature of human subjectivity buttress each other such that both together provide the rational motivation for respecting human personhood and how a human person self-represents (and self-understands) is to be respected.

¹⁰⁸ For more on this, please see the following: Christman, John. 2020. "Autonomy in Moral and Political Philosophy", *The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy* (Fall Edition), Edward N. Zalta (ed.), URL = <<https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/fall2020/entries/autonomy-moral/>>; Buss, Sarah and Westlund, Andrea "Personal Autonomy", *The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy* (Spring Edition), Edward N. Zalta (ed.), URL = <<https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/spr2018/entries/personal-autonomy/>>. ; and O'Neill, Onora. 2004. *Autonomy and Trust in Bioethics*. Cambridge, England: Cambridge University Press.

¹⁰⁹ Tye, Michael, "Qualia". 2021. *The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy* (Fall Edition), Edward N. Zalta (ed.), URL = <<https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/fall2021/entries/qualia/>>.

¹¹⁰ For a position on how this would take shape, please see Ludwig Binswanger's, 1992 – 94, *Ludwig Binswanger: Ausgewählte Werke in Vier Bänden, Vol.1 – 3*. Heidelberg, Baden-Württemberg, Deutschland: Roland Asanger Verlag as well as Ludwig Binswanger's 1963, *Being-in-the-World: Selected Papers of Ludwig Binswanger*, Needleman, J., (trans.) Translated and with a Critical Introduction to His Existential Psychoanalysis New York: Basic Books, Inc.

¹¹¹ See both volumes of Charles Taylor's, 1985, *Human Agency and Language: Philosophical Papers*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press. See also: Shoemaker, S. (2011). Personhood and consciousness. In J. Liu & J. Perry (Eds.), *Consciousness and the Self: New Essays* (pp. 198-213). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. doi:10.1017/CBO9780511732355.010.

One might object that this is all well and good, but so what? That humans are like this is partly constitutive of what gives rise to all technology, since the sophistication it evidences is what makes artifacts possible at all. As such, it would be the common denominator for all forms of human technology, not a basis in particular for adjudicating between more ethically sound technology and less ethically sound technology in virtue of selecting the more (or even the most) ethically sound token of R_{CM}^T . Hence, though it's important to understand this aspect of human nature, it is not clear how relevant it is for selecting the most ethical configuration of the co-mediated relationship between humanity and “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems. For personhood and subjectivity would be what is common for any configuration of that relationship, so it would not be clear what role a parameter would play which explicitly acknowledges it for the purpose of aiding in selecting a more or even the most ethical configuration of the co-mediated relationship in question: that which is common to all the possible tokens of R_{CM}^T is no difference-maker between them.

Despite the commonality of personhood and subjectivity to all possible configurations of the co-mediated relationship between humanity and technology more generally and “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems in particular, this parameter is, indeed, relevant for providing the rational motivation for the parameter being articulated and justified. This is so because the parameter in question is designed to capitalize on the nature of human personhood and subjectivity by means of providing an explicit way in which to capture its role in shaping our R_{CM} by providing a parameter which explicitly acknowledges and operationalizes these key features of humanity, thereby taking the nature of human personhood and subjectivity seriously and actively including it in engineering R&D and practice, through incorporation of these features into the workflow of selecting more or even the most ethically viable token of R_{CM} ;

thus, for example, embedding respect for human personhood and subjectivity into the design norms, along with functional design norms, of a technical artifact. This would allow for human personhood and subjectivity not only to be in the background of the inspiration, development, and usage of this or that technical artifact, but rather to enter into the workflow of creation of a technical artifact thereby being an explicit factor determining the creation of technical artifacts.

In rejoinder, one might point out that incorporation of human personhood and subjectivity is a rather abstract idea: too abstract to be useful from an engineering perspective. For personhood and subjectivity are not things we can codify or for which one can translate into a data structure, algorithm or the like, or even represent very well in terms of an engineering diagram, functional or otherwise. In reply, one could indicate that the available options for the way to incorporate human personhood and subjectivity into the workflow of engineering R&D and practice are not exhausted by the enumerated options, namely: data structure or algorithm. Moreover, there is a way to concretely incorporate human personhood and subjectivity from an engineering perspective using precisely an engineering diagram.

To see how all of this would work, consider that human personhood and subjectivity would enter into the workflow quite early in the process of creating a technical artifact. As such, it would serve as a control mechanism which places a value constraint on the types of goals to be sought. For example, in making care robots, of course effort is put into making the robots easier to work with, more congenial with which to interact; but inclusion of the parameter in question would preclude or restrict development of care robots that are just as “real” as live-persons or for which one would even pose the issue of authenticity regarding such technical artifacts.¹¹²

¹¹² For an enlightening discussion in this regard, please see Sherry Turkle’s 2011, “Authenticity in the Age of Digital Companions”, in *Machine Ethics*, Anderson, Michael and Anderson, Susan Leigh (eds.), 62–76. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. For an illuminating discussion concerning social robots and human robot interactions that attempts to elaborate an approach consisting of new conceptual tools for the purpose of moving towards a unified theory of human robot interactions, see the following: Seibt, Johanna et al. 2020. “Sociomorphing, Not Anthropomorphizing: Towards a Typology of Experienced Sociality”. In: Nørskov, Marco et al. (Eds.) *Culturally*

Suitably, then, the parameter in question would be operative at one or more phases of development of the life cycle of technology.

Keep in mind that a functional diagram allows one to get an overview of the overall function of a technical artifact, of its collection of sub-functions, and how the sub-functions relate to one another and to the overall function of the technical artifact. Ultimately, it provides information regarding how the practical purpose it is to serve is to be accomplished. Now, to be clear: functional diagrams are used to help understand, from a functional perspective, what a technical artifact is to accomplish and how. We can, though, use the same structure in an illustrative manner so as to explain how the parameter under scrutiny can be incorporated into the life cycle of a technical artifact:

Sustainable Social Robotics—Proceedings of Robophilosophy, 51–67. Amsterdam: IOS Press. One noteworthy aspect about the approach elaborated therein is that it provides considerations that call into question some of the fundamental presuppositions and assumptions which inform discussions and debates regarding the issue of authenticity as it relates to care robots, which can be applied, *mutatis mutandis*, to artificial intelligence systems, “autonomous” or otherwise, more generally.

Figure 2.

The author fully acknowledges the crude nature of the diagram presented. Nevertheless, the diagram is illustrative of a logical workflow with antecedent conditions. Accordingly, the diagram illustrates that the parameter, *respect for personhood and self-representationality*, designated by 'P' in the diagram, is operative at a very early stage of the lifecycle of the development of a care robot (or similar type of technology). This is to limit how well it mimics intelligent human behavior. Furthermore, this all illustrates how the parameter in question: (1) can be made concrete enough to factor into engineering R&D and engineering practice (2) can be incorporated on an engineering diagram. Of course, a concrete consequence of incorporation of this parameter, at least in the case of care robots, is that it is at such an early stage that it determines the goal, course of the technological development, and approach.

Even if the above reasoning is accepted as a strong justification in favor of the parameter in question, one could still ask: But how is it a necessary condition for the ethical template? It is so because it is requisite for prioritizing and maintaining human distinctiveness, which itself rests, at least in part, on human personhood and subjectivity. As such, this parameter underscores that humans are not just things among other things in the environment; but rather have a distinct status due to our nature. Something whose import cannot be overstressed in light of the growing sophistication of artificial intelligence systems, mimicking human behavior with ever greater verisimilitude and refinement, engaging in some daily human behaviors even better than most humans (e.g., driving) and even surpassing human capabilities entirely (e.g., memory).

This puts humanity in a rather curious situation. For the co-mediated relationship that humans have with their technical artifacts, their socio-technology, such as “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems, is such that the status question is answered in favor of humans; that is, humans have a different and higher status than technical artifacts, no matter how refined or complex they may be. This status rests on certain capacities that any artificial intelligence system simply would not possess (e.g., thought, consciousness, freewill); and in the strongest versions of the view – so the Bright-line Argument goes – could not possess.¹¹³ This categorical difference between humans and machines, in general, would extend to artificial intelligence systems, “autonomous” or otherwise. And with the ever-expanding and refinement of capacities of artificial intelligence systems moving even towards artificial general intelligence (AGI),¹¹⁴ the categoricalness is precisely what is being questioned more and more; perhaps, the difference consists more in a spectrum, which of course runs counter to the position supported by the Bright-line Argument (henceforth: BLA).

Without directly taking a particular side in this debate, as doing so would take the discussion too far afield, it is noteworthy that were the BLA or something like it, rejected in light of the optimization of the development of artificial intelligence systems in the trajectory of an AGI, humans in terms of their status risk being put on par with an artificial intelligence system. This, in turn, would risk precipitating a negative cascade effect on human morality. This effect which may be entitled the *Moral Degenerative Cascade Effect (MDCE)* is characterized thusly:

¹¹³ Please see Stevens F. Wandmacher’s 2016 enlightening discussion, “The Bright Line of Ethical Agency”. *Techné: Research in Philosophy and Technology* 20 (3): 240–257.

¹¹⁴ Keep in mind that an artificial general intelligence (AGI) is an artificial intelligence system that can problem-solve for unfamiliar tasks across a wide variety of domains. For more on this see Stuart Russell and Peter Norvig’s 2020 book entitled, *Artificial Intelligence: A Modern Approach*. 4th Edition, London, England: Pearson.

The effect in which our moral sentiments, habits, beliefs, *et cetera*, are negatively affected such that those values no longer support an account of the Good that takes human wellness and wellbeing seriously causing a banal view of human personhood and subjectivity (even to the point of becoming the dominant view). This could, naturally, lead to not respecting other morally significant positions that do take human personhood and subjectivity seriously, such things as human dignity, human rights, the value of human life, and other moral ills which threaten human flourishing (broadly conceived).

Moreover, the problem represented by the *MDCE* is not something that need take the form of a conscious extant position to which one espouses or opposes; rather, it could be far more insidious. Just as one can sit on one's surfboard floating in the ocean chatting with friends not far from shore, all the while gently and nearly imperceptibly being pulled out to sea by the currents' undertow, so too the scope, nature, and depth of the alteration of human morality thereby may be subtle, gradual, and seemingly insignificant until it leads to a surprising transmogrification of our category of axiology, and acutely so for the subcategory of ethics, constituting a substantive degrading of human values and quality of life.

And yet one may withhold assent to their being a serious problem of the relevant sort on a twofold charge. In the first, namely: slippery-slope fallacy which holds that a course of action should be rejected on the basis that were it accepted, it would precipitate a chain of events resulting in some undesirable outcome(s), but no or insufficient support in the form of evidence for the proposed succession of events or some tight logical connection so as to substantiate the logical transition is given (Parker & Moore 2020). An example of this would be a familiar

argument like the following, ‘one shouldn’t smoke cannabis, because it is a “gateway drug” to harder drugs’. This counts as an example because the argument presupposes that on the basis of cannabis smoking one would unrelentingly move to harder drugs. Yet there is no evidence the cannabis in and of itself is a “gateway drug” in the relevant sense.¹¹⁵ Moreover, the position under scrutiny is based on it insofar as it expresses a specious concern justified by a rational consideration instantiating this unreliable logical form. Recall that there are, broadly-speaking, two classes of inference: (1) reliable, namely: those that can guarantee or make more likely a transition from truth to truth (2) unreliable, namely: those that cannot guarantee or make more unlikely a transition from truth to truth, and even can make it more likely (and perhaps even guarantee one) to transition from truth to falsity. The former are the business of the fields of deductive, inductive, and abductive logic, the latter are the business of the fields of critical thinking, informal logic, and the like, both of which benefit from metalogical notions and principles as well as from the principles of theory of argumentation, proof theory, or the body of reasoning best practices and strategies. Each of these classes has its members, and the slippery-slope fallacy is a member of the class of unreliable logical forms or explained in terms of cognitive psychology: unreliable patterns of inference.

Now, how does the reasoning under scrutiny instantiate this unreliable logical form? It does so as follows. It flatly claims that were the BLA rejected and artificial intelligence systems to continue to develop to greater degrees of sophistication even unto something like an AGI, then on that basis a cascade – a chain of events – would be precipitated leading inexorably to an undesirable outcome(s), and it does so by means of providing no or insufficient support in the form of evidence for the proposed succession of events or some tight logical connection so as to

¹¹⁵ For more examples of this fallacy, please consider the following:
<https://www.txst.edu/philosophy/resources/fallacy-definitions/Slippery-Slope.html>.

substantiate the logical transition. As such, the justification provided for this claim is fallacious. This is underscored all the more by further noting that what the reasoning demands is acceptance of a succession of events with little or nothing in the way of sufficient justification as to why this succession of events is to be accepted at all.

Yet, this is not the only problem with the reasoning under examination, so the objection continues: the reasoning also suffers from the fallacy of hyperbole. Recall that this fallacy occurs when in attempting to establish a claim, the support for this claim is exaggerated: made far more strongly than the evidence would substantiate (Ibid). For example, the argument, namely: ‘Many pharmaceutical companies have had to adjust their prices due to recent inflation: prescription drug costs are sky-rocketing out of control!’, commits the fallacy of hyperbole in that it relies on an exaggeration regarding the impact of price adjustment practices in the pharmaceutical industry on prescription drug prices overall, the extent of such impact not being supported by the available evidence. Furthermore, the way in which the argument being criticized suffers from the fallacy of hyperbole is that it exaggerates the impact of increased incorporation of “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems in various aspects of society on becoming a technological dystopia (e.g., the movie, *The Terminator*).

In rebutting the first objection, namely: that the reasoning justifying the concern presented by the *MDCE* is based on a slippery-slope fallacy and the second, namely: that the reasoning justifying the concern presented by the *MDCE* is based on the fallacy of hyperbole, the thrust of the criticisms may be granted, but only alongside accepting the point expressed by the following interrogative: ‘Is it really worth the risk though?’. That is, even if the rational basis for the concern instantiates either a slippery-slope or fallacy of hyperbole, is dismissing the concern the reasoning attempts to rationally justify worth the risk? Considering the effect on

human flourishing, just on pain of experiencing a catastrophic outcome or series of catastrophic outcomes, risk avoidance or minimization is the best strategy. Moreover, having a value-constraint in the form of the parameter, *respect for personhood and self-representationality*, so as to avoid unnecessary risks to human flourishing would, arguably, be most prudent. Additionally, this underscores just why this parameter is a necessary condition for the ethical template.

The parameter, *respect for personhood and self-representationality*, is a necessary condition for the ethical template under discussion on two bases. First, it's based on a hypothetical necessity, that is: that which is necessary for achieving some goal or other. This hypothetical necessity consists in a value-constraint designed to avoid developing technology – particularly: “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems – that present considerable, intolerable risks to human flourishing in the fullest sense, which is inseparable from a healthy set of moral values, sentiments, and conduct. Second, it's based on preserving the distinction one finds in human phenomenological experience, namely: that between persons and objects. The quality of human conscious experience is such that it is shaped and contoured, at least for the most part¹¹⁶, by the distinction between sentient and non-sentient. The distinction between persons and objects being a special instance of this phenomenological distinction. Moreover, so as to preserve the rationality underpinning our practical reason as beings possessed of the first-person experience who live in a world, it is important that our relationship to our technology and our technological development, precisely due to our technology's potential to shape our comportment in the world as well as lived self-understanding in virtue of the co-mediated relationship between humans and

¹¹⁶ There can always be outliers to this generalization. Yet, the presence of a few outliers doesn't necessarily call into question the veracity of the generalization.

their technology, maintain this distinction between sentient and non-sentient, and thereby (or so it is hoped) between persons and objects.

Now, as was mentioned above, the central idea lying at the heart of the parameter, *substitutional accountability*, is one of oversight and ultimately moral accountability. The context germane to this central idea is social in nature, and expresses itself in terms of fulfilling the social requirements. These social requirements may not all be moral in content, purpose, or reference; nonetheless, they are entangled with human morality. So, in taking on a social role, one takes on the obligation to uphold the socio-moral fabric pertaining to that role. As such, were any entity, for example: an “autonomous” artificial intelligence system (e.g., an “autonomous” artificial institutional adviser), to fulfill a traditionally human role in the public space, then this entity must fulfill the social requirements pertaining to that role, one of which just is moral accountability (Bostrom and Yudkowsky 2014, pp. 316–334).

Furthermore, this parameter draws its merit in the current discussion not only by referring directly to the problem of enforceability for “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems, which will take centerstage latter in the overall discussion of this book; but also a condition needing-to-be-met so as to extend the privilege of allowing “autonomous” artificial intelligence system to fill a traditionally human role (e.g., loan officer). The purpose of the parameter, *substitutional accountability*, is to ensure persistence by means of requiring that all “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems are and maintain functional equivalence in fulfilling a traditionally human social role; that is, must be able to fulfill all requirements of that role including moral accountability.

How, though, is this parameter necessary for the ethical template? This parameter is hypothetically necessary in that it is necessary to effect persistence. The notion of persistence is

analogically extrapolated from two contexts to which the concept is germane. The first context is that of data structures for computer systems (Thatte 1986). Persistence in this context means, for instance, that the data survives after the process in which it was engendered has ended (e.g., persistent memory during a power outage).¹¹⁷ The second context is system design which is the application of system theory to product development so as to design such things as components, interfaces, and architecture for end-user requirements.¹¹⁸ One could see persistence expressed in concrete terms of a distributed digital network system that maintains data-traffic even when specific nodes in the network become inoperative.¹¹⁹ Analogically extrapolating from the principle behind the notion of persistence, axiological persistence, namely: preservation of a moral order beyond its generative context (e.g., normative framework), sufficient conditions (e.g., moral subjects), and activities, would consist in preservation of a moral order conducive to promoting or maintaining human flourishing. This sort of necessity, of course, is not so in a vacuum. Rather, it becomes necessary on the condition that we wish to consistently extend our moral order to include “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems thereby allowing them to fulfill a traditionally human role or to know where, at the very least, the boundary lies for this extension so as not to overstep this boundary and thereby risk marring or degrading the set of moral values desired to be extended.

It likely has not gone unnoticed that each parameter of the ethical template is a necessary condition for this template, but of differing sorts. Some may view this as a problem: holding that

¹¹⁷ Relatedly, please see: Dushyanth Narayanan and Orion Hodson. 2012. Whole-system persistence. SIGPLAN Not. 47(4): 401–410. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2248487.2151018>.

¹¹⁸ For more on this, please see the following: Hawryszkiewicz, Igor T. 1994. *Introduction to system analysis and design*. Hoboken, NJ (USA): Prentice Hall PTR.

¹¹⁹ One can take the basic principle behind persistence and apply it, *mutatis mutandis*, to a host of different contexts, requirements, and engineering applications. For example, an interstellar spacecraft that has built-in redundant power systems such that should one power system (e.g., nuclear propulsion) fail for whatever reason the redundant systems (e.g., ion propulsion) would become operative; the switch between the systems can be automated based on power-output thresholds: when the power output drops below a certain threshold a power-system switch would occur from, for example, nuclear to ion propulsion.

differing sorts of necessary conditions could make the ethical template conceptually incoherent or practicably infeasible. Yet, nothing could be further from the truth, or so it is hoped will become clear. To begin to see how a heterogeneous set of necessary conditions poses no special problem here, it is important to provide a critical overview of the rationale as to why and how each parameter is a necessary condition.

The necessity of the first parameter, *benevolence*, consists in what is required for rational practice or practical reason for rational agents; that is: it's the parameter that needs to be in place in order to provide a rational underpinning to ethically significant practical reason. Without it, it becomes difficult to make sense of why a rational agent possessed of self-interest would create technology that would present an existential threat to its own existence, unless of course such an agent would do so rationally motivated out of altruism or evidencing deficient rationality, some relevant oversight, an error(s), non-ideal restriction, or the like. Moreover and relatedly, the parameter is important for guiding rational practice so as to keep the development of technology on track so that it doesn't end up causing an existential threat to the rational agents responsible for the development of that technology. This, of course, applies to the technology highly relevant for this overall discussion; so too, *mutatis mutandis*, with other forms of extant technology as well as technology to be developed by such agents in the foreseeable future. Additionally, the parameter of *benevolence* would be necessary whether one endorsed co-mediation or not. In fact, the way in which it is necessary highlights its generality such that one needn't endorse co-mediation as such: the point would still stand even if one rejected co-mediation.

The second parameter, namely: *impartiality and intelligibility*, draws its necessity from discernment engendered from reflection upon humanity's interests, desires, and goals given its design, development, and deployment of technology, "autonomous" artificial intelligence

systems being no exception. As such, the parameter is of pragmatic necessity; that is, it is what needs to be in place so as to satisfy our interests, desires, and goals regarding human technology, namely: to have optimized and innovative technology that is maximally compatible (ideally or approaching this ideal asymptotically) with the social circumstance(s) in which humans wish to use it.

The third parameter, *respect for personhood and self-representationality*, is necessary for acknowledging and maintaining respect for a highly morally significant distinction, namely: between persons, on the one hand, and things or objects, on the other hand. This distinction is important for our moral considerations in that we adjudicate to whom our moral obligations, sentiments, actions, and the like are to be (and even should be) directed based on this distinction: one has moral obligations towards one's children or even pets that one simply does not have towards one's smartphone or a box of tissues. Furthermore, the intuitive appeal of this morally significant distinction likely is so due to it tracking the structure of conscious experience, namely: that between sentient and insentient, the former being one's neighbor, for example, the latter being one's bedpost, laptop or kitchen sink.

Yet, a query remains, one might object, as to why this distinction is crucial to the ethical template. Sure, so the objection continues, on the condition that such a distinction is important or even crucial to the ethical template, one may accept that the parameter in question is necessary for the ethical template: But why grant that? The crucial import this distinction has for the ethical template is as follows. Arguably, humans desire such potentially disruptive and groundbreaking technology as "autonomous" artificial intelligence systems, precisely due to their potential relative functional independence, still to respect this distinction that morally permits sending a doll to a trash dump, but not an actual child. Thereupon, this distinction is to be granted as

crucial or even necessary to the ethical template. Moreover, it is necessary, in turn, to have a way to operationalize this distinction in some fashion for such technical artifacts. The parameter in question is that proposed way. As such, the necessity of this parameter is determined by the necessity to preserve and operationalize this distinction, the latter of which in turn is necessary to build in constraints on the relevant technology so that it does not transmogrify the moral fabric of human life.

The fourth parameter, *substitutional accountability*, is necessary so as to ensure functional equivalence and persistence on the part of “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems so that meeting the social requirements, disentangleable from morality, for a role for which such technical systems are substituting for a human person(s) is safeguarded.

Now, the heterogeneous nature of the set of necessary conditions is not peculiarly conceptually problematic, unavoidable, and even beneficial. For the ethical template, being conceptual in nature, should at least not be conceptually incoherent, and the parameters taken as a whole do not constitute an inconsistent set. What is more: since the ethical template is meant to guide development of the relevant technology, it must have, and indeed does have, certain necessary features that are morally fecund and reflective of moral values founded on a strong rational basis – not just any values will do – and yet those selfsame features must be practice-oriented or at least not obstructions to the rather practical engineering endeavors behind developing “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems as well as be effective in operationalizing the relevant moral sentiments, values, and priorities so as to have morally optimized “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems. Additionally, the joint sufficiency of the parameters rests, too, on this latter basis, namely: to assist in providing a conceptual and practice-oriented framework for the design, development, and deployment of morally optimized

“autonomous” artificial intelligence systems, and *mutatis mutandis*, technical artifacts more generally.

One final query remains, however, for the ethical template: How is it a necessary condition for the ethical module? The reason can be discerned from the foregoing. Namely, it is so because it is what needs to be in place so as to provide an ethically sound and rationally robust framework for the prospective embedding of well-reasoned and rationally substantiated moral values into the very design¹²⁰ of “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems whilst simultaneously providing a way to operationalize such values in a concrete system of the relevant sort. It does not do this alone, however, but is aided by the afore-discussed social imaginary and the following considerations, to which this discussion will soon turn, regarding metaphor and models.¹²¹ This, naturally, is so due to the aforestated structure of S.E.M., the current practice-oriented conceptual framework (axio-conceptual framework)¹²² for which this discussion is an attempt to characterize, explain, and justify.

The preceding considerations feature a clear set of moral values for which it is hoped that their strong rational basis and significance are clear. Moreover, the sensibleness of their adoption, as they are certainly what the author recommends be adopted, does not stand alone. Rather, this recommendation is buttressed by additional considerations concerning relevant pertinent aspects of human ontology to which the discussion next turns.

¹²⁰ The reader may have noticed an equivocation on the word ‘design’ within this discussion. So as to clarify, it is used in two ways. In the first, it is used so as to refer to a specific phase of the technology lifecycle of “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems as well as, *mutatis mutandis*, other technical systems. In the second, it is used as a means so as to refer to the general way in which the relevant technical system is produced.

¹²¹ To be clear, the portion of the discussion regarding models will, in fact, be a discussion from a metaperspective on models; hence, a metamodel discussion. This will be important for the section to follow wherein the model itself will be constructed which will in turn form part of the theoretical base whose viability will be subsequently assessed.

¹²² By labeling *S.E.M.* to be an “axiological-conceptual framework” or “axio-conceptual framework” it is in line with its orientation towards practice in the form of value-based engineering implementation. For it is, indeed, ethical and conceptual in nature, but not passively so as in the sense of the Greek *θεωρεῖν* (*theōrein*), whence stems the English word theory, the Greek meaning “to consider”, “to look at”, “to speculate”, which ultimately stems from *θεωρός* (*theōrós*) “spectator” meant in the sense of a spectator at a theater (Kroes 2012, *Introduction*, footnote 1; Strong, James (2010). *The New Strong's Exhaustive Concordance of the Bible.*; <https://www.etymonline.com/word/theory>).

1.5.2 Metaphysics of Human Persons

Human ontology is a rather wide field of study. It ranges, for example, from discussions concerning the nature of the human mind and body to humanity's status in the cosmos, and includes many broad-based inquiries of a metaphysical nature. It is tempting to think that inquiries concerning the nature of the human mind and body as well as humanity's place in the cosmos are solely empirical inquiries best left under the auspices of physics, chemistry, biology, and related sciences. Though, there is some merit to such a view, empirical means of addressing such inquiries as applied to humanity fall short. This is due to the nature of scientific methodology which is rooted in reliable observations, development of causal models, and predictive success as a result of the former. This is not to deny the fecundity of and exemplary rationality evidenced by scientific methodology nor is it to hold that science is only concerned with observation, causal models, and prediction; these three constituting some of its pillars notwithstanding. No one can deny the marvels of the current scientific (and by extension: technological) age or its benefits to humanity. Nevertheless, when it comes to ontology there are queries regarding humanity, and the universe more generally, that are simply outside the grasp of scientific methodology or whose answers are presupposed by that very methodology.

An example is in order. Building a causal model of, say, a rocket leaving the Earth involves, among other things, modeling the rocket leaving Earth's orbit. This, of course, would utilize concepts such as "thrust per cubic square meter", "escape velocity", and the like as part of providing not only adequate explanations illustrating what is causally sufficient for what, but also adequate means of making viable predictions based on the model for some rocket excursion or other. All of this involves events, and in fact a certain understanding of how events stack in

linear time, one leading to another, and even as to which ones do and don't precipitate other events, etc. As such, providing the relevant causal model would presuppose a prior understanding of what an event is, however implicit that understanding is, and would not provide by means of the causal model an understanding of what an event is. Sure. A causal model may deepen our understanding of events, but it would only presuppose, not provide a basic understanding of what an event is: one would require such an understanding beforehand. Much of this understanding of events is likely implicit, and there is some evidence in favor of this (Dreyfus 2016); nevertheless, the explicit and even formal study of events is not something graspable by scientific methodology. Rather, it is wrought through inquiries into metaphysics. It is through metaphysics we can come to understanding the answer to the 'what is it?' question for events, divining its sortal membership, so as to understand the sort of thing an event is. This type of metaphysical inquiry bodes to illumine its individuation conditions so that we may have a formal basis to distinguish it from something like, for instance, a state of affairs. It is through metaphysical investigation that we come to understanding what persistence conditions are in relation to the class of items labeled *events*; and although it may be in part an empirical matter as to knowing when this or that particular event is expired (which itself is an event) recognizing that its persistence conditions are violated or even that it was in virtue of persistence conditions having been violated is a metaphysical, not an empirical matter. What is true of causal models and events is no less true of states of affairs, substances, properties, and relations: each being briefly touched upon in turn.

The crux of the idea of a state of affairs is an arrangement of circumstances in the world. This is consistent with the way the concept is presented in Wittgenstein's work, *Tractatus* (Textor 2021) The metaphysics, semantics, and proper theoretical role of this concept is a matter of

debate among philosophers, and there is no need to take a stand on any of that for this discussion. Nonetheless, a few points can be helpful for contextualizing this concept so as to illustrate the nature and value of metaphysical inquiry, on the one hand, and the value and limits of scientific inquiry, on the other hand.

We begin with some examples of states of affairs, namely: ‘driving through a snowstorm’, ‘being late for dinner’, ‘telling the truth’; and in so doing, it is hoped that the intuitive thrust behind and everydayness of states of affairs are appreciated. In fact, even from this small set of examples along with the central and basic idea behind the concept of a “state of affairs”, a few things are noteworthy. The first being, states of affairs are the sorts of things that propositional attitudes, thoughts, and propositions are about. These all have satisfaction conditions however these conditions are explicated. Moreover and for each one there is something that makes the satisfaction conditions fulfilled. For assertoric thoughts or assertoric propositions, and the sentences that they embody, that which satisfies in the relevant sense is called a truth-maker.

Recall that a truth-maker, in the relevant literature, is that which makes something true. The basic idea here, then, is that assertoric thoughts or thoughts whose structure can be expressed as an assertion are either true or false, and that there must be something that makes them so; hence, the concept or notion of a “truth-maker”. As a famous example illustrates, ‘snow is white’ if and only if snow *is* white; that is, something in the actual world makes the assertoric thought or expressed assertion true or false. This, of course, would still apply for thoughts, propositions, and propositional attitudes for which truth is not the appropriate property: hence, the relevance of the notion of satisfaction herein meant: it being the wider notion which subsumes such things as truth, falsity, fulfilled, violated, and the like. Furthermore, one finds a

similar idea in metaphysics, namely: that which makes two or more things distinct from one another – that which accounts for the difference – is the “difference-maker”.

How this applies to states of affairs is as follows. The concept or notion of a state of affairs does its work as part of inquiries into the metaphysics of modality. States of affairs, then, are “modal truthmakers”; that is, they are satisfiers, in a modal context, of some proposition, thought, or the like. As such and as was the case with truthmakers for assertoric propositions and thoughts expressing this structure of an assertion, so too, *mutatis mutandis*, with modal propositions or thoughts concerning possibility and necessity, there is something which “makes it true”, in the relevant sense, or rather: which satisfies the modal proposition, *et cetera*, or not. Now, there are competing theories and so forth regarding how best to understand the semantics or metaphysics of states of affairs, and taking a particular stand on them is not the business of this discussion. Nonetheless, it is important to note that none of this can be decided on an empirical basis: that is simply not the right currency here. Thereupon, explicating the nature of states of affairs falls outside the kin of scientific methodology; yet the ontology of states of affairs, for example, and other aspects concerning them can be addressed using largely conceptual analysis peculiar to metaphysics.

Again, something is no less true with events; these are not amenable to a purely scientific investigation. Take, for example, a scientific endeavor to explain, by means of neurobiology, the raising of one’s arm. It would be quite natural for a neurobiological model of explanation to provide a causal explanation by means of providing a causal model. A causal model regarding the neurons in the brain causing one’s arm to raise, as one would expect, relies on a prior understanding of what an event is. What an event is, however, is not explained by the causal model, but is presupposed by the very activity of generating a causal model in the first place. But

as to what an event is, that's a metaphysical matter, despite how well one may understand it in scientific practice. The story is much the same with relations, substance, and properties.

Starting with relations, it may be a scientific matter as to what psychological identity is over time, but it is certainly a metaphysical matter as to what persistence of a subject consists in, whether that be diachronic or synchronic; that is, in the case of the former what the principled reasons in virtue of which 'subject-a at time t_1 is subject-b at time t_2 '.¹²³ These principled reasons would consist of specification of necessary and sufficient conditions for subjects to persist diachronically thereby determining subjects' diachronic identity. Some rudimentary understanding of this entire structure of the diachronic identity relation R_d for the persistence of subjects would need be, on some level, understood so as to make sense of the scientific investigation of psychological identity over time. That understanding is not wrought through science; it's presupposed by it.

With substance, it's the same. It may be a matter of scientific investigation to plumb the depths of substance so as to discover (or so it is hoped) its nature: be that matter, atoms, quarks, strings, or whatever; yet the very concept of substance and its various subsidiary inquiries – concerning its individuation conditions, sortal membership, persistence conditions, *et cetera* – gain no purchase by means of scientific methodology. Moreover, what is true of substance is, *mutatis mutandis*, true of properties. The following specific inquiries bear this out regarding both substance and properties that highlight both the usefulness of scientific investigation and the scientific methodology; yet nonetheless, indicate whereat the baton must be passed to metaphysics. Consider the 20th-century attempts ontologically to reduce minds to brains, mental states to brain states. When the reduction is successful it demonstrates that all As are Bs or that there is nothing over and above a B to being an A. For example, the property of liquidity, or so

¹²³ The 'is' here is that of identity, not predication.

the example goes from Searle, is such that there is nothing about it over and above molecules in motion arranged in a certain geometry (Searle 1992). Now, when it comes to the mind and brain, ontological reductionism has largely been fraught with difficulties: the mind is not ontologically reducible to the brain nor are mental states ontologically reducible to brain states, whether they be types or tokens (Von Lucadou and Kornwachs 1983; Shanjendu 2012; Jaworski 2016). Some might balk at such a claim, but it is hard to deny that antireductionism regarding the mind has grown in appeal through the course of the 20th century and continues to appeal to more and more throughout the 21st century so far (Koons and Bealer 2001). Simultaneous to the faltering and reorienting of the reductionist research approach in the philosophy of mind, the scientific knowledge of the causal mechanisms behind many aspects of the mind has grown. Yet again, certain key questions about the very ontological nature of the mind remain elusive with respect to scientific investigation but not necessarily metaphysical investigations, e.g.: ‘What is thought?’, ‘What does it mean for mental states to have content?’, ‘What does it mean for a mental state to be about anything?’, ‘What is consciousness?’ ‘If mental properties are not reducible to brain properties and subjectivity has its own regularities and structures discernible through psychological investigation, does the subjective constitute its own realm (i.e., in the sense of the rather loose but apt phrase, ‘quantum realm’)?’

The foregoing highlights the value and necessity of metaphysical inquiry for human inquiries, scientific or otherwise. Along the way, an indirect partial characterization of metaphysics was provided. Be that as it may, the indirect partial characterization would benefit from an additional direct one. Appropriately, then, metaphysics may be understood as the broad-based inquiry into being.¹²⁴ Moreover, there is a great deal of debate concerning the nature

¹²⁴ For a rather enlightening discussion concerning the topic of metaphysics, please see the following: van Inwagen, Peter, Sullivan, Meghan and Bernstein, Sara. 2023. "Metaphysics", *The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy* (Summer Edition), Edward N. Zalta & Uri Nodelman (eds.), URL =

and scope of metaphysics, and thereby just how to explicate this terse direct characterization. A hard stand amidst this debate is not taken here, as that would misdirect the course of the current investigation. Rather two points will serve as guideposts instead.

The first point is rooted in the realization that, at least from an intuitive standpoint, metaphysics concerns itself with the enduring principles and features that account for why and how human experience of the world turns out the way it does. In objecting, it may be pointed out that scientific disciplines are sufficient for understanding this, e.g.: neurobiology, cognitive science, and psychology, since much of this experience can be accounted for by study of the human mind/brain.¹²⁵ In reply, it is observed that this doesn't account for the fittingness and correspondence one finds between different aspects of how the human mind/brain operate and the world. In rejoinder, one could remark that evolutionary biology, a science, can account for this. In response, it may be remarked in the form of an interrogative: Sure, but why should nature turn out to be this, namely: 'Why should there be this interplay between biological traits, selection pressures, mechanism of mutation?' Yet, one might inveigh that this can be accounted for by means of chemistry and physics, and further substantiated by mathematics. In response, however, one might ask, Yes, but what principles and features account for those discipline's explanatory and predictive effectiveness – some might even say, in the case of mathematics, “uncanny” effectiveness.¹²⁶ This last response, however, in the dialectic brings the rational scrutiny full circle back to the intuitive thrust of the inquiry behind metaphysics in the first place,

<<https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/sum2023/entries/metaphysics/>>. Moreover, as the article indicates, there are non-trivial difficulties in even understanding the concept of metaphysics, let alone defining the term 'metaphysics'. Although the author may depart from the considerations in the aforementioned article, he in no way attempts to deny these difficulties exist nor the importance of being aware of them.

¹²⁵ The following formulation, namely: 'mind/brain' is used so as not to take a stand on the relationship, reductive or otherwise, between the human mind and brain.

¹²⁶ Witten, Edward. “Why the ‘Unreasonable Effectiveness’ of Mathematics”, *Closer to Truth*, April 2020, https://youtu.be/1-ZI9o7I4Fo?si=w_ulJo2rlQtfaHjV.

namely: metaphysics concerns itself with the enduring principles and features that account for why and how human experience of the world turns out the way it does.

The second point is that there is not a clear dividing line in terms of definition between metaphysics and science, but there are recognizable indicators as to when one is engaged in a scientific versus metaphysical investigation. To see this, take inquiries into persistence of objects. This is often an inquiry into what the conditions are for an ordinary middle-sized object to persistence, namely: what object identity of over time consists in or what would ground the meaning of the claim that ‘object-a at time t_1 is object-b at time t_2 ’.¹²⁷ It is not unreasonable to hold that spatiotemporal continuity is what persistence of objects consists in; nonetheless, this would make the matter of persistence of objects not entirely outside the scope of scientific investigation. Yet, again the very inquiry into the necessary and sufficient conditions under which or that allow for objects to persist over time is not entirely a matter of physics for the reasons already discussed (see first guidepost point). How is this seeming impasse resolved?

One could say that there are certain inquiries which are hybrid in nature, being both physical and metaphysical. But this would be problematic for two reasons. In the first, it would create taxonomic vagueness as to how to classify certain inquiries: whether they would be metaphysical inquiries or physical. This would be methodologically problematic, as it would interrupt the grounding process; that is: the process of finding more fundamental principles and features which are sufficient to give rise to certain aspects of human experience regarding, for example, the physical world. In the second, it would violate parsimony. For it would run counter to an understanding based on as small of a set of principles, assumptions, and the like which are highly generative. Moreover, parsimony is a methodological virtue due to the fact that insofar as it consists in the least amount of principles, assumptions, and the like which are jointly highly

¹²⁷ Again, this is the ‘is’ of identity, not prediction.

(ideally the most) generative, it is insular from *ad hoc* additions, irrelevancy, and lack of sufficient grounding objections, the latter being important because this least set of principles, assumptions, and the like are (ideally) to be foundational. As such, proliferation of categories and distinctions is discouraged, for it violates the rather important methodological virtue of parsimony. But this is precisely what holding an additional hybrid type of inquiries would do. Hence, it is to be avoided. Therefore, based on these two reasons, holding that there are certain inquiries which are hybrid in nature, being both physical and metaphysical is not the way to proceed.

It, rather, makes more sense to avoid the impasse whilst not creating further methodological problems (e.g., like the aforementioned) by viewing the relationship between science and metaphysics in the following way. Accepting metaphysics as the broad-based inquiry into being which concerns itself with discerning enduring principles and features that account for why and how human experience of the world turns out the way it does, science is understood as the more specific inquiry into being concerned with empirical investigations into human experience focused largely on the objects of experience in this regard or the relationship between the subject and the relevant objects of experience. The scientific investigation, of course, is organized and executed by the employment of scientific methodology and the principles of scientific epistemology, and the activities are largely (but not solely) centered around developing best fit explanatory models and optimized predictive models; whereas, metaphysical investigation is organized and executed by the employment of optimized rationality aided by utilization of various systems of logic along with mathematical analysis techniques of various sorts broadly construed, and the activities are largely (but not solely) centered on developing theoretical bases rooted in argued-for or self-evident fundamental principles and features that

give rise to or somehow make possible various aspects of human life, scientific or otherwise. As such, metaphysical investigation is the wider investigation into being, whereas scientific investigation is the narrower investigation into being. Thereupon, the relationship between the two can be viewed such that the latter is nested in the former and of a far narrower scope.

If the above understanding of the relationship between metaphysics and science is correct, or at least merits sufficient cogency, then this understanding lines up well with how the relationship between metaethics and ethics is understood, namely: metaethics is the wider inquiry concerned with the metaphysical, epistemological, logical, and psychological assumptions, presuppositions, and commitments to various moral concepts, expressions, attitudes, and practices, some issues of which being about the relationship between values, reasons, action, and human motivation posing such questions as:

Is morality more a matter of taste than truth? Are moral standards culturally relative? Are there moral facts? If there are moral facts, what are their origin and nature? How is it that they set an appropriate standard for our behavior? How might moral facts be related to other facts (about psychology, happiness, human conventions...)? And how do we learn about moral facts, if there are any? These questions lead naturally to puzzles about the meaning of moral claims as well as about moral truth and the justification of our moral commitments. Metaethics explores as well the connection between values, reasons for action, and human motivation, asking how it is that moral standards might provide us with reasons to do or refrain from doing as they demand, and it addresses many of the issues commonly bound up with the nature of freedom and its significance (or not) for moral responsibility (Sayre-McCord 2014).

As such, both metaethics and metaphysics can reasonably be viewed as a set of wider investigations containing a subset of narrow investigations, ethics and physics respectively:

Figure 3.

This alignment suggests deeper inquiries that fall outside the parameters of the current discussion; and as a result, their pursuit will be forsaken at this time.¹²⁸ Nonetheless, it also provides a clearly circumscribed point of entry so as to introduce the specific metaphysics of persons operative as a parameter of S.E.M. The autonomous individual is this metaphysics of persons. The concept “autonomous individual” and characterization thereof utilized here is found in the work of Charles Taylor. This concept along with his characterization of it will prove useful, because it reflects an updated contemporary understanding of the human person that is appropriately morally textured. As such, it provides a metaphysics of persons that is

¹²⁸ Nonetheless, for a bit more on this, please see the *Introduction* section of this discussion.

contemporary and germane to moral reasoning and discourse, and thereby is most useful as a parameter of the ethical module of S.E.M. Moreover, this conception buttresses the moral order of the social imaginary component of S.E.M., thereby functioning much like a thread binding together with more thread creating a stronger support structure. But what is the autonomous individual?

According to Taylor, the “autonomous individual” is a conception of the individual, this being a metaphysics of persons in society as autonomous whilst under law (Taylor 1989). There are two ways to deepen understanding of this conception: (1) genealogical¹²⁹ (2) semantically; both will be utilized. In the first, genealogically, the initial steps begin with understanding the “new vision of moral order” (Taylor 2007). This new vision, as Taylor refers to it, tracks our 21st-century understanding of moral order, which was discussed in greater detail when discussing the social imaginary component ‘S’ of S.E.M (please see “Social Imaginary” section of *Conceptual Tools I* of this book). That having been said, some of those considerations bear repeating here so as to bring it within a wider understanding that clearly connects these considerations to the relevant metaphysics of persons parameter of the ethical module and the greater role this metaphysics of persons plays in handling the upcoming discussion concerning the autonomy problem.

The modern moral order (or MMO) of the 21st century is rooted in rights and obligations. There is a rather complex story here about how this came to be which falls outside the purview of the present discussion.¹³⁰ The exact nature of the relationship between rights and obligations

¹²⁹ Nietzsche Friedrich Wilhelm. 1989. *On the Genealogy of Morals*. Walter Kaufmann and R. J Hollingdale (eds.). New York: Vintage Books.

¹³⁰ For more on this, please see: Taylor, Charles .1989. *Sources of the Self: The Making of the Modern Identity*. 11–13. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press, .2002. *Varieties of Religion Today: William James Revisited*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press, 79–92, .2004. *Modern Social Imaginaries*. 3–12; 23–30. Durham, NC: Duke University Press, .2007. *A Secular Age*. 11–12;79–92;146–170, 294. Cambridge, MA: the Belknap Press of Harvard University Press.

being non-obvious notwithstanding, some measure of explication of this relationship is in order. Nonetheless, in so doing, a full and carefully defended account of this exact nature must be the task of another discussion, as it would take the current investigation and critical examination too far afield. Furthermore, the extent to which this relationship will be discussed would only be in the service of fleshing out the relevant metaphysics of persons germane to the current investigation. With the scope of the relevant considerations concerning metaphysics of persons having been well-defined, or so it is hoped, the discussion resumes the genealogical characterization of the concept of the “autonomous individual forthwith.

The MMO holds that along with a right on the part of an individual to life, for example, there are certain obligations of mutual service (Taylor 2007). For instance, with respect to the right to life is the corresponding obligation of not inflicting harm on another individual through action or inaction. In fact, in this case, the obligation to mutual service correlative to the right to life draws its content, at least in part, from J.S. Mill’s harm principle (Taylor 2002, 79–92). Accordingly, this obligation contributes towards ensuring conditions which are conducive to human flourishing, along with providing avenues for active participation of the relevant right-bearer in protecting one’s own rights (Taylor 1989). Furthermore, the complementary way in which obligations and rights function together according to and within the framework of the MMO highlights the latter’s shape and contours as an evaluative framework as well as a peculiar conception of persons germane to the present inquiry. This conception regards the natural rights of persons as universal and inalienable aiding in a shift in understanding of the individual human person as autonomous, yet under law (Taylor 1989).¹³¹

¹³¹ It is, of course, possible to go into finer-grained detail regarding the historical idea of the concept of the “autonomous individual”. Such fine-tuning of the history of this idea, though of great interest, is not germane for the current investigation. The reader is rather referred to the following, should this line of inquiry prove of interest: Swaine, Lucas. 2016. “THE ORIGINS OF AUTONOMY.” *History of Political Thought* 37(2): 216–237. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/26228692>.

This shift to a conception of the individual person restructured the ordered relationship individuals had with the universe. This new “autonomous individual” whilst under law constituted a dislodgement of the individual person from a larger and all-encompassing cosmic order. Though due to the natural rights such a person possessed, they were nonetheless under some ordering or other (Taylor 2007). This ordering, however, was not of the grand cosmic sort evidenced by pre-modern societies (Taylor 2004). Moreover, the nature of this new ordering was twofold: (1) its *locus* was internal to the individual instead of “out there” in the cosmos (2) it was explicated in terms of moral values promoting human life and welfare (Taylor 1989). Furthermore, the contrasting position to the order being “out there” was not always such that the order was conceived as being only within the autonomous individual person, although some accounts depicted this new moral ordering as such.¹³² Nevertheless, the crux of the change of the *locus* of ordering consisted in this ordering being immanent to human life and affairs as opposed to some grand design transcendent of it to which human life and affairs must in some way conform.

The foregoing genealogical sketch of the concept of the “autonomous individual” being used herein to explicate the metaphysics of persons operative as a parameter of the ethical module contextualizes the contemporary semantics of “autonomous” as it applies to human persons. How so? To see this, the semantics of the relevant notion must be discussed. The semantics of “autonomous” as it applies to the individual human persons is as follows. The word ‘autonomous’ is a compound word derived from Greek consisting of two significant parts:

1. *autos*: reflexive pronoun meaning, “selfsame”; the word element, ‘auto’ meaning “self”, “one's own”, “by oneself”, “of oneself”

¹³² One salient example of this sort is Ralph Waldo Emerson’s 1908 essay entitled *Self-Reliance*. East Aurora, New York: The Roycrofters.

2. *nomos*: meaning “law” or “custom”. As such, ‘autonomous’ means “one’s own law” “self-law”, “by oneself law”, and so forth (Harper 2018).

From the composition of these two meaningful parts, the word ‘autonomous’ and its relevant cognates (e.g., ‘autonomy’, etc.) mean something like “to provide one’s own laws, customs, norms, rules, etc.”.¹³³ Accordingly, ‘autonomous’, as it applies to human persons, to the individual, refers to the capacity to provide one’s own laws, norms, rules and customs for oneself: this involves the ability to freely think of and select which laws, norms, and so forth one wishes to follow (EGESNT 2018). Furthermore, there are certain cognitive processes that are associated with such a metaphysics of human persons that are traditionally understood as facilitating and enabling autonomy: consciousness, self-awareness, freewill, and rationality (Ibid). It is, indeed, this modern conception of human persons, this metaphysics of human persons that conceives of the human individuals as “buffered disciplined selves” (Taylor 2007) free from dependence on any sort of complementary hierarchical ordering capable of providing their own ordering (Ibid.).

Now, one might object that the metaphysics of human persons explicated within this section provides a rather enervated depiction of the human individual. For metaphysics of persons is a wide and rich, even baroque, domain of inquiry; hence, the depiction of human persons whence this domain should reflect that complexity. Whilst admitting the force of the objection, the author responds that precisely due to the richness of this domain of inquiry, it is

¹³³ The author uses such phrases as ‘something like’, not because an approximate semantic definition of ‘autonomous’ is given, but rather the semantic definition is given the form of an infinitive verb for a word that is in adjectival form. This lack of precision aside, the author is attempting to provide the semantic content that informs all forms of the word, thereby applying to all of its cognates.

incumbent on anyone working within this domain to provide a depiction of human persons that is relevant for this or that particular universe of discourse. Recall that the underlying idea of a universe of discourse (henceforth: UD) is the collection of things discussed, which circumscribes a discussion such that it is not about every possible thing (unless of course that just is the UD). This discussion fitly focuses, then, on the metaphysics of human persons most relevant for moral reasoning, making it most apt for use in the present discussion.

Lastly, this parameter of metaphysics of persons is necessary for the ethical module. This is because any such thing as an ethical module needs a way to ground what it is that matters in moral reasoning. Hence, it needs explanatory adequacy grounded in some fundamental feature; that is, a metaethical foundation that accounts for why moral reasoning in human experience is structured the way that is insofar as it holds persons in such high regard.

Given the appropriateness of the metaphysics of persons focused upon herein, how does this connect to such moral concepts like responsibility?

1.5.3 Conception of Responsibility¹³⁴

Moral responsibility is a key moral notion which plays a central role in moral theories and deliberations. It also plays a central role in our everyday moral understanding both of oneself and others. Given the premium put on and ubiquity of the import of the concept of responsibility, there have been many attempts to explain what it consists in, how it informs human lives, the different species of it, etc. The current discussion concerning responsibility will proceed a bit differently, however. In this section, a particular theory of responsibility will neither be utilized

¹³⁴ As was discussed in the introduction, the focus of the current investigation is on the moral. Accordingly, what is meant by ‘responsibility’ herein is moral responsibility. Hence, ‘responsibility’ and ‘moral responsibility’ will be used interchangeably.

nor defended. Rather, the discussion concerning the concept of responsibility will proceed based on an analysis of phenomenological experience which gives rise to an intuitive understanding of responsibility which will be brought into dialogue with the previous metaethical considerations of the previous section: a workable conception of responsibility operative within the ethical module will be therefrom developed. It must be noted that, of course, this way of proceeding is not completely divorced of theory, since it relies on phenomenological analysis. The point, however, is that the discussion concerning responsibility will not be based on an extant “high-level” theory of responsibility, such as that based on Immanuel Kant¹³⁵, G.W.F Hegel¹³⁶, or that of Christine Korsgaard’s¹³⁷, Sarah Cobb’s¹³⁸, or the like. Rather, the discussion will be constructive of a workable conception of responsibility based on an analysis of human experience. This, nonetheless, does not rule out discussion of certain theories of responsibility through the course of developing a workable conception for the current undertaking of this book.

The analysis, then, begins where the previous discussion concerning metaphysics of persons leaves off, namely: with the autonomous individual human person. Upon reflection, it quickly becomes clear that it is difficult to tease apart this modern conception of what it means to be a human person from moral concerns, concepts, and notions of morality in general. This highlights a couple of things. In the first, it highlights the evaluative framework of the aforementioned MMO, but this point need not be belabored further. In the second, it highlights respect for what is considered to be morally distinctive about personhood itself. This respect is not the sort at play when someone commands our respect, like say: a political figure (e.g.,

¹³⁵ Uniacke, Suzanne M. 2005. Responsibility and Obligation: Some Kantian Directions, *International Journal of Philosophical Studies*, 13(4): 461–475, DOI: 10.1080/09672550500321528.

¹³⁶ Alznauer, Mark. 2015. *Hegel's Theory of Responsibility*, Cambridge University Press.

¹³⁷ Korsgaard, Christine M. 2018. *Fellow Creatures: Our Obligations to the Other Animals*, Uehiro Series in Practical Ethics. New York: Oxford. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oso/9780198753858.001.0001>.

¹³⁸ Cobb, Sarah. 1994. “Theories of responsibility”: The social construction of intentions in mediation, *Discourse Processes*, 18(2): 165–186, DOI: 10.1080/01638539409544890.

President Obama), a scientist (e.g., Albert Einstein), or social leader (e.g., Mahatma Gandhi). Rather, it is respect in the sense that it results in: (1) a general regard for that which is considered to be of high value (2) nurturing and protecting behavior which is consistent with this high regard. Hence, respect in this sense evokes support and protection of the integrity of the one in possession of the grounds or basis that secures such respect. Moreover, this is not to say that the two forms of respect are unrelated; for their common ground is value. The nature and role of value within the current investigation was touched on at length above, so will not be repeated here (see section entitled *Value, Axiology, and the Needful Tool, Rightly Understood*). Insofar as they share this common ground of value, the latter is a diving board whence springs a dive into a deeper understanding of that morally distinctive aspect of personhood.

The folk or intuitive understanding of personhood is that of a being with a certain moral status (Taylor 1985a). At its heart, this status is rooted in an understanding of being of a privileged position. This understanding is an extrapolation from phenomenological experience. As particular subjects, persons are perspectival beings for whom things matter. This makes subjects, and thereby persons, loci of subjectivity that can assign value to objects and other subjects. This ability to assign value is a self-evident and an originary capacity of signification possessed by subjectivity: is of the fundamental nature and structure of subjectivity. Now, there is an element of choice, but perhaps not always a conscious choice; that is to say: one has a bit of a modal relationship there, which means subjects can “dial in” their originary power of signification to different “channels” of objects (or subjects) so as to focus upon a significant; and insofar as subjectivity (i.e., the intrinsic powers of subjectivity) allow this to be possible, human persons are from that basic standpoint a respondent. This alone, however, does not make a person responsible. Rather, it only provides a minimum necessary basis for responsibility: it

explains why, for example, a tree stump is not a respondent, but a person is. Thereupon, being a respondent is necessary, but not sufficient condition for being responsible. Recall that: a property Q is a necessary condition for a property R if and only if whenever R is present, Q is present (Skyrms 1999, p.84). Accordingly, being a respondent is a necessary condition for responsibility in that whenever responsibility is present, being a respondent is present. This is a rather intuitive point, but showing how it conforms to rational and reliable procedures of reasoning is useful for providing an accounting of moral responsibility.

The aforementioned “modal aspect” of being a respondent is key to understanding what might be sufficient for being responsible. Responsibility also requires that one be sensitive to capacities as well as attributes intrinsic to being a subjectivity – freedom. Starting with the latter, the kernel of this idea, drawing from a critical reflection on the phenomenological experience of subjecthood, is that one could significate otherwise: one could assign meaning and value to another object or subject or simply in a different way regarding the same objects or subjects. This sets one up for being in a position to be responsible insofar as actions are an expression of that originary capacity of signification. This, in turn, is due to the fact that actions in their ontology are not just individuated by bodily movements, but also by their intention (Searle 1983). One can, of course, try to explicate what this freedom consists in through various models of explanation (and their concomitant justification “stories”), and this can be done in, broadly speaking, two ways: thick or thin. These two designations refer to two broad-based classes of approaches to the inquiry into human free will.

The current discussion does not allow for an extensive discussion regarding these two broad-based classes; moreover, doing so would take the discussion in directions not germane to the mainstay of this book’s discussion. Furthermore, what the two broad-based classes have in

common is an inquiry into the sort of control one has over one's actions (O'Connor & Franklin 2022). Suffice to say, in the thick way of explication, one develops a metaethical theory and a set of strong ontological and epistemological considerations in favor of more or complete control over one's actions or less to no control of one's actions. One can see examples of this throughout the history of Western philosophy from antiquity to the 20th century in discussions concerning the freedom of the will (Lucas 1971) or free will (Kane 2011; O'Connor & Franklin 2022). Moreover, these debates are usually cashed out in terms of 'whether the will is free or not' or some form of compatibilism. The latter attempts to take the most rationally convincing considerations from both antipodes – that the will is wholly determined and that the will is wholly free – and harmonize them in some way, or at least bring them into dynamic tension or subsume both under a "higher" theory.

By contrast, in the thin way of explication, one provides a minimal or in some cases no greater metaethical theory in terms of strong ontological and epistemological considerations in order to address the inquiry into free will; nonetheless, one in this case does have a positive account of how much control one has. An example of this is what may be called the "pragmatist" view of William James, namely: humans are determined, but also determine: that is, we are this dual nexus of that which is determined and that which determines (James 2014 [1884]). James's view, in addition to being considered thin, in the relevant sense, can also be considered a form of compatibilism.

Either way – thick or thin – both reflect an understanding extrapolated from the bareness of the lived-experience of subjects, namely: that human persons are subjects with the capacity of originary signification, and are thereby respondents in the sense above, but have a freeness of control as to how this is expressed in action, verbal or otherwise. But this is still not enough to

get the threshold of sufficiency of responsibility, even from a bare-bones analysis of lived-experience. No. An additional aspect must be added which can also be extracted from phenomenological experience. Subjects are not just free to do anything: there are certain things that are just beyond our control, and so there must be a demarcation of this sphere of responsibility; that is to say: things within our control as related to this originary act of signification or things that are outside of our control as related to this originary free act of signification. Hence, capacities become important in one's analysis of what it means to be responsible. Thereupon, from an analysis of phenomenological experience: (1) the perspectival originary acts signification (2) the freeness of manner or degree of control of subjects to significate and express this in actions or inaction, verbal or otherwise (3) a sense of finitude of capacities and powers on the part of subjects are jointly sufficient or enough for moral responsibility. Accordingly, whatever model of explanation one prefers or preferred justifications given for an account of moral responsibility, "thick" or high-level, on the one hand, "thin" or low-level, on the other hand, the fact remains that it can be traced back to lived-experience and the phenomenological structure sketched out in this section. Of course, much more fine-grained detail can be given regarding how a, for example, high-level theory of moral responsibility can be built on an analysis of phenomenological experience as well as what this may imply. This, however, will have to await another discussion. The goal here was to develop, through critical reflection, a workable depiction and understanding of responsibility based on its seedform, which can be used to explicate the parameter of the ethical module in question. It is hoped that the above suffices in this regard.

This parameter is necessary because any module putatively designed to ethically analyze or even implement ethics in an "autonomous" artificial intelligence system must be able to

account for how our moral notions might apply to them. Of course, in this case, the focal point of that is now the notion of responsibility might apply to them. This, of course, must be predicated on an articulated conception of moral responsibility to use as a touchstone so as to determine whether it can really apply to them or not, and *mutatis mutandis*, how that might work if at all. As such, the current parameter of the ethical module is necessary in this light. Moreover, the articulated shape of the conception of moral responsibility as the current parameter was purposively worked out in its basic form or rather its form as a non-high-level extant theory of responsibility, focusing instead on the kernel of the idea and intuition of moral responsibility. The advantage here is that this provides a robust, but faithful conception of moral responsibility flexible enough to be adapted to various configurations of implementation of ethics within the relevant technical artifacts and that which is easily made compatible with high-level theories of moral responsibility.

Lastly, given the low-theory approach to the concept of responsibility focused largely on human experience, do responsibility and accountability on such an approach come out to the same thing or is there a difference between responsibility and accountability for the current author? First, it is important to get clear on the particular type of accountability in question: moral accountability. The focus on moral accountability is understandable in light of the primacy of the ethical (see *Introduction 0.3, 0.4*); and as such, shan't be further justified: should the reader wish to see the appropriate justification, then the author encourages the reader to see the sections of the introduction above cited. Second, moral accountability and moral responsibility, though overlapping to some degree in their core concepts, have different foci. They overlap in that they, for example, both focus on evaluating the relationship between moral value(s) and behavior. This evaluation, of course, requires explanation, use of principles of explanatory

adequacy, focused on making that relationship intelligible (i.e., providing a measure of traceability). This is consistent with the very meaning of the words ‘account’ and ‘accounting’ (see *Introduction 0.5*; Torrance 2021). They differ in foci in that, in the case of responsibility, the status of being a respondent capable of originary free acts of signification takes centerstage. Whereas, in the case of moral accountability, explanation takes centerstage. Both are related to value-based outcomes. With responsibility, the emphasis is on what an agent is to do given the value-based outcomes (e.g., making amends for wrong-doing). With moral accountability, the emphasis is also on value-based outcomes (e.g., receiving a value-based attribute), requiring a value-based response not necessarily from that which received the value-based assignment, but rather from an external party. This, of course, can occur with the concept of responsibility, but what distinguishes this concept from moral accountability is that the responsible agent has the right status and capacities to respond appropriately or at least be judged by one’s response. By contrast, in cases of moral accountability, that which is held accountable need not have the appropriate status or capacities to respond appropriately nor need it have appropriate status or capacities for the correct attribution of moral accountability.

This view of moral accountability departs greatly from that of Thomas Bivins, for example:

If responsibility is defined as a bundle of obligations, functional and moral, associated with a role, then accountability might be defined as “blaming or crediting someone for an action” - normally an action associated with a recognized responsibility (Bivins 2006).

This conception on the part of Bivins differs greatly in a twofold manner. In the first, the conception of responsibility is social obligation based as opposed to the present author's more structural and phenomenologically based conception. In the second, moral accountability is associated with value-based outcomes of praise or blame with respect to an action that, normally, has some relationship to an acknowledged responsibility. By contrast, the author's view of accountability is such that it needn't be associated with an action that has some relationship to an acknowledged responsibility *or even with the ability to be responsible at all*. These differences are important because it will not do to have a conception of responsibility or moral accountability that automatically precludes application of the concept to "autonomous" artificial intelligence systems; rather, if the concept does not or cannot apply to them, it must be shown independently, even if based on requirements that when met give rise to the legitimate application of the concept, and if they cannot meet those requirements, it does not or should not apply thereby. Yet, so as to avoid ontological chauvinism, it must be acknowledged that some of our moral concepts, and the like do or can apply to them. The view presented herein is an attempt to find this fine balance.

With the mention of technical artifacts, the discussion now turns forthwith to an articulation of this parameter of the ethical module.

1.5.4 Technical Artifacts

An "autonomous" artificial intelligence system is a technical artifact. As was stated in the introduction of this book (see *Introduction, 0.4*), this understanding of technical artifacts is adopted from Peter Kroes's treatment of them in his work entitled *Technical Artifacts: Creations*

of Mind and Matter (Kroes 2012). Though his work is rather useful for the current discussion concerning ethics of “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems, his views on technical artifacts will not, in their entirety, be adopted or defended, as doing either would, in the former, be unwarranted due to the nature of current inquiry, and in the latter, take the current discussion too far afield. Rather, his basic conception of a technical artifact as well as some of its concomitant fundamental principles and important consideration will be used.

It bears keeping in mind, as this will aid in understanding the employ of technical artifacts within the current investigation, that the purpose of such a theoretical and highly philosophical discussion concerning something as flat-footed and practical as technical artifacts is so as to better understand them. Yet, this is no mere academic pursuit. A better grasp on the nature of technical artifacts can aid in better understanding how they can be better utilized and integrated into an ever changing world, especially in cases where such technical artifacts pose the sorts of challenges that “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems pose. Admittedly, this will not explore every important avenue in this regard, only those germane to ethics and metaethics, and a small subset even of that union. Furthermore, this attempt at a better understanding of the nature of technical artifacts must need be restrained by how they are understood in engineering practice.

With the aforestated in mind, technical artifacts are of a dual nature: (1) technical function (2) materiality. In its functional aspects, it is designed to do something by means of certain instructions. That which it is to do is its aim, which it fulfills by means of following its instructions. This is pretty straightforward. In its material aspects, it is made up of certain materials (e.g., silicon, metal, plastic, wood, etc.), and that material aspect plays some sort of causal role. The technical function is related to both physical structure and human intentions

(Kroes 2012, 38). Due to the nature of technical function, technical artifacts have a peculiar nature, being both of physical and social objects (Kroes 2012, 43). This is why in order to get an accurate characterization of them, one must use both conceptualizations from physical and intentional frameworks (Kroes 2012, 40–43).

To illustrate this, take for example a pen. It is designed to write, which is its technical function as determined by the designer. This technical function is not just a capacity that the pen has. For if it were merely that, then it would be difficult to account for its assigned purpose within a social environment as well as how it could still remain a pen even if it could no longer be used for writing (e.g., were the ink cartridge inoperable). Moreover, this technical function is determined by human preferences, interests, and aims (e.g., by the designer). Hence, this technical function was assigned by some human person who determined what the goal was (e.g., writing) and what the conditions of satisfaction of that goal were (e.g., to write).

Conceptualizations from an intentional framework make it possible to understand all of this. The pen, however, only achieves its goal, some practical aim, by means of a certain material structure configured in a certain way. The role of this material structure is made sense of by conceptualizations from a physical framework: in terms of causation and physical properties (Kroes 2012, 13–45). Of course, not any material structure will do: a diving flipper is not a pen.

What of the moral status of technical artifacts? If they have any, how and what would ground it? Although it was a rather popular view that technology is value free, and thereby morally neutral, deriving value from human responses to it as well as its moral significance from how such technology is regarded and used, in recent years it has been acknowledged that technology is both value-laden and neither morally neutral nor is value extrinsic to it (Kroes 2012; Gonzalez 2013, 2015). This, of course, makes sense, given that human intention

determined the technical function of a technical artifact, and thereby the latter's aims.

Accordingly, this intention(s), which naturally has moral significance whatever its moral quality, was "embedded" in the technical function of the technical artifact. So, really how could the moral significance of technical artifacts be neutral or even extrinsic to it? This makes sense even if one were to reject the bulk of Kroes' account of the ontology of technical artifacts. Whence, however, does the moral significance of a technical artifact, which an "autonomous" artificial intelligence system is one sort, come? In other words, what grounds its moral status? The straightforward answer is human intentions and ends: ultimately, human agency.

Does this mean that technical artifacts are intrinsically moral? No. For to say that they are intrinsically moral presupposes that they are mind-independent. But as creations of *mind and matter*, evidence of the former being that the technical functions are determined by human intention: So how could they be mind-independent? Yet, in the previous paragraph, it was made clear (hopefully) that they are neither morally neutral nor is their moral significance extrinsic. What is going on here then? Keep in mind that the purpose of an inquiry into technical artifacts, a domain by and large relegated purely to engineering pursuits, despite the fact that this inquiry is theoretical and philosophical in nature, is to get a deeper understanding into the *logos* of this domain so as to better understand its underlying rationality and to optimize rational practices pertaining to this domain (e.g., better understanding how they can be better utilized and integrated into an ever changing world, *et cetera*). As such, a better way to conceptualize technical artifacts with respect to their moral significance is sought. Accordingly, the better way to do this is to hold that technical artifacts are *inherently* moral (Kroes 2012, 171–173, 179–182). This being so precisely because they are *mind-dependent* physical objects, physical structures possessed of technical functions, and these technical functions are determined by human

intentions and aims, which have a moral quality to them and which are “embedded” into the technical artifacts.

Consequently, and this is the most important takeaway from the discussion concerning the current parameter – the last parameter – of the ethical module, “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems are inherently moral. This highlights why this parameter is necessary for the ethical module. If this module is to do its job of ethically assessing “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems, then it must have the right ontological framing of the systems it purports to assess. This parameter provides that.

This wraps up a parameter-by-parameter rational articulation and defense of the ethical module attempting to show how each parameter is necessary. Recall that the parameter of the *ethical template* is necessary, because it is what needs to be in place so as to provide an ethically sound and rationally robust framework for the prospective embedding of well-reasoned and rationally substantiated moral values into the very design¹³⁹ of “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems whilst simultaneously providing a way to operationalize such values in a concrete system of the relevant sort. The parameter of the *metaphysics of persons* is necessary, because an ethical module needs a way to ground what it is that matters in moral reasoning; that is, explanatory adequacy grounded in some fundamental feature: a metaethical foundation that accounts for why moral reasoning in human experience is structured the way that is insofar as it holds persons in such high regard. Furthermore, the parameter of the *conception of responsibility* is necessary, because any module putatively designed to ethically analyze or even implement ethics in an “autonomous” artificial intelligence system must be able to account for how our

¹³⁹Although the following was mentioned in *Conceptual Tools 1.5.2*, it bears repeating: the reader may have noticed an equivocation on the word ‘design’ within this discussion. So as to clarify, it is used in two ways. In the first, it is used so as to refer to a specific phase of the technology lifecycle of “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems as well as, *mutatis mutandis*, other technical systems. In the second, it is used as a means so as to refer to the general way in which the relevant technical system is produced.

moral notions might apply to them; in this case, how moral responsibility might apply to them. Of course, all of this must be predicated on an articulated conception of moral responsibility to use as a touchstone so as to determine whether it can really apply to them or not, and *mutatis mutandis*, how that might work. As such, the parameter in question is necessary in this light. Lastly, the parameter of the *technical artifacts* is necessary, because it provides the right ontological framing of the systems it purports ethically to assess, namely: “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems.

What of their joint sufficiency for the ethical module? They are together enough for the ethical module to perform its function. For on the assumption that the parameters are jointly enough for the ethical module to perform its function, then they would together be sufficiently powerful for the ethical module to do its job. Then, they would work in a coordinated fashion in order to execute the ethical module’s function. Of course, were there no parameters, the sufficiency threshold for the ethical module to perform its function would not in any way be met ($n - 4$). Then, were they missing three parameters, the remainder would not be enough to perform the ethical module’s function ($n - 3$). Then, were they missing two parameters, the remaining complement would not be enough to perform the ethical modules function ($n - 2$). Then, were they to be missing one parameter, the remainder would not be enough for the ethical module to do its job ($n - 1$). Hence, the ethical module would need each parameter to perform its function. Therefore, each parameter would be needed, if the parameters of the ethical module are jointly sufficient for the ethical module to perform its function.

The discussion now transitions to a discussion of metaphor highlighting its benefits as a feature of the conceptual framework being worked out.

1.6 Metaphor

Although it is commonplace to associate metaphor with literature and poetry, the importance and power of metaphor is not restricted to these two. Metaphors play a pivotal role in science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (the S.T.E.M fields). Some well-known metaphors in this regard are “the clockwork universe” (Dolnik 2011), “digital ecosystem”, “motherboard”, and a “covering” in topology (Munkres 2000). Metaphor, as such, is the ink which permeates the waters of all domains of inquiry, scientific and non-scientific. What is more: it flows through humanity’s everydayness, as seen in common English language idioms, like: “the rain will hurt the rhubarb, if it is not salted”, “a day late and a dollar short”. Yet, the power and ubiquity of metaphor itself is rooted in a dynamic relationship which facilitates it.

In his article entitled “What Metaphor Means” (1978), Donald Davidson provides an account of metaphor attempting to explicate and elucidate its nature and significance. On this view, although he acknowledges the power and ubiquity of metaphor, he holds that metaphor does not constitute a special act of communication nor does it accomplish its effect through some indirect meaning which piggybacks on the literal meaning of whatever sentence or utterance expresses it. Metaphor also has no special meaning, figurative or otherwise, over and above the literal meaning of the words a metaphorical utterance or sentence contains (Davidson 1978, 257, 260–262). Hence, there is no special semantic subclass to which metaphor belongs. What, then, does it constitute? If it has no additional meaning, how does it work? Ultimately, what does metaphor mean?

What metaphor means is seeing something as something else (Davidson 1978, 263); and to repeat, what it doesn’t mean is something beyond the literal meaning of the words. It is not a shift in meaning from literal to figurative (Davidson 1978, 257–260). For it is not a trading

between meanings; that is: not a shift by a trade between two or more meanings, like for instance when one trades on an ambiguity. But rather *a shift in how one sees the world* which is facilitated by the literal meanings of natural language, because in metaphor one learns not something about language, but rather something about the phenomena to which language applies (Davidson 1978, 263).

Consider three examples. In the first, Mike comes to understand something and exclaims to his friend Janet, “I see the truth of it!”. Truth, of course, is not something that is available to one’s visual perception, so the person in the example is not literally seeing truth. However, the literal meaning of the words of the sentence, taken as a whole, convey a change in the world, namely: Mike’s epistemic state, that he’s learned something. This helps Janet to see Mike as someone else or better yet to see Mike’s epistemic status as some other epistemic status, to see something X as something Y, where: ‘X’ and ‘Y’ stand for two distinct epistemic *stata* of Mike. In the second, a sculptor is having difficulty creating a new sculpture. Her mentor and friend attempts to help her by encouraging her to see what it is she wishes to sculpt by saying, “the sculpture is in the block of clay, you just have to free it”. With these words of encouragement, the artist is able to create a breathtaking sculpture with relative ease. Again, the metaphorical utterance, since the sculpture was not literally in the block of clay, by means of the literal meaning of the words of the utterance itself, effects a change: helping the artist to see her task as some other task; that is: not as creating a sculpture, but as freeing one that was already there. In the third example, consider John Wheeler’s coinage of the term ‘black hole’ in 1929 for a region of spacetime where gravity is so strong that not even light and other waves on the electromagnetic spectrum can escape. Black holes themselves were not proposed by Wheeler, who further worked out some of their properties, but rather by John Michell (Schaffer 1979). It

took a rather long time from the proposal of the idea referring to the phenomena, which would be later confirmed empirically, until coinage of the term. The term itself being a metaphor, one which is taken for granted at this point in history, helps one to see the world in a different way. To see a world where spacetime and gravity are such that for a region of the former not even light can escape: a way of looking at the world that escaped the conceptions of most scientists of Wheeler's day (Ibid.). What these examples all have in common is that metaphor facilitates seeing phenomena in the world in a different way.

It must be remarked for sake of clarity that the facilitation metaphor provides is not peculiar to metaphor: simile does the same thing. So, this characterization of metaphor does not as such uniquely individuate metaphor. In response, the author grants that simile can perform that same function, namely: of facilitating seeing something as something else: seeing X as Y. They, however, both do so through very different means. Simile does so by positing a specific relationship of isomorphism: X is *like* Y, whereas in metaphor, we are helped to see X as Y, but not through positing a specific isomorphic relationship. One example of this is David Hume's own take on how his *Treatise of Human Nature* (1739) was received, "Never literary attempt was more unfortunate than my *Treatise of Human Nature*. It fell *dead-born from the press* [author's italics], without reaching such distinction, as even to excite a murmur among the zealots." Hume's opinion of how his work was received says something about a change in the world; that is, to say: a change that helps us to see how the book was received, which constitutes a change in the world. This is different in structure, of course, than if he had said, 'It fell *like* [author's italics] a dead-born from the press.', both help us to see the publishing of the book in a light that conveys something new about the world, namely: how the book was received. Metaphor does so in a way that doesn't establish an explicit isomorphic relationship between objects, or in this case

between an object and a subject, with respect to some aspect; whereas, simile does indeed posit such a relationship. Furthermore, one can of course rephrase metaphor as simile, but metaphor as metaphor is such that – like simile – it allows and facilitates seeing something as something else.

The facilitation of seeing the world in a new way, but not through positing an isomorphic relationship between objects or subjects and the like, that metaphor affords is not reducible to nor entirely explainable by simile. For were it, then how is the peculiar means of accessing this new “vision” of the world accounted for exactly? Richard Moran’s view of a “framing effect” does a better job in accounting for the peculiar means of intelligibility access in question (Moran 1989; Hills 2022). This idea is related to that of a “fundamental framing” touched upon in the last chapter of this book (see *Conceptual Tools I: 1.1*), which in turn is related to Wittgenstein’s idea of being held captive by a picture (*Conceptual Tools I: 1.1*), though Moran’s view as well as that of the author’s is less pejorative in nature. Moreover, similarity (or dissimilarity) as a way of accounting for the power and meaning of metaphor fails to be explanatorily adequate, because everything is trivially similar or dissimilar to everything else (Davidson 1978, 39). So, how is metaphor, thereby, distinguished from anything else? How is the peculiar type of intelligibility access explained thereby? Furthermore, even if similarity and dissimilarity could non-trivially account for the power and meaning of metaphor, such an approach would nonetheless remain explanatorily inadequate. For such an explanation would insufficiently ground the *explanandum*; that is: would fail to provide an explanation for metaphor in terms of fundamental properties, structures, entities, and the like. This is because similarities and dissimilarities between objects and subjects, objects and objects, subjects and subjects, *et cetera*, themselves are always perspectival with respect to an agent or agents, and seeing these similarities and dissimilarities so as to use them to account for anything relies on a prior understanding of ways of grouping and

classifying things in the world, which are rooted in our habits of classifying things (Goodman 1976, 23). It is these habits of classifying, then, that would ground metaphor, not similarity and dissimilarity as such, and therefore not theories of metaphor relying on similarity and dissimilarity so as to account for the power and meaning of metaphor (e.g., elliptical simile view).¹⁴⁰

The reason why any of this is important for the current investigation of this book is that in science and engineering seeing the world in a different way, in a new light aids in understanding the world. This can not only further scientific understanding of the world and humanity's relationship to it, which in turn improves our explanatory models and predictive relationship to phenomena in the world (more on this to follow), but this can also help to improve engineering practice, which of course can feedback into improving scientific investigation and human welfare (e.g., the invention and use of the electron microscope). This, along with the quality of parsimony evidenced by this view on metaphor, for the purposes of the present investigation of this book, is what recommends adoption of the Davidsonian account of metaphor. Furthermore, all of this speaks in favor of why including metaphor, herein understood, as a parameter of the conceptual framework – S.E.M., where 'M' stands for the parameter of metaphor – is a necessary condition for the conceptual framework, namely: it's an explicit parameter which grounds and facilitates one of the most important aspects of both science and human life more generally: the nature and manner of representation. Such a parameter of immense import needs to be accounted for in a way in which it can be active in efforts to guide human technological development on an ethically optimized trajectory.

¹⁴⁰ In this latter regard, see: Fogelin, R.J. 1994. *Metaphors, Similes and Similarity*. In: Hintikka, J. (eds) *Aspects of Metaphor*. Synthese Library, v. 238. Springer, Dordrecht. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-015-8315-2_2 and Keehley, Jay T. 1979. "Metaphor Theories and Theoretical Metaphors." *Philosophy and Phenomenological Research* 39 (4): 582–588. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2106902>.

In concluding this section on metaphor, it is important to highlight that with the inclusion of metaphor, the last piece of the conceptual framework has been articulated and defended. As such, S.E.M. (*Social Imaginary. Ethical Module. Metaphor.*) is complete. Yet, with the inclusion of all parameters of S.E.M, the inquiry may be posed, namely: ‘How are the parameters – *social imaginary, ethical module, metaphor* – jointly sufficient for the conceptual framework in question?’. They are in virtue of being enough for the conceptual framework to perform its function. This function is to guide the technology lifecycle from the standpoint of an ethically-value-based perspective. This can be seen by means of two lines of argumentation.

In the first, from the standpoint of rational practice, when one intends to guide the technological lifecycle from the standpoint of an ethically-value-based perspective, one can see that an evaluative framework is present, that a specific set of ethical values is present, and that the whole target item or set of target items (e.g., the technological life cycle of “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems) is seen as that which cannot or should not be distinct from ethical-value-based considerations. One can see this in the GDPR documentation (GDPR 2016) and the debates concerning regulation of *Facebook* (Senate Judiciary and Commerce Committees 2018). Hence, one may conclude from an all-things-considered perspective that these three components are considered enough (if only minimally so) for the task of guiding the technological lifecycle of some technical artifact more generally and, *mutatis mutandis*, “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems (and even digital transformation). Of course, the last consideration, namely: being seen as that which cannot or should not be distinct from ethical-value-based considerations, does not require embedding of such values in the technology itself. Nonetheless, it is hardly controversial that, given the technology in question, this would be considered a step towards optimization in this regard, even if only seen as a complement to

external means of ethical regulation. This is a positive argument in favor of the joint sufficiency of the parameters in question.

In the second, if *social imaginary, ethical module, metaphor* are jointly sufficient for S.E.M to perform its function, then it would be in accordance with the definition of a sufficient condition. Consider that: if a property H is a sufficient condition for K, then whenever H is present, K must be present. Thereupon, whenever property K is absent, then property H is absent (Skyrms 2000, 84–86). Moreover, using an example inspired from Brian Skyrms own epidemiological example (Skyrms 2000, 86), suppose that exposure to poison oak is sufficient for a severe skin rash and blistering. One may conclude, in all probability, that from the absence of a severe skin rash and blistering, one has not been exposed to poison oak.¹⁴¹ Accordingly, if *social imaginary, ethical module, metaphor* are jointly sufficient for S.E.M to perform its function, then whenever the effort to guide technology in the relevant manner is absent, then one of these parameters is absent, too (e.g., the ethical module being disregarded). Hence, they would not be jointly present. This is a negative argument in favor of the joint sufficiency of the parameters in question. Additionally, although these two arguments are not conclusive, they provide a non-trivial measure of cogency in favor of the parameters, *social imaginary, ethical module, metaphor*, being jointly sufficient for the conceptual framework S.E.M.

Lastly and some of this bears repeating: this conceptual framework will both help embed moral principles, and the like, into all levels of the technology lifecycle. In so doing, it will work in tandem with the model, which is articulated in what follows. But first a discussion of models from a metaspective is necessary so as to properly understand the nature of models within the

¹⁴¹ This reason is, as is so for all inductive reasoning, defeasible. For one could both be exposed to poison oak and have neither a skin rash or blistering due to being immune to the effects of the oils from the plant. But since this counterexample simply shows that with inductive argumentation the truth of the premises does not guarantee the truth of the conclusion, this presents no weakness peculiar to the argument given by the author: just a vulnerability of a certain class of reasoning having been employed. Yet, the greater point attempting to be made stands.

parameters of this overall investigation. It is hoped that by doing so, the way in which S.E.M. would work together with a model-construct will be more clearly understood.

2.0 Conceptual Tools II: Models (M.)

2.1 The Nature of Models

Social imaginaries and metaphors play a central role in human understanding and lived-experience. In fact, humans understand themselves and the world around them often through and with the aid of these. What is true of social imaginaries and metaphors is no less true of models. Models come in a variety of sorts, e.g.:

Probing models, phenomenological models, computational models, developmental models, explanatory models, impoverished models, testing models, idealized models, theoretical models, scale models, heuristic models, caricature models, exploratory models, didactic models, fantasy models, minimal models, toy models, imaginary models, mathematical models, mechanistic models, substitute models, iconic models, formal models, analogue models, and instrumental models (Frigg & Hartmann 2020)

Moreover, some of the key roles models play are explanatory, justificatory, and predictive (Bailor-Jones 2002; Frigg & Hartmann 2020). Models primarily play this role in the fields of science, technological development, engineering, and mathematics (henceforth collectively referred to, when appropriate, as S.T.E.M fields). Insofar as models play this role, they draw on deep roots connecting to everyday human experience in its multifarious aspects and activities.

But what are models? In what sense is the term ‘model’ to be employed within the overall discussion of this book? Furthermore, what way do models draw on deep roots connecting to human experience?

In the S.T.E.M fields, the term ‘model’ is used in at least two ways, which are relevant for the current discussion. The first is for deductive systems. These are systems closed under proveability. What this means was explained at length in *Conceptual Tools I* concerning the ethical module. The reader is encouraged to consult that section, as this will not be repeated here. For such systems, a model is an interpretation that makes a sentence true (Chang & Keisler 2012). For systems not closed under provability (see *Conceptual Tools I: 1.4*), the author proposes that a model is an interpretation that makes an explanation adequate. This is consistent with the way models are often used in practice: they function, at the very least, as interpretive lenses and explanatory vehicles and tools for understanding phenomena in the world (Bailor-Jones 2002; Frigg and Hartmann 2020). Moreover, there is additional merit to this proposal, as it provides a way to consistently extend metalogical concepts from one class of systems of logic, principles, and proof procedures to another in such a way so as to highlight the fundamental idea behind models that applies both to non-empirical and empirical endeavors within the S.T.E.M fields.

Besides a maximally consistent way to understand models extending between (largely) empirical domains of application (inductive and abductive) and (largely) non-empirical domains of application (deductive), what is it about models such that they can be understood this way? The key to answering this question is the notion of interpretation; this is the key intelligibility vector. Many things can be said about interpretation, much of which must remain unsaid here. One point that will be pursued, however, is that interpretations represent their referent, whatever

their referent. If this is not entirely wrong-headed, this would mean that interpretations are a form of representation. Hence, models – for deductive and non-deductive systems – are representations. With respect to the S.T.E.M fields, the fields of relevance for this discussion, they are a form of scientific representation. But what sort of representation does this make them?

The author proposes, in line with Roman Frigg and James Nguyen’s illuminating article, that models insofar as they are a species of scientific representation are a form of *representation-as* (Frigg & Nguyen 2017, 158–162). There is a complicated story here behind understanding scientific representation in this way, a story whose exploration would take the current discussion in directions not germane to the overall goal of the main investigation of this book. Suffice to say, the intuitive idea behind *representation-as* can be seen from the history of science in how electrical current was discussed and represented. Due to the difficulties in conceptualization, it was *represented as* water flowing in a hydraulic system (Nahin 2002). In this way, complex systems, some of which behave in ways that can often only be understood when represented in more simple and intuitive ways, can be understood as an extension of a prior knowledge-base. This example is instructive; and from it and the above considerations, one may conclude thusly: in scientific representation, understood herein as *representation-as*, one represents phenomena in the world under some elucidating (ideally) aspect.

Simplifying matters into takeaways relevant for the current investigation, a few additional considerations are noteworthy. First, *representation-as* says something about how we classify things (Frigg & Nguyen, 150–160). Moreover, we learn how to classify things based on developing habits of classification, not just through learning definitions and definitional analysis (Ibid; Goodman 1976). This makes sense, because in order to define something, one needs to recognize it. Hence, this recognition would be prior to definition. Moreover, recognizing

something (a tree, a wooden chair, a wooden ladle, etc.) is based on isolating repeatable patterns in terms of name, form, and function.¹⁴² This repetition allows one to understand what patterns are reliable; that is: more enduring and conforming to expectation. Thus, prediction is involved, as patterns conform more and more to expectations. This process is aided too by intervention.¹⁴³ Through this, predictions become more robust. Thereupon, habits of classifying become more robust and reliable. Furthermore, they become more fine-grained, robust, and reliable with the addition of explanation. When this process of growth and learning, which is rooted in habits of classifying, is mature, it becomes easier, though not fool-proof, to determine which regularities are reliable and correspondingly which predicates are projectible.¹⁴⁴ These sorts of predicates can be seen as units in models of explanation that are adequate and robust prediction-wise (i.e., maximally predictive [sometimes aided by causal intervention]).

Second, models and metaphors are more closely related than they might *prima facie* appear. On the Davidsonian understanding of metaphor touched upon in the last section and adopted herein, namely: the “brute force” account of metaphor (Hills 2022), metaphor is that property of language whereby and through which we learn to see something as something else (Davidson 1978, 263). This, of course, means that in metaphor one is learning about how language applies to the world; that is to say, how words apply to phenomena (Ibid.). This means that in metaphor one is learning how to represent phenomena under differing aspects. Hence, metaphor would also be a form of representation-as.

What, then, would distinguish models from metaphors, or are they the same thing? No,

¹⁴² This phrasing, namely: “name, form, and function” is, though not unique per se, inspired by a teacher of spirituality from the Indian tradition, Swami Sarvapriyananda, “God in Every Experience”, *Vedanta Society of Southern California*, June 2016, https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=vk6evY05b_0.

¹⁴³ For an illuminating discussion on intervention and causal inference, see: Eberhardt, Frederick and Scheines, Richard. 2007. “Interventions and Causal Inference.” *Philosophy of Science* 74(5): 981–995. <https://doi.org/10.1086/525638>.

¹⁴⁴ For an illuminating discussion in this regard, see: Moreland, John. 1976. “On Projecting Grue.” *Philosophy of Science* 43(3): 363–377. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/187231>.

they are not. In this regard, I agree with the late Daniela Bailor-Jones that models and metaphors are not selfsame (Bailor-Jones, 110–121). Her rejection of the idea that they are selfsame is based on her rejection of Mary Hesse's conception of models as having some sort of figurative meaning (Ibid.). Given that the present author also rejects this account of metaphor due to his endorsement of the Davidsonian account of metaphor, he nonetheless does not adopt the same rational basis upon which to reject the claim that metaphors and models are selfsame. Rather, the present author holds the view that models and metaphors are distinct due to the following. They both belong to the overall category of representation-as, but respectively belong to different subcategories of it: they each constitute different subclasses of the class representation-as. Moreover, the subclasses are to be distinguished by the *manner in which they represent*. Models, especially within the S.T.E.M fields, on the one hand, are a type of represent-as in accordance with standards, often high, of explanatory adequacy, strictures of logic (e.g., deductive, inductive, abductive, etc.) and mathematics (e.g., set theory, statistics, probability theory, etc.), methodological constraints associated with scientific epistemology (e.g., scientific method) as well as model and theory building (e.g., parsimony), along with aesthetics of model and theory building (e.g., elegance, simplicity, etc.); and in the case of causation specifically, rigors of causal model building (e.g., the Neyman–Rubin Causal Model approach)¹⁴⁵ and the standards for establishing reliable predictions (Kuhn & Johnson 2018). Metaphors, on the other hand, are a

¹⁴⁵ Sekhon, Jasjeet. 2007. "The Neyman–Rubin Model of Causal Inference and Estimation via Matching Methods". *The Oxford Handbook of Political Methodology* New York: Oxford University Press. Please also see: (1) Rubin, Donald. 1974. "Estimating Causal Effects of Treatments in Randomized and Nonrandomized Studies". *Journal. Educational. Psychology.* 66 (5): 688–701. doi:10.1037/h0037350. (2) Holland, Paul W. 1986. "Statistics and Causal Inference". *Journal American Statistical Association* 81 (396): 945–960. doi:10.1080/01621459.1986.10478354. JSTOR 2289064. (3) Pearl, Judea. 2009. *Causality: Models, Reasoning, and Inference* 2nd ed. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. (4) Sloman, Steven. 2005. *Causal Models: How People Think about the World and Its Alternatives*. New York: Oxford University Press.

type of representation-as operating in a less restricted way. That is, they need not comply with rigorous scientific, mathematical, or analytical techniques and the like in order to secure their representation. As a minimum criterion, they must aid in seeing something as something else, but they have far more options at their disposal for securing this type of representation.

Third, despite the discussion so far focusing on representation-as in the context of the S.T.E.M fields, there is a finer distinction to be made between representation-as in science and representation-as in engineering. Models in engineering are also a form of representation-as, but they are a little different. In scientific forms of representation, as representation-as, models (or theories), represent some putative phenomenon. In engineering, however, one is not necessarily representing something that is acknowledged as already “being there” in some sense, however that is explicated. But one is more representing something that *could be* there. So, it is a type of modal representation in the form of representation-as or *modal representation-as*. For in engineering, one would use a model as a design schematic in the service of creating something. That something is a possible technical artifact unless it's created. After its creation, it's an actual technical artifact. If this is not entirely wrong-headed, then metaphors, models in science, and models in engineering, are all different forms of representation-as from a taxonomic perspective. So, the genus is representation-as, and there are three different species of representation-as: (1) metaphors (2) models in science (3) models in engineering.¹⁴⁶

¹⁴⁶ The author here acknowledges the cognitive and intellectual value of representation and the central role that plays in the enterprise of science. However, the author does not necessarily want to endorse more traditional forms of representation theory coming out of 20th and 21st century philosophy which seems to be largely cognitive as if representation can be disentangled from embodiment (Lycan 2019; Pitt 2022). The author acknowledges that this is really not a viable conception of representation, since it leaves out an explanatory feature germane to its understanding – the body. The author recognizes one key aspect of the value that embodiment brings to the concept of representation, namely: immersion. That is, one is not a spectator to one's body, rather one is immersed in one's body: one has an immersive relationship in one's interactions with the body. One way the value of this can be transferred, *mutatis mutandis*, to this conception of representation-as, with respect to conceptions put forth herein, is that it can highlight the value of immersive or interactive models of explanations. So, if representation-as is the larger genus for which metaphors, models in science, and models in engineering are species, then all of that which falls under this genus is such that it would not be separable from embodiment. Although the author fully acknowledges the added elucidation that immersive or participatory knowledge may bring (Polanyi 1958, 1983

It is hoped that with the metamodel discussion plus the preceding discussion articulating and arguing in favor of S.E.M. and its components, the stage is set to complete the theoretical basis with the introduction of the model-construct itself followed by a subsequent discussion as to how the conceptual framework, S.E.M., would work in tandem with the model-construct.

2.2 The Model-Construct

How would the foregoing considerations transfer into engineering practice? The author proposes the following:

Figure 4.

[1966]), a full explication of this conception, along with a discussion of its implications, falls outside the purview of the current project of this book.

The key to understanding the model-construct or model proposed is as follows. Each module above introduces constraints. Each module of constraints constitutes a phase of the technology lifecycle. Moreover, the arrows designate a movement within this process technological lifecycle or “techno-lifecycle”¹⁴⁷; and as such, designates a movement from one modular subprocess wherein one determines some key feature of the modular stages of the techno-lifecycle as it moves to the next subprocess. Furthermore, each movement between modular subprocesses is a filtering step¹⁴⁸. This filtering reduces the axiological possibilities upon which features of our technology can be based, and it does so by means of the nature of the particular constraint.

Theoretically, this idea of axiological-filtering constraints, is adapted from semantics for modal logic. To see how this is intended to work, a brief overview of this semantics is given: keeping in mind that this is not a project on modal logic, so an extensive discussion is unnecessary. Moreover, the following overview of semantics for modal logic is incorporated from a draft the author published online; and the reader should see this publication, should she or he wish to follow up.¹⁴⁹ Beginning with the nature of modal expressions, note that modal adverbs and adjectives are used interchangeably. Moreover, the sentence operators, “diamond” (‘ \diamond ’) and

¹⁴⁷ The author puts scare quotes around this term so as to signify that the term is being used in a non-standard way. ‘Techno’, in popular parlance, refers to a type of popular music. The author in no way intends the word in this sense; hence the author is not referring to the cycle of a music type or even fad. Rather, the term “techno-lifecycle” is intended as a shortened version of ‘technology lifecycle’.

¹⁴⁸ Dr. Peter G. Kirchsclaeger has a similar concept which he features in his book, *Digital Transformation and Ethics: Ethical Considerations on the Robotization and Automation of Society and the Economy and the Use of Artificial Intelligence*, 165–176. Baden-Baden, Germany: Nomos. The current author’s idea is not inspired by his, but due to the *prima facie* similarity, it is important to acknowledge Dr. Kirchsclaeger’s work.

¹⁴⁹ Butler, Aaron. 2017. “Concerning The Underlying Reasoning in von Balthasar’s Philosophical Theology: A Modal Analysis”, 6–8. *The Philosophical Theology of von Balthasar (Spring Semester Seminar)*, Yale University.

https://www.academia.edu/33568003/Concerning_The_Underlying_Reasoning_in_von_Balthasars_Philosophical_Theology_A_Modal_Analysis_Re_upload_

“box” (\square) are, respectively, used for ‘possibly’ and ‘necessarily’. These can be prefixed to any sentence, and they can also be iterated: $\diamond\diamond A$, $\square\square B$, $\diamond\square C$. For example, the latter reads “possibly, C is necessary”. Also, necessity and possibility are inter-definable; thus, $\diamond A \Leftrightarrow \sim\square\sim A$ and $\square A \Leftrightarrow \sim\diamond\sim A$.¹⁵⁰ Furthermore, modal logic is systematic. Accordingly, modality is often spoken of with respect to a formal system. Revisiting the idea of a formal system within this context (see *Conceptual Tools I: 1.4* of the current book), what is meant here by ‘formal system’ is a set of sentences “closed under provability”¹⁵¹; that is, a set of sentences of some language that contains every sentence of that language provable from that set. This means that if a set is closed under provability, then if there is a proof that a sentence follows from such a set, then the sentence is in the set in question. Moreover, within the context of mathematical logic, the term ‘formal system’ is synonymous with ‘theory’; and as such, a theory means “a set of sentences that contains all sentences of its language that are provable from it. Thus, the theorems of a theory are just the sentences in T, and $\vdash_T B$ and $B \in T$ are two ways of writing the same thing.” (Boolos, et al. 2007, 191).

With this in mind, a system K is considered. The system K is the least normal modal logic; it will serve as the basic system within which our discussion of modality will take place. What it means for K to be a “least” modal logic is that it has the least amount of axioms, proof

¹⁵⁰ This also allows for such rules as Modal negation (MN):

$$\sim\square\sim A \Leftrightarrow \diamond A$$

$$\sim\diamond\sim A \Leftrightarrow \square A$$

$$\sim\square A \Leftrightarrow \diamond\sim A$$

$$\sim\diamond A \Leftrightarrow \square\sim A.$$

¹⁵¹ I am indebted to the work of Peter Vranas for his rather informative and insightful handouts, “Handouts” *Philosophy 512: Modal Logic*, (Spring Semester, 2023)), available online at: <https://vranas.website/512/512Handouts.pdf> [accessed 13 June 2022 and 11 April 2023]. Moreover, for an expanded discussion of this topic, please see the following works: (A) Boolos, George S. 1995. *The Logic of Provability*, Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. (B) Williamson, Timothy .1996. “Logics of Provability.” *Philosophical Quarterly* 46 (182):110–116. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2956313>. (C) Buehler, R.J. 2014. *The Logic of Provability: Notes by R.J. Buehler Based on the Logic of Provability by George Boolos*. Berkeley: UCB Mathematics: University of California Press. <https://math.berkeley.edu/~buehler/The%20Logic%20of%20Provability.pdf> [accessed 24 June 2022]. (D) Verbrugge, Rineke (L.C.). 2017. “Provability Logic”, *The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy* (Fall Edition), Edward N. Zalta (ed.), URL = <<https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/fall2017/entries/logic-provability/>>.

procedures, and rules of equivalence.¹⁵² Moreover, what it means for K to be a “normal” modal logic is for it to contain the rule for Modal negation (MN) and modality operator prefixed sentences for every sentence: whenever it contains something of the form $(p_1 \& \dots p_n) \rightarrow p$, it also contains something of the form $(\Box p_1 \& \dots \Box p_n) \rightarrow \Box p$ ($n \geq 0$). Furthermore, whatever is true of a modal system K, must preserve classical validity in every modal context; that is, it must be a consistent extension of what we already know about natural deduction. In other words – and this would be the worst, should it come to pass – whatever is valid in a non-modal context cannot become invalid in a modal context.¹⁵³

Now, modal logic, like all logic, is studied within a language, and each language possesses both syntax and semantics. For this discussion, syntactical considerations are set aside in favor of focusing on the relevant semantics. The semantics, then, are as follows. A language is a set of sentence letters (e.g., E, F, G, ...), and interpretation of a language is an ordered-triple where:

1. ‘W’ is a nonempty set of possible worlds .¹⁵⁴

¹⁵² What an axiom is needs no thorough explanation here, save only to say that it is a statement taken to be true as an initial point for reasoning. A ‘proof procedure’, however, needs some explaining. A proof procedure is a non-empty set of rules of inference, for example, Conjunction Elimination (CE): $p \& q / \therefore p$; $p \& q / \therefore q$. A rule of equivalence also needs some explaining. These allow conversion from one sentence of a given form to another sentence of a given form with no change of truth-value, e.g.: Distribution (Dist): $(p \& (q \vee r)) \Leftrightarrow ((p \& q) \vee (p \& r))$; $(p \vee (q \& r)) \Leftrightarrow ((p \vee q) \& (p \vee r))$. For more on this, please see Peter Vranas. 2021. “Handouts” *Philosophy 511: Symbolic Logic*, (Fall Semester, 2021]), available online at: <https://vranas.website/511/511handouts.pdf>.

¹⁵³ The other way around, is fine and to be expected: with less tools, validity becomes harder to evaluate. But, as intuition would have it, with more tools judging the presence of validity should become easier. The author directs the reader to a most illuminating discussion of modality, whence I get much of what I here discuss: John Hawthorn. 1990. “Natural Deduction in Normal Modal Logic”, *Notre Dame Journal of Formal Logic* 31 (2): 263–273.

¹⁵⁴ The author, unfortunately, cannot go into a detailed discussion of exactly what a possible world is. This would take the current discussion too far afield. The author can say, however, that it tracks the intuitive idea of a set containing a particular way in which circumstances could be otherwise with respect either to an actual circumstance or some other possible circumstance, assuming there is more than one possible circumstance.

2. ‘R’ is a binary relation on ‘W’, which maps from world to world (i.e., the accessibility relation: ‘Rww’ stands for “w’ is accessible from w”).

3. ‘v’ is a function which assigns truth-values to every sentence letter world-pair. Normal truth functional connectives are employed, namely: ‘∨’ (“vel” in Latin) for ‘or’, ‘∧’ for ‘and’, ‘¬’ for negation, etc.

Moreover, at a given world:

1. $\Box p$ is true exactly if p is true at every world accessible from w; where $w \in W$.
2. $\Diamond p$ is true exactly if p is true at some world accessible from w; where $w \in W$.¹⁵⁵

Lastly, an argument is K-valid precisely if, for every interpretation of its language, at every world of the interpretation at which all its premises are true, the conclusion is also true (Vranas 2023, 4).

The semantics for a modal system K can, and indeed needs to be, extended to allow for making sense of various inferences of interest. Moreover, K is extended *by specifying constraints on the accessibility relation governing just how K can be consistently extended*. The details of these extensions are numerous and baroque, and ultimately not necessary to go over in a copious manner. It is, nonetheless, important to describe them briefly, because they will add specificity and concreteness to the comparison being made to axiological-filtering constraints. The constraints on the accessibility relation are as follows (Vranas 2023, 6):

Extendability (η) - $\forall w \exists w' Rww'$: some world is accessible from every world.

¹⁵⁵ If no world is accessible from w, then for every sentence p, $\Box p$ is true and $\Diamond p$ is false at w.

Reflexivity (ρ) - $\forall w Rww$: every world is accessible from itself.

Symmetry (σ) - $\forall w \forall w' (Rww' \rightarrow Rw'w)$: for every world, if w' is accessible from w , then w is accessible from w' .

Transitivity (τ) - $\forall w \forall w' \forall w'' ((Rw'w'' \& Rww') \rightarrow Rww'')$: for every world, if w'' is accessible from w' and w' is accessible from w , then w'' is accessible from w .

Euclideaness (ϵ) - $\forall w \forall w' \forall w'' ((Rww'' \& Rww') \rightarrow Rw'w'')$: for every world, if w'' is accessible from w and w' is accessible from w , then w'' is accessible from w' .

Universality (υ) - $\forall w \forall w' Rww'$: every world is accessible from every world.

Again, these constraints govern just how the semantics for a modal system K can be consistently extended. This impacts the conditions under which certain modal formulas are true and the truth preserving permissibility of certain modal inferences (Blackburn et al. 2001). Accordingly, a modal formulas' truth-value at a possible world may depend on what is true at some other possible world; hence, the notion of access from one world to another and various rules which govern the shape of that interaction (Ibid.). This tracks the intuitive idea expressed in natural languages that the truth of a modal sentence like, 'There may be an earthquake today.' depends on some, but not all possible circumstances. This, of course, would affect the nature of certain inferences in natural languages such as, 'There may be an earthquake today; therefore, we should

be prepared to get to safety.’ This inference’s validity or lack thereof would depend on some, but not all possible circumstances, like the relevant party’s location. The mechanics of accessibility relations for modal logic semantics is an attempt to formalize this understanding.

Just as the accessibility relation facilitates access between worlds impacting the conditions under which certain modal formulas are true and the truth preserving permissibility of certain modal inferences, which tracks the intuitive idea that the truth of one’s natural language sentences, and thereby claims which they express, may come to depend on some, but not all possible circumstances, so too with the axiological-filtering constraints. These constraints facilitate passage to possible value bases for the operationalization and implementation thereof in “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems. This tracks the intuitive idea that the ethical viability of our artificial intelligence technology, “autonomous” or otherwise – and this applies to technology in general – depends on what ethical values these technical artifacts are based on and that which they embody. Accordingly, just as the truth of a modal sentence may depend on the circumstances on which they are based, the ethical viability of human technology may depend on the configuration of values on which the technology is based. If this is not entirely wrong-headed, then in taking up an ethically prospective orientation on the technology lifecycle of “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems (again: really all human technical artifacts), one would need to have a way of filtering the value bases of the technology. Furthermore, this would need to be thorough: operating at all stages of the techno-lifecycle: design, development, and deployment (i.e., utilization in society or “rollout”). Providing the aforementioned model herein proposed, along with its axiological-filtering constraints, *et cetera*, is an attempt to provide an accounting or account: an interpretation that makes an explanation adequate, which can be

simultaneously implemented by attempting to illustrate – even if only in broad strokes – how this could be done.

From a practical perspective, and this might further elucidate how the proposed model would function, this would prevent features of technology that encode or operationalize bankrupt moral values such as racism, antisemitism, sexism, and the like, or even interpersonal values like that which make it easier to engage in social bullying, of which at a group level mobbing is a form, and various forms of duplicity and skullduggery all too rampant (e.g., in professional and industry settings).¹⁵⁶ The point being: not any moral value will do the job. The community of stakeholders in technological development in general, and “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems in particular, need to be more discerning about the ethical-value basis of their technology. Turning now to a look at each constraint, the author hopes to increase understanding of how the model, from a practical perspective, might work.

In the first, the constraint is on research goals and approach to technology. This constraint can be extended, *mutatis mutandis*, to all technology, but the specific focus is, of course, “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems. Moreover, in terms of the dynamic process the proposed model is to embody, the arrow communicates the subprocess being targeted: moving from initial brainstorming yielding a design. Furthermore, an example of how the axiological-constraint filtering might work is in taking an approach to creating human-centered artificial intelligence systems, like the approach proposed by Stuart Russell (Russell 2019). His approach is one that calls for a shift in impetus for development of artificial intelligence systems,

¹⁵⁶ The author would like to acknowledge Dr. Peter G. Kirchsclaeger’s contributions in working out the practical consequences. For in conversation with him during the November 17, 2022 colloquium session of the Institute of Social Ethics ISE, wherein the author presented a PowerPoint presentation of the project of this book, the example of antisemitism as a concrete bankrupt moral value would, of course, need to be blocked from being operationalized (i.e., filtered out) in “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems. Given that the author was already thinking of this idea in relation to racism and sexism, he has chosen explicitly to incorporate Dr. Kirchsclaeger’s extension of the same concept of rigorous value discernment. The extension of this same concept to interpersonal values which are bankrupt and in need of blocking (filtering) remains the author’s.

“autonomous” or otherwise from that of optimization – getting better and better and better at so-called “human tasks”, which may proceed in ways inconsistent with human welfare or even the human values to which their creators aspire – to something that reflects greater discernment as to what values guide or *should* guide development of the relevant technology. This approach would, of course, call into question markers of “progress”. For example, would it even, from a machine ethics perspective or perspective that takes human values seriously, make sense to develop artificial intelligence systems – again “autonomous” or otherwise – in the direction of an artificial general intelligence system (AGI), the latter of which affords for the operation of “machine intelligence” across a wide variety of domains and novel contexts: intelligence thought to be most closely approximating hominid intelligence, and especially that of *homo sapien* intelligence in particular (Bostrom & Yudkowsky 2014, 316–334)? Taking a slower more reflective approach, which Russell calls for, would be an example of the constraint in question. Now, the particular nature of the value constraint operating at this level is that of the evaluative framework set forth by the *Social Imaginary* component of S.E.M. This evaluative framework is one of moral values offering a moral ordering.¹⁵⁷ In fact, it is from the ordering provided by the evaluative framework that the content of the constraint is provisioned.

In the second, the constraint is on design, architecture, *et cetera*, of technology. As was so with the previous module, the arrow communicates the subprocess being targeted: moving from design yielding a development. Naturally, this constraint can be extended, *mutatis mutandis*, to all technology, but the specific focus is “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems. Moreover, an example of how this might work can be twofold. First, providing built-in data auditing for stakeholders (Haas 2017). This would be a built-in feature of the architecture providing a way *in*

¹⁵⁷ For more details on this, the author encourages the reader to see the relevant section of this book, namely: *Conceptual Tools I: 1.2.*

situ to observe the running of the algorithm(s) so as to understand what the instructions are and how they are being executed. This data audit would provide both a code and code-translated version side-by-side so as to increase intelligibility. This would make it easier to know whether different subroutines, for example, unduly weigh certain demographic factors in the algorithms of an “autonomous” artificial institutional assistant or some such relevant artificial intelligence put to the task of determining who receives a bank loan; or as another example, making it easier to know whether an “autonomous” vehicle, drone – rescue or combat – unduly weighs skin complexion in identifying human patients or combatants, respectively. These are just a few examples – but the point, or so it is hoped, is clear – of how this axiological-constraint filtering can be concretely manifested. Second, to provide engineering or data scientist consultancy so as to assist, if need be, in making sense of the data audit, etc. The key here in either case is to make the features ubiquitous, persistent, and standard. Lastly, the particular nature of the value constraint operating at this level can be traced back to and extrapolated from the *Ethical Module* component of S.E.M. Given the examples provided, it can be traced back to the ethical template (*Conceptual Tools I: 1.5.1*), the parameters thereof provisioning the content and structure of the constraint.

In the third, the constraint is on implementation or rollout of technology or making it generally available to the public.¹⁵⁸ The concomitant arrow signifies a movement from development yielding deployment. This constraint can also be extended, *mutatis mutandis*, to all technology, but the specific focus is, as was the case with the other two constraints, “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems. An example of how this might work would be in

¹⁵⁸ The author needs to be very clear here. By use of the term ‘rollout’ the author does not intend any special, philosophical or technical usage of this term. The author also does not intend, by introduction of the phrase “available to the public”, to start a discussion about the nature, social or otherwise, of public spaces or the like. All that is meant by use of the aforementioned term and phrase is release of technology to a general audience, like when Apple makes the latest iPhone available.

the form of value-embedding and oversight. In the second, namely: oversight, in terms of rollout, there would have to be enforceable norms whose content is determined by moral values and principles governing how technology is being introduced to the public. Moreover, if the infrastructure for this is not in place for a given technology (e.g., “autonomous” vehicles, smart homes or cities whose function is largely “autonomous”), then penalizing (e.g., legally) rollout. For this to work there would need to be an oversight body. This idea is neither new nor is it the author’s per se. Dr. Peter G. Kirchsclaeger articulates a similar idea in his proposed concrete body, the DSA (Kirchsclaeger 2021, 352–355). The current author is not attempting to argue for that body in particular, as it or something like it would due, details pending of course. Moreover, the author refrains from articulating the details of a particular oversight body at this time. It is enough to mention the idea; and in so doing, highlight how such a body would work in tandem with value-embedding. In the first, namely: value-embedding, specific values would be implemented or encoded in the algorithm (e.g., subroutines) of the relevant “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems or at the very least a clear set of values, properly filtered in the sense relevant for this discussion, would be the basis whence such instructions (i.e., algorithms) are extrapolated. Having such a technological feat would, however, not be enough. No. Rather, just as children are raised up being inculcated with values, but of course not just any values, yet are nonetheless subjected to oversight measures (e.g., on the part of their parents), so too, prospective technology value-embedding would need to work in tandem with an oversight body, whatever the latter’s precise details.¹⁵⁹ The particular nature of the value constraint operating at this level is based on and extrapolated from the *Metaphor* component of S.E.M. This provides a

¹⁵⁹ This argument was verbally sketched out for Dr. Peter G. Kirchsclaeger by the author of this book on January 31st, 2023 during a break between proctoring exams for students in the former’s course on ethics and digital transformation at the The Lucerne University of Applied Sciences and Arts. It was sketched out so as to provide an example of the sort of argument in favor of a two-pronged strategy which would work in tandem with efforts in the field of value-based engineering.

way of seeing implementation or rollout of technology (i.e., deployment) as a process best to be regulated by value-embedding and oversight.

Having attempted to articulate the model-construct or model, the author turns now to explaining how the model would work together with the conceptual framework, S.E.M., so as to form the theoretical foundation attempting to be constructed within the parameters of the project of this book and whose preliminary viability is to be assessed through the execution of this book project.

2.3 The Theoretical Foundation

The theoretical foundation that the author has attempted to go through great lengths to articulate and provide reasons in favor of is the union of the conceptual framework and the model-construct (or simply: model) entitled *Social Imaginary, Ethical Module, Metaphor, and Model (S.E.M.M.)*. In addition to the theoretical foundation being the union of the two, it is important to understand how they work in tandem in order to be the theoretical foundation they are intended to be.

The conceptual framework, S.E.M., will both help embed moral principles, and the like, into all levels of the technology lifecycle and serve as the fundamental framing whence the relevant machine ethical model is generated. It serves that latter function by creating the necessary framing and in that way serves as the conditions that make it possible to see something as something else. S.E.M., then, *provides the horizon against which we come to see something, and thereby are put in a position to see it “as” in the broadest sense*. Thus, just as Space, Time, and the Other, serve as horizons that, from a phenomenological perspective, define and make experience possible (Keen 1982; van den Berg 1972), so too S.E.M, and conceptual frameworks

more generally, serve as a horizon that allow representation-as to be possible within which and out of which humans can generate the genus representation-as, and whence humans get the aforementioned different species of representation-as (see *2.1 The Nature of Models*). This highlights the power and indispensability of a conceptual framework. Such frameworks are always there shaping how humans experience themselves and the world around them, including their artifacts (technical or otherwise). This is no less true of S.E.M. Additionally and more specifically, it also provides the basis, structure, and content for the axiological-filtering constraints of the model provided in the last section of this book.

Given the general and specific function conceptual frameworks play, from a machine-ethical perspective, it is important, then, to be explicit about the influence of conceptual frameworks, taking the reins and constructing those that are ethically prospective in a more robust sense, instead of ethically retrospective. That is, in fact, what this book attempts to illustrate and provide a way forward regarding. In fact, S.E.M. is such a conceptual framework. This is how the conceptual framework and model work in tandem, both in a general way in virtue of the nature of conceptual frameworks, especially in relation to types of representation-as, of which models are a type, as well as in a specific way peculiar to S.E.M. and the model. All of which yields, or so it is hoped, an ethically needful, dynamic, and robust theoretical foundation: *Social Imaginary, Ethical Module, Metaphor, and Model (S.E.M.M.)*.

The discussion now turns to an attempt to provide “proof of concept” testing of S.E.M.M. This will be done by means of briefly discussing how it can be used so as to ameliorate the severity of three key challenges to “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems: (1) the autonomy problem (2) the opacity problem (3) the enforceability problem.

3.0 Proof of Concept Testing

In this chapter, the theoretical viability of S.E.M.M. is brought under rational scrutiny. This is done by means of assessing how well it deals with three key challenges to “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems. (1) the autonomy problem (2) the opacity problem (3) the enforceability problem. Each of these tests are acute or “key” challenges, because they are limiting factors on the rationality of the very idea of “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems, on whether or how well the extant expressions of this idea can be brought into intelligible dialogue with human moral concepts, and on whether specific concepts such as “responsibility” can really be applied to them in any meaningful way outside of hyperbole and fiction.

This testing is not extensive. Rather it is preliminary. That is, it is aimed at establishing whether S.E.M.M. is a viable idea. Hence, the tests are for and dubbed “proof of concept”, as they are to be litmus tests as to whether the idea makes sense. This type of testing is no stranger to technology or technology related development. For one can have many ideas, but far less that actually work. Moreover, there are several ways in which an idea can “work” depending upon the nature of the idea. Of course, the “proof of concept” testing herein is focused on the theoretical viability of S.E.M.M. and not empirical viability, as S.E.M.M. itself is not a technical artifact – not yet anyway. The goal in the testing is to find out whether S.E.M.M. as a theoretical proposal could gain any traction. This means S.E.M.M. is being tested as to its rationality in terms of its coherence, its implications, its fruitfulness, *et cetera*, in being a putative basis for producing ethically optimized “autonomous” artificial intelligence technologies.

It is hoped that this brief introduction provides the proper orientation to the work to be done in this chapter. The discussion turns to the testing forthwith.

3.1 Autonomy Problem

This chapter is the first of three in which the theoretical viability of S.E.M.M. is brought under scrutiny. As such, the chapter begins with addressing the autonomy problem for “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems (henceforth: autonomy problem). This exposition is followed by a discussion of how the problem may be addressed by S.E.M.M., along with an evaluative assessment thereof.

What precisely is the problem in question? The problem ultimately consists in a confusion of rational practice in the face of impressive technologies (e.g., *Chat GPT 4.0*). Furthermore, the problem results from two things: (1) our leaning towards extending our moral notions to include such systems (2) semantic ambivalence. In the first, there is a quandary regarding how such systems can be brought under normative regulation (e.g., moral, legal, and governance). The quandary is motivated out of a concern as to whether an “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems’ demonstrable skills associated with intelligence (e.g., decision-making, some forms of social behavior, etc.) bespeak of an autonomy that should be taken seriously from a moral point of view. It is noteworthy that a chief rational motivation for the very discipline of machine ethics directly confronts this leaning: either through critically questioning the aforementioned leaning or presupposing its legitimacy for machine ethics’ own research endeavors (Moor 2006; Anderson and Anderson 2010; Floridi 2011; Mackworth 2011; Johnson 2011; Pereira and Saptawijaya 2011; Sullins 2011; Torrance 2011; Segal 2017). Moreover, this quandary becomes acute in light of the current and foreseeable technological trends – moving towards ever greater sophistication – in the development of “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems in the direction of an artificial general intelligence system (AGI system). The idea here is that if their autonomy should be taken seriously in the relevant sense, then humans should extend our moral notions to include such technical systems so that we may

bring these technical artifacts under our moral, legal, and governance norms, especially as these technical systems become more complex and are operating independently of (direct) human control and oversight. Recall that the relationship presupposed here between our legal and governance regulations, on the one hand, and morality, on the other hand, is in virtue of the fact that governance and legal norms do not determine their own content; but rather, their content is determined by moral matters.¹⁶⁰ As such, in order to bring something or someone under our legal and governance norms, that thing or person in question must be that which can be brought under our moral norms, or more generally must be that for which our moral concepts apply. Naturally, an example of this would be a human person, which is regarded as an *autonomous individual* (see *Conceptual Tools I: 1.5.2*) and thereby dubbed ‘autonomous’ in the relevant sense, but this would be in virtue of the nature of human agency and subjectivity as touched on both in *Introduction: 0.7* and *Conceptual Tools I: 1.5.1*. The upshot here: if the status of autonomous may be correctly attributed to them, then we are warranted to extend our moral notions to include such systems. The maximum consequence of this is that they would be held responsible for their behavior in a way that would be on par with that of humans. In fact, we may be obligated to do so on pain of failing to do so being morally impermissible.

In the second, namely: semantic ambivalence, one is faced with the very meaning of the term ‘autonomous’ and its respective ontological significance. Critical reflection reveals that the term ‘autonomous’/‘autonomy’ has multiple meanings, not all having the same ontological significance. The problem arises in knowing whether, in the face of the current and foreseeable capacities of the relevant technical systems, whether one has the appropriate notion of autonomy which would attribute the correct ontological status to “autonomous” artificial intelligence

¹⁶⁰ For more on this, please see the introduction of the current book project, especially the section thereof entitled *0.3 The Primacy of Ethics in Questions of Responsibility*.

systems. This is not purely an academic concern or one of indulging in needless pedantry. No. Rather, it is important because it determines how and with what understanding they are to be regulated. Should it turn out, for example, that their autonomy is that of autonomous individual persons, then it would be in no way appropriate or even morally permissible to bring them under regulatory norms that conceptually frame “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems as tools. On the other hand, should it turn out their autonomy is other than that of autonomous individual persons, then it may only required that they be brought under norms – whether these be moral, legal, or governmental – dealing with technical artifacts and other human tools; this would be so even if “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems warrant being classified as a special class of human tool or machine. As such, the problem lies in opacity regarding rational practice: What is the best way to proceed? What is the best-fitting semantic attribution of ‘autonomy’ for “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems, and what does that say about their ontological status? Under what class of norms should they be brought – those regulating persons or non-persons?

The key to addressing this problem is to begin to understand what the different senses or meanings of autonomy at play here are. The first sense of ‘autonomy’/’autonomous’ is that which is popular among artificial intelligence researchers: “unsupervised” (Allen and Wallach 2014, 55). This sense has to do with human control and oversight. The idea here is that of a technical system that can operate without any or with minimal direct human control. Moreover, this sense is that of the English word ‘automated’, and is derived from Latin, namely: *automatus*, *automata*, *automatum*, and it means “voluntary”, “spontaneous”, or “self-moving” (Whitaker 2010). Bringing this into sharper focus, the sense relevant for this discussion is that of “self-moving”. Now, the range of items to which the term applies include wind-up toys that are

constructed in such a way so as to “move on their own” by means of wheels, pulleys, and the like to artificially intelligent systems that can operate without direct human supervision or control (e.g., a smart atmospheric pressure monitoring system). As such, artificially intelligent systems are dubbed “autonomous” in the sense that they do not require a direct human controller or can make substantive decisions regarding a particular circumstance without human consultation.¹⁶¹

There is another sense of ‘autonomy’, closely related to the ones just discussed, but nevertheless distinct. This is “autonomous” in the sense of highly functionally integrated such that the item possessing this property subsumes a component or subsystem into its functional aims. Such a system would possess an artificial sort of organic unity (Ellul 2014; Orsini 1975). Some might hold that such a system would evidence autonomy by means of influencing the trajectory of its own development in virtue of its functionality, behavioral output and functional role as an artifact within a social context (Ellul 2014). Additionally, such technology would also be generative of its own taxonomic classification(s) (Ibid). Yet, in response, the author notes that this does not sufficiently distinguish this sense of autonomy as a legitimate sense of autonomy apart from attributes peculiar to simply the momentum of technological development of technical artifacts more generally. For the ability to influence the trajectory of its own development in virtue of its functionality, behavioral output and functional role as an artifact within a social context does not uniquely pick out this or that particular technology nor is it something peculiar to “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems or any other “autonomous” technology. Rather, this would be something common to all technology and technological development within a social context (e.g., smart homes, vehicle tires, electronic device chargers).

¹⁶¹ There are variations in the machine ethics literature on this sense of ‘autonomous’. In Steve Torrance’s paper entitled *Machine Ethics and the Idea of a More-Than-Human Moral World*, he uses the term ‘operationally autonomous’ or ‘functionally autonomous’ (Torrance 2011, 119–124). Therein, these two terms are used interchangeably and they carry the same meaning as “unsupervised”.

Concomitant with the sense of autonomy as a form of artificial organic unity (Ellul 2014; Orsini 1975) is something far more illuminating. In the early 21st century, companies like IBM spearheaded the autonomic computing movement. The rational motivation behind this movement was to develop a series of systems, so-called “smart” systems that have the intelligence pertaining to their nomenclature: that is the intelligence of the autonomic systems of the body, that kind of intelligence (Hildebrandt 2011, 3–5). Of course, this conceptualization was a metaphor: a way to see these technical artifacts as a certain thing in virtue of designing them to function in a way that mimics the biological systems that evidence such types of intelligence: a form of biomimicry. It is noteworthy that there is a deep conceptual connection between “autonomous” in the sense of automated and “autonomous” in the sense of autonomic, namely: that something functions “on its own”, like the body’s nervous system and other autonomic systems of the body. It is in this sophisticated sense that “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems are “self-moving” or have themselves as a locus of their own activities. As such, the idea motivating “autonomous” artificial intelligence research and development circles is to have artificial intelligence technologies that are “unsupervised” in the sense that the autonomic systems of biological bodies (e.g., the human body) operates in an unsupervised manner.

By contrast, the third sense of ‘autonomy’/’autonomous’ is far different than the previous two senses. To begin to understand this, consider an etymological analysis of the English word ‘autonomous’:

(compound word derived from Greek) –

1. *autos*: reflexive pronoun meaning, “selfsame”; the word element, ‘auto’ meaning “self”, “one’s own”, “by oneself”, “of oneself”

2. *nomos*: meaning “law” or “custom”. As such, ‘autonomous’ means “one’s own law” “self-law”, “by oneself law”, and so forth (Harper 2018).

This sense of ‘autonomy’/‘autonomous’ comes from philosophy, and refers to the capacity to provide one’s own customs, norms, rules, and laws for oneself, all of which are based on the ability to think of and select freely which of these one wishes to follow (EGESNT 2018). Having and exercising such autonomy requires certain cognitive processes which were traditionally thought to facilitate and enable this, namely: rationality, freewill, and self-awareness (Ibid; Levine 2004). Moreover, autonomy in this sense is traditionally thought to be the cornerstone of what makes us, in the fullest sense, dignified human persons. It is in virtue of this sense of autonomy, possessed of human persons, that respect for personhood and how a human person self-represents (and self-understands) is to be respected (*Introduction 0.7*).

With these senses of autonomy in mind, namely: (1) “autonomous” in the sense of automated (2) “autonomous” in the sense of autonomic: like the body’s nervous system and other autonomic systems of the body (3) “autonomous” in the sense of giving one’s own laws. The first and second senses are more closely related and help to buttress each other, it is clear that the meaning of ‘autonomous’ is substantively changed from its etymological roots, as well as its traditional ethically relevant sense. This is all well and good: there is nothing wrong with this per se. However, the autonomy problem results from conflating, equivocating, or oscillating between the different notions of ‘autonomy’/ ‘autonomous’ - metaphorically: sitting between chairs regarding the three notions - such that it is not clear which one is guiding one’s regulatory

policies, thereby confusing one's rational practice or confusing the rational basis of one's policy and governing practices. Furthermore, as a bulwark against such confusion, it must be kept in mind that the third sense is the only one of them appropriate to be used for the extension of our moral notions in the relevant sense. Yet this sense highlights that it may be wise not to consistently extend our moral notions to include such systems, given the significant difference in concomitant ontological status given the appropriate semantics being applied.

S.E.M.M possesses the resources to circumvent the autonomy problem entirely. This is because of its axiological-filtering constraints on design, architecture, and the like pertaining to the model-construct (model) regulating the technological production phase transitional from development to deployment. This would afford for the correct technological development framing of the relevant technical system promoting the correct regulatory framework for such technology in its regulation in the public space. This would create the benefit of clarity of conceptions of autonomy that apply to it and serve as a bulwark against over attribution or expecting too much from the technical systems (e.g., not expecting the technical systems to produce authentic care behavior or to have a "mind of their own", as the expression goes). Of course, this axiological-filtering-constraint benefit of the model is rooted in its practice-oriented-conceptual frame, S.E.M. In particular, it is rooted in the ethical module of S.E.M.: in its metaphysics of persons (see *Conceptual Tools I: 1.5.2*). This parameter of the ethical module would preclude ontological misattribution aiding in selecting and underscoring the correct sense of "autonomous" applying the technical systems in question; thus, providing a means of avoiding the autonomy problem entirely. As such, S.E.M.M. is thereby shown to have the resources to deal with this first "proof of concept" test.

The discussion now proceeds to evaluate S.E.M.M. in terms of how well it handles the

opacity problem for “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems.

3.2 Opacity Problem

In this section, the second of the three tests as to the theoretical viability of S.E.M.M. is executed. As such, it begins by articulating what the opacity problem for “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems is.

The opacity problem for “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems consists in the difficulty to ““look inside”” such systems so as to understand “why they do what they do and how they work” (Zednik 2019, 256). The reason this is a problem peculiar to these systems is that the dominant AI technique for programming such systems is machine learning. As such, machine learning lies at the heart of many “autonomous” systems platforms and approaches. The machine learning architecture and approach afford for machine “decisions” that do not issue forth from explicit programming (Mitchell 1997). The author puts scare quotes around the word ‘decision’, because the application of terms like this or even ‘learning’ to machines uses these terms, which normally apply to humans in a non-standard way. Admittedly, use of such terms when speaking of artificial intelligence systems is widely accepted these days, which is something the author does not contest. In fact, the author, due to non-contestation of this acceptance, does not take it upon himself to call into question the term ‘machine learning’: the comments regarding the word ‘decision’ apply *mutatis mutandis* nonetheless. Moreover, the discussion herein is not primarily focused on calling into question term usage, so pursuance of this topic at length would not be fruitful. All that having been stated, the use of such terms, however widely accepted, and in some sense thereby normalized, is instructive despite indeed being non-standard: anthropomorphic. For the usage in this regard, keeping with Arthur Samuel’s coinage and usage of the term ‘machine learning’, though anthropomorphic in

application of the term ‘learning’ to such systems, is nevertheless understandable due to the unique aspect of the architecture and functionality Samuel’s was attempting to highlight thereby, namely: that of adaptive behavioral outputs not solely in virtue of explicit programming (SPRH Labs 2019, Ftnt. 2).

The lack of explicit programming intended by Arthur Samuel has both strengths and weaknesses. Clarifying how this would be expressed in modern terms, machine learning as an approach and set of techniques is such that developers in machine learning provide minimal internal structuring. That is, such developers utilize particular machine learning models (e.g., supervised [regression or classification] or unsupervised) and their concomitant learning algorithms: for example, linear regression in the case of some supervised learning (of the regression subtype), Naïve Bayes in the case of other supervised learning models (of the classification subtype), or either some variety of clustering algorithms in the case of some unsupervised learning models or some variety of dimensionality reduction algorithms in the case of other unsupervised learning models (Shin 2020; Kubat 2021). Reinforcement Learning (RL) can be viewed as a species of supervised machine learning “on optimized data sets” (Eysenbach et al. 2020). Yet, machine learning developers do not, as a general rule, define the specific values “these parameters eventually obtain” (Zednik 2021).¹⁶² So, despite needing to determine the learning parameters, machine learning developers don’t entirely define how the problems being tackled by the system yield their solutions or outputs (Ibid.). This is both advantageous and disadvantageous.

¹⁶² Dr. Carlos Zednik words it thusly: “Nevertheless, ML developers do not typically decide on the particular values these parameters eventually obtain (e.g. the weights of individual network connections), and in this sense, do not wholly determine the way in which the problem is actually solved.” (Zednik 2019, 3): <https://arxiv.org/ftp/arxiv/papers/1903/1903.04361.pdf>. Please see also: Zednik, Carlos. 2021 “Solving the Black Box Problem: A Normative Framework for Explainable Artificial Intelligence.” *Philosophy & Technology* (34): 265–288. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13347-019-00382-7>.

In the first, namely: advantageous, the lack of further definitional refinement affords for the machine learning system to come to rather “unintuitive” and at times ingenious solutions to problems that would be difficult to come by ‘using more computationally traditional methods’ (Ibid.). In the second, namely: disadvantageous, the aforementioned strength of the types of systems is simultaneously their weakness insofar as this makes the systems relatively opaque in that it makes it difficult to understand or make sense of how the systems’ inner-workings relate to the generation of their outputs such that one can understand why and how¹⁶³ they got to their outputs in virtue of these inner-workings (i.e., difficult to provide an account of traceability). This is the basic opacity problem for machine learning systems, which in turn is the opacity problem for “autonomous” artificial intelligence due to the fact that machine learning architectural principles and approaches lie at the heart of the bulk of these systems.

The opacity problem might just seem like a peculiar oddity of computer engineering. It, however, becomes acutely problematic when such systems are sought to be used, or at least there is keen interest to use them, in various sectors of society. As such, opacity of the relevant sort makes it difficult to justify their usage in situations where the risk to human security and welfare are high and the relevant stakeholders don’t understand these systems but must cede a fair amount of control over to the “autonomous” artificial intelligence system (e.g., situations of strong legal liability: banking, judiciary procedures, recidivism, etc.) or the system must operate in a highly unsupervised manner wherein the risk to human security and welfare are high (e.g., military combat, rescue, medical diagnoses and procedures, etc.) (Northpointe 2015; Haas 2017; Hass & Fischer 2017; Zednik 2019, 1–6; Mayer et al. 2020; Zednik 2021; Schedl et al. 2021; Gumbs et al. 2021; Zichun Xu 2022). This is because all of these types of situations require traceability or rather a related concept in human social affairs – accountability. Both notions are

¹⁶³ In this case, why is being answered in terms of how as in: ‘Why did the glass crack?’ ‘It was overheated.’

closely related to each other; they even share some core concepts regarding adequate explanation and justification of behavioral outcomes. Of course, the requirements may differ, and the author is by no means claiming they are synonymous. Nevertheless, it is noteworthy that the better part of accountability involves traceability but not necessarily *vice versa*, and the same holds for responsibility: moral, legal, or institutional. This makes sense, as accountability and responsibility require an intelligible “score chart” and “mapping” of how things came about and in virtue of what, etc. Of course, these two concepts are not synonymous, neither are they synonymous to traceability. But given how they relate, what core concepts they share, and the prominence of accountability and responsibility in human social affairs, it's understandable that the opacity issue peculiar to such technical systems would give one pause to adopt usage of these systems, especially their standard usage, in human affairs (Bostrom & Yudkowsky 2014, 316–334).

The author holds that the difficulties of the opacity problem can be addressed by S.E.M.M. In fact, how this would work was anticipated in the previous chapter when discussing the axiological-constraint filtering of the model. Recall that this constraint of the model is extrapolated from the ethical module, the latter of which, in virtue of the ethical template, especially the parameter *impartiality and intelligibility* is an attempt to value-embedded or provide a concrete value-basis for transparency rooted in values that have broad-based rational appeal. With respect to the opacity problem, S.E.M.M., would resolve the problem, or at least ameliorate the problem by means of warranting provision of built-in data auditing for stakeholders (Haas 2017). This would be a built-in feature of the architecture providing a way *in situ* to observe the running of the algorithm(s) so as to understand what the instructions are and how they are being executed. This data audit would provide both a code and code-translated

version side-by-side so as to increase intelligibility. As was mentioned before, this would make it easier to know whether different subroutines, for example, unduly weigh certain demographic factors in the algorithms of an “autonomous” artificial institutional assistant or some such relevant artificial intelligence put to the task of determining who receives a bank loan; or as another example, making it easier to know whether an “autonomous” vehicle, drone – rescue or combat – unduly weighs skin complexion in identifying human patients or combatants, respectively. S.E.M.M. would also warrant providing engineering or data scientist consultancy so as to assist, if need be, in making sense of the data audit, etc. The key here in either case is to make the features ubiquitous, persistent, and standard. These ways forward warranted by S.E.M.M are all pretty straightforward, and largely practical and geared towards changing the conditions of one’s epistemic status in relation to “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems given a class of situations. This is fitting, as the opacity problem is rooted in an epistemic problem surrounding the relevant technical artifact amenable to a straightforward set of practical solutions. From the straightforward resolution to the opacity problem S.E.M.M. provides, it is tempting to think that this is enough. This, however, is mistaken. This may only work as a solution to what the author calls the “weak” opacity problem.

There is, however, another form of the opacity problem: the “strong” opacity problem. This is the problem of attempting to understand how the inner-workings of a technical artifact like an “autonomous” artificial intelligence system relates to human ethical categories, moral reasoning, and moral concerns, or how such inner-workings can be incorporated into moral reasoning, and the like. Furthermore, due to the previous considerations having been provided that ethics is not computable (see *Conceptual Tools: 1.4*), it would be useless to propose to translate ethical categories, moral reasoning, and the like into computable or mathematical

categories, etc. Moreover, technical artifacts, as has been discussed, are inherently moral due to being products of mind and matter, and thereby are mind-dependent (see *Conceptual Tools: 1.5.4*). This seems more promising as a way to relate ethical categories, moral reasoning, and the like to technology and “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems in particular. However, to parse that out would require tracing the inherent moral significance of technical artifacts back to the function(s) of the technical artifacts, and in turn to human agency whence that function(s) came, and in turn to a discussion of peculiarly human affairs, moving the investigation further from the technical artifacts as such. But this would result in what may be called “attenuation of traceable potency”: meaning that the further one gets from the target *explanandum* (dealing with the strong opacity problem, given the nature of human technical artifacts and human categories) the less relevant one’s *explanans* (or at least harder to see how they are relevant). One can go on and on unto baroque complexity with this, but perhaps that is not the way at all. Perhaps, a better way is not to solve or resolve the “strong” opacity problem, but rather to *dissolve* it.

Perhaps, attempting to relate our moral notions and the like to human technical artifacts, “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems or whatever, in a proximate way is the wrong approach. Perhaps, the way forward here is to have discussions more peculiarly human focused: on human moral behavior and its outcomes, even its products (e.g., technical artifacts: “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems), and not one that shifts the focus to the machines. Of course, this would affect machine production, *et cetera*, but at least so with the right emphasis: a human-centric one. It must be remarked that to S.E.M.M’s credit, it is a human-centric theoretical basis for developing “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems. Perhaps, it could help steer “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems research and development in a better direction.

The discussion now shifts to evaluating S.E.M.M. in terms of how well it handles the enforceability problem for “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems.

*3.3 Enforceability Problem*¹⁶⁴

This is the last section of this chapter in which the theoretical viability of S.E.M.M. is brought under scrutiny, and the focus is the enforceability problem. The section will proceed as follows. First, a characterization of the standard conception of enforceability focusing on some of the driving ideas central to it is provided. Second, the relevance of this standard conception of enforceability for “autonomous artificial intelligence systems, in terms of its driving central ideas, is discussed. Third, the author provides an assessment of S.E.M.M. in light of the enforceability problem for “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems.

For this discussion, a characterization of the concept of enforceability is rather important due to the fact that the concept of enforceability occurs in many aspects of society and due to the importance of the concept for the overall discussion of this book in light of the current and foreseeable use of “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems within society. Of course, its importance is brought into sharper focus by the theme of the current chapter. Fittingly, some prominent discussions of the concept of enforceability are in both governance and legal spheres (Fine 1976; Reiff 2005; Marchant 2019; Daly et al. 2020). However, due to the complexities of discussions concerning enforceability and enforcement, the present author, in an effort to simplify the discussion, keeping it focused on what is most relevant for the overall investigation of this book, chooses to focus on some key ideas common to enforceability and enforcement, whatever sphere or sector of society these concepts gain purchase or whatever particular type of enforceability is adopted or upon whatever particular explication of it in terms of a theory of

¹⁶⁴ The considerations provided in the following are meant to complement, not replace, those provided in *Conceptual Tools I: 1.2*.

enforceability, *et cetera*, is elaborated and relied. This is because whatever the precise details are of these, admittedly, finer-grained (and likely thereby superior in many ways) articulations of the concept of enforceability or enforcement, there is an underlying operative understanding of its sortal.¹⁶⁵

As such, it is noteworthy that two ideas feature prominently in the core concept of enforceability: (1) compliance (2) oversight. In the first, namely: compliance, this concept is such that it is of a relational nature. This relational nature is normative such that something must satisfy certain conditions. For example, an automobile's emissions must meet or satisfy certain standards limiting emissions or a parachute must meet certain critical safety standards. In most, if not all, cases certain conditions must be satisfied by some item, feature, or even a person. Hence, with compliance, at least conceptually, some item or feature, *et cetera*, is required to meet certain conditions of satisfaction. This is, intuitively, pretty straightforward. In the second, namely: oversight, some mechanism, however it is explicated or implemented, secures compliance and serves as a switching mechanism should compliance be met or not met. This "mechanism" can take the form of an institutional body (e.g., *Food and Drug Administration* [FDA] of the United States of America), an automated system (e.g., distributive-ledger-based system)¹⁶⁶, a group of persons (e.g., an ethics committee), a single individual (e.g., a referee), or the like.¹⁶⁷ This is a way to ensure compliance as well as to facilitate in determining outcomes should compliance be met or not. Oversight would assist in determining what the next steps would be. These steps

¹⁶⁵ The word 'sortal' is used in the sense of the type of thing something is. In this way, providing the sortal of something is an answer to the 'what is it?' question for that thing. For more on this, please see David Wiggins. 2001. *Sameness and Substance Renewed*. Cambridge, England: Cambridge University Press.

¹⁶⁶ Yet, such a system would not be completely divorced from human participation. In this regard, please see the author's publication: Aaron J. Butler. 2021. "Preliminary Reflections on the Ontological Significance of Blockchain Technology for Trust and Trustworthiness." in *Digitalisierung aus theologischer und ethischer Perspektive: Konzeptionen, Anfragen, Impulse*, Ulshöfer, Gotlind, Kirchschräger, Peter G., and Huppenbauer, Markus (eds.), 211–225. Baden-Baden: Nomos.

¹⁶⁷ More than one of these instances may be present at a time: a referee can work in concert with an ethics committee of an institution.

could take the form of negative incentives (e.g., punishments) for failing to comply or positive incentives (e.g., rewards) for succeeding to comply. In fact, one particular form that oversight might take was discussed in a previous chapter with respect to “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems and digital systems more generally (see *Conceptual Tools II: 2.2*). Both of these concepts, compliance and oversight, are part of the cluster that make up the core concept of enforceability. Furthermore, in enforceability, the ideas of compliance and oversight work together and in so doing can take the following form.

Compliance with conditions of satisfaction that must be met bespeak of normative assignments for a given item, feature, or even a person with a trivalent structure of assessment: either the conditions of satisfaction, given its normative assignment, are satisfied, violated, or the conditions don’t apply in a particular case or at all (i.e., avoided).¹⁶⁸ Oversight, with its regulatory (i.e., serving as the aforementioned switching mechanism) and securing (i.e., safeguarding compliance) aspects, facilitates the process of compliance ensuring its veracity and determining outcomes for compliance (if any), non-compliance (if any), or determining what is to be done when conditions or concepts of compliance do not apply. If this analysis of the rather intuitive idea of enforceability is not entirely wrong-headed and the way compliance and oversight working together might take shape is not misconceived, then the concept of enforceability and enforcement could be represented by the following table:

Compliance Metric	Oversight Outcome:	Oversight Outcome:
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¹⁶⁸ In this respect, I am inspired by the work of Peter Vranas. Please see some of his work on imperative logic, “New Foundations for Imperative Logic I: Logical Connectives, Consistency, and Quantifiers.” *Noûs* 42 (4): 529–572. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-0068.2008.00684.x>. Moreover, one can find more of his work in this regard at the following: <https://vranas.website/research.htm>.

	Reward	Punishment
Satisfied	X	
Violated		X
Avoided	N/A	N/A

Table 3.

This table illustrates the trivalent assignment possibilities associated with the conditions of satisfaction needing-to-be-met by compliance and the bivalent determination of incentivized outcomes associated with the switching mechanism oversight functions as along with the security function of oversight incentivization.¹⁶⁹ Again, this analysis presents a simplified depiction of the concept of enforceability focused on some of the driving dimensions of its core concept. It is hoped that this provides a clear and intuitive articulation of this concept that would be common to all versions of it.

Some might object that the depiction of enforceability herein is misleading. For it is not fine-grained or rigorous enough. Hence, it is overly simplistic. The author acknowledges the thrust of the objection whilst attenuating its force, thereby replying that the depiction is indeed simplistic, yet not overly so, namely: the conception of enforceability herein characterized is a minimal conception. This is because it needs to be sufficiently general to be both common to all versions of the concept and answering the ‘what is it?’ question for the concept; that is, articulating its sortal or the type of thing it is (Wiggins 2001). This is the conception which is

¹⁶⁹ This, of course, is not to preclude that the security function of oversight could be more complex or simply different.

given. Moreover, it must be a conception that does not by its very nature exclude applicability or even adaptability to “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems. For such a conception would be incompatible with an independent argument against the application of the concept of enforceability to such systems. It may turn out that it is inappropriate to apply such a concept to these technical artifacts. But this conclusion would need to be based on an independent argument or set of independent considerations, not a conception of enforceability whose content and structure already precludes application to such technical artifacts: that would be just assuming the very thing needing-to-be-substantiated. A minimal conception avoids this problem altogether.

In rejoinder, one might both grant the rational value of the motivation behind the author’s conception of enforceability, namely: to avoid question begging or circular reasoning, whilst holding that the author, nevertheless, throws out too much content in his characterization of enforceability. For example, the author could have included more of an explanation of the incentivization aspect of the dimension of oversight connecting this to a theory of punishment, its opposite, and so forth. The benefit of doing this would be a fleshing out of one of the key aspects of the concept of enforceability; this would go a long way towards clarifying the concept as well as building a conceptual bridge between the moral, legal, or institutional domains which might prove useful for later evaluation.

Whilst the author agrees with the clarificatory value of a finer-grained explication of the nature of incentivization and even the value of connecting this to a wider theory of punishment and its opposite acknowledging the further benefits this might bring, the author responds by pointing out that this, nonetheless, would incorporate too much conceptual content that could preclude from the very start the application of the concept of enforceability to “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems which would, again, be circular. It may turn out that, for whatever

version of the concept, there are significant difficulties in applying it to such systems. However, this is something that cannot be “front-loaded” at the beginning of the inquiry as to whether the concept applies to these technical artifacts.

In regards to tailoring or providing a conception of enforceability or enforcement that precludes the application in question, some might still inveigh that the application of the concept of negative incentivization or punishment to “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems is absurd due to being incoherent. For there are status requirements that indelibly come into play based on one’s attributes. For example, machines, which an “autonomous” artificial intelligence system is a type of, don’t – as the objection goes – feel pain or loss. So, from where would the sting of punishment come? What would matter to a machine such that its loss or removal count as a punishment? In response, the author notes that such a critical question, however, is based on the view that the ability to feel pleasure or pain are necessary conditions in some way for punishment. Yet, such a view is needlessly chauvinistic. For it holds creatures like us as paradigmatic for negative incentivization or punishment insofar as we can feel pain or loss. The idea here being that without such a vulnerability, there would not be something that would really be at stake for such technical systems such that its loss as a form of punishment would carry any weight. The author also notes that even formulating the objection in terms of “what would matter to a machine” is itself chauvinistic with respect to the technical systems under examination, since they lack the ability for ordinary signification and concomitant abilities. Yet, the ability to feel pain is not the only way to flesh out an account of negative incentivization for an “autonomous” artificial intelligence system such that its loss could be used as a form of punishment or that would be viewed as a form of punishment, and this way does not require them to possess abilities they don’t have. There are functionally equivalent ways of fleshing out negative incentivization

for such technical systems, even if they lack the ability for signification. For example, there could be limits on available power or service maintenance placed upon them as punishment in the relevance sense. In fact, even the same forms of punishment could be used: confinement. Applying these forms of negative incentivization to “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems may seem odd at first, but this would just be due to lack of familiarity or exposure. Nevertheless, newness alone does not make the idea absurd or incoherent.

What is the relevance for “autonomous artificial intelligence systems of characterizing, in any way, the concept of enforceability? For such technical artifacts, were the concept of enforceability to apply to them, they would need to be that which takes the aforestated normative assignment. Hence, they would need to be normative-assignment-worthy or that for which taking on such an assignment has some value. But what would justify this type of assignment having value? Substitution of a traditionally human social role would justify this type of assignment having value. This is because, as Nick Bostrom and Eliezer Yudkowsky hold, substitution of a traditionally human role on the part of an artificial intelligence system, “autonomous” or otherwise, makes the social requirements of that role incumbent on the technical system doing the substituting (Bostrom & Yudkowsky 2014, 316–334). This includes moral accountability, something on which Bostrom and Yudkowsky focus, but the author holds that the same would apply for moral responsibility. Moreover, there is extant interest in or discussion concerning usage of such technical artifacts filling human social roles (Abbass 2019; Horowitz et al. 2019; Boulanin 2019;¹⁷⁰ Juliussen 2022). Thus, an interest to have such technical systems fulfill social roles traditionally filled by humans would justify the aforestated normative assignment having value; that is, in it being something, at least worth looking into as a possible viable option. This,

¹⁷⁰ The author recommends looking at the entire publication, which can be found online: <https://www.sipri.org/sites/default/files/2019-05/sipri1905-ai-strategic-stability-nuclear-risk.pdf>.

of course, is not decisive in attributing such assignments to these technical systems. Nonetheless, these considerations explain the relevance of even considering this possibility as well as the relevance of the concept of enforceability for “autonomous artificial intelligence systems.

Yet, ought “autonomous artificial intelligence systems be held to standards of moral responsibility pertaining to the social roles in which they would fill? If Bostrom and Yudkowsky’s position be taken seriously the straightforward answer would be “yes” or better yet: “yes, if it made sense to do so”. This would mean then that the concept of enforceability would putatively apply to them. But does this make sense? Were “autonomous artificial intelligence systems to be responsible, would enforceability or enforcement apply to them, and what would that even look like? The idea would, at least, not be incoherent. But would the application of such a concept fit the structure of enforceability for which humans are accustomed? The current author proposes that S.E.M.M. can assist in providing answers to these types of questions.

The model component of S.E.M.M. has three levels, each with axiological-filtering constraints. In the second module, which provides the second level of axiological-filtering constraint, the nature of axiological-filtering is based on the ethical module of S.E.M. One of the parameters of the ethical module is that of a *conception of responsibility* (see *Conceptual Tools I: 1.5.3*). This conception holds that for something to be truly capable of responsibility – the focus here is moral responsibility – it would need to be a respondent and to be free (Ibid.). Starting with the second requirement, namely: freedom. The type of freedom humans presume of themselves is not something attributable to machines. The reason being is closely connected to the first, namely: being a respondent, in that the minimal account of freedom here is one of being able to signify otherwise (Ibid.); that is, being able to adopt possible meanings, valuations,

and regards of importance. This, of course, would shape one's actions as an expression of these significations creating from the first-person perspective the experience of oneself as being free to do this or that. Humans, being finite beings of limited power, however, cannot express their significations in just any way they like due to physics and physical constraints (i.e., determinism: Hoefer 2023; O'Connor 2022; McKenna & Coates 2021). An awareness of this alongside an awareness of the sort of freedom humans do possess, makes certain forms of compatibilism appealing. Regardless of whatever theory of freedom one adopts, however, – compatibilist or otherwise – being a creature for whom things matter is a central part, even if only implicitly on some accounts, of an understanding of human freedom.¹⁷¹ Moreover, machines, whether they be “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems or not, as far as current human understanding, are not capable of being respondents. So, both with respect to respondency and freedom, “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems lack the required attributes for moral responsibility.

One might object that “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems could be a respondent and possess a sort of “freedom” which together could make them morally responsible in the relevant sense. For they could be considered as a source of “self-originating actions” (Allen & Wallach 2014; Misselhorn 2022). As such and in virtue of their “autonomous” character, they would exhibit, at least technically, a form of agency. Hence, they would, at least technically, be respondents. Moreover, they would constitute a type of nexus of compatibilism: being that which determines and is simultaneously determined by its environment. This would be consistent with some of William James' understanding of human freedom or human freedom of the will (James

¹⁷¹ Even if the focus is on ‘what humans can control’, this makes no sense without starting from a standpoint of signification in the sense meant herein. For what would motivate control or even the question without granting or arguing in favor of humans being *loci* of signification? This lies at the heart of any such debate: this phenomenological sense of oneself as such a being, even if the focus is actions, thoughts, circumstances, the “will” (however well or poorly such a concept is articulated in a given account), or whatnot.

1884, 1896). Hence, with these two conditions being met, then “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems could be rightly held to be morally responsible.

In rebuttal, the author notes that these proposed substitutes, however functionally equivalent they may be, are poor substitutes for the conditions sufficient for moral responsibility, even if these conditions *prima facie* constitute a minimal sufficient basis for moral responsibility. Recall that in the case of uncontested moral responsibility – that which pertains to human persons – being a respondent and being free to significate or assign signification otherwise were *bona fide* sufficient conditions. For in the section wherein the parameter *conception of responsibility* is discussed (again, see *Conceptual Tools I:1.5.3*), only a minimal intuitive characterization of responsibility was given. Yet even this is unreachable with what is specified in the objection. To see this, consider that a primitive form of human agency is not the same as being a locus of signification. For being that which is “self-originating” (Allen & Wallach 2014; Misselhorn 2022), however sophisticated this may be, is not the same as being a locus of signification. Were it the same, then when a Boston Dynamic robot does a sideflip and a “victory gesture” after handing off some construction equipment or whatever, it expresses pride in its accomplishments (Boston Dynamics 2023). It would be absurd to conclude that (and no one seriously would). Hence, “self-originating” (Allen & Wallach 2014; Misselhorn 2022), though it may be granted as technically a form of agency, is a far cry from peculiarly human agency. Furthermore, even if the freedom humans have can be explicated in a Jamesonian sense, this alone would be insufficient for moral responsibility. Were it, then a billiard ball would have freedom on par with that of humans: an absurd claim to be sure, and such a billiard ball, thereby, would have half of what it takes to be morally responsible for its actions: an even more absurd conclusion. Thus, even if one grants that the proposed substitutes in question are functionally

equivalent, they would still not be sufficient for moral responsibility. Moreover, their lack of sufficiency would even call into question their status as functionally equivalent. No, they would be (and are) tools for aping those qualities in humans, and to put forth the claim that they are sufficient for moral responsibility or even that they are functionally equivalent would indeed be perverse.

The same consideration would hold for moral accountability. Again, the author is not claiming that moral accountability and moral responsibility are the same or even that accountability and responsibility are synonymous. Yet, consistent with what was stated in addressing the *opacity problem* in the previous section, the better part of both responsibility, moral or otherwise, and moral accountability involve traceability, the latter of which requires adequate explanations and justifications. But only a being that is a *locus* of signification and can take a metaperspective can really provide what is required for either moral responsibility or accountability. Machines of any kind cannot do this, only their human creators can. Furthermore, if accountability and moral responsibility cannot apply to “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems, except perhaps only derivatively, then it wouldn’t make sense to apply the concepts of enforcement or enforceability to such systems. For when an elaborate self-cleaning espresso machine fails to run its cleaning cycle, and as a result someone who got espresso from it gets sick, enforcement is not applied to the machine itself due to it not being held responsible or even accountable in the relevant sense. No, it’s applied to the designers, maintenance technicians, and the like. So, too with “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems. Nonetheless, it is not entirely wrong to claim that moral accountability applies to such systems. Yet, it would do so only in a sense derivative of human agency, and even for that: *not so in a way that need be associated with the ability to be responsible (1.5.3 Conception of Responsibility)*, but rather for sake of

explanatory adequacy and rationally tracing the relationship between moral value(s), human behavioral outcomes (e.g., producing a technical artifact in the world), and human agency.

These considerations come from a reflection on having addressed the enforceability problem for “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems with S.E.M.M.: using its resources yields these considerations as a result. This shows that S.E.M.M. can handle this problem, but not in a way that yields favorable results for “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems enthusiasts. Yet, its ability to handle this problem does indeed speak in favor of its theoretical viability, which is what is being evaluated here. Moving on: the concept of enforceability cannot apply to “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems, because they cannot be held morally responsible or even morally accountable except only in a derivative sense based on human agency. (But if these moral attributes can only apply to such technical artifacts derivatively in virtue of their human creators, then why not just cut out the “middle-men” and apply them directly to their human creators?) This would apply, *mutatis mutandis*, to AGIs, because the problem is not one of flexibility, robustness, novel problem-solving, problem-solving across a wider array of novel domains, faster or more sophisticated processing, a different architecture or architectural principles, and the like. No. The problem, rather, lies in a categorical difference between humans and machines such that certain human axiological categories, concepts, and so forth, either don’t apply at all or not in a straightforward way such that human moral notions can be consistently extended to machines: whether they be “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems, AGIs, “autonomous” AGIs, or whatnot. Additionally, these considerations and conclusions are right in line with another parameter of the ethical module of S.E.M.M., namely: *technical artifacts*. For in virtue of the understanding of technical artifacts peculiar to that parameter, “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems would, as technical artifacts, be

inherently moral. But the way in which they are, as mind-dependent objects whose technical function is determined by human agency, shows that the vector of approach in dealing with moral issues surrounding them is to deal with the human agency aspect directly, not in attributing moral properties to the technical systems alone divorced from their human creators, etc.¹⁷²

The foregoing “proof of concept” testing is only aimed at establishing that S.E.M.M. is not just merely an interesting academic artifact whose discussion has some intellectual entertainment value, but rather that it has a measure of theoretical viability as a guide for the design, development, and deployment (i.e., phases of the techno-lifecycle) of “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems, along with establishing that it can serve that role in a tangible way: as that which can be implemented at all three of the aforementioned phases. This provides some measure of cogency in favor of the claim that S.E.M.M. is a viable theoretical foundation in the relevant sense, which was the main goal here. This, of course, speaks in favor of S.E.M.M. Yet, a call for celebration may be premature. For much more testing of S.E.M.M. is needed. Recall that this round of testing was only to show that the concept of S.E.M.M. and S.E.M.M. as a prototype makes sense given what it is designed to do. Further testing of S.E.M.M. so as to establish just how robust and useful it might be are needed.

Some possible further tests of S.E.M.M. beyond mere “proof of concept” testing are as follows. From a theoretical standpoint, S.E.M.M. would benefit from further testing by means of the opacity problem with respect to different machine learning architectural platforms and principles (e.g., interpretable models).¹⁷³ This would test S.E.M.M.’s resources for dealing with “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems based on different architectural principles, etc.

¹⁷² This, too, along with considerations given in the section dealing with the autonomy problem would call into question their “autonomous” nature: as to just what that really means.

¹⁷³ For more on this see: James Murdoch et al. 2019. “Definitions, methods, and applications in interpretable machine learning.” *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America* 116 (44): 22071-22080. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1900654116>.

Moreover, with respect to the enforceability problem, it may prove useful, beyond “proof of concept” testing, to test S.E.M.M. on differing finer-grained accounts of enforceability and enforcement.

Another type of testing that would be beneficial is empirical. Perhaps, an attempt to take a technical artifact through the entire design, development, and deployment process based on S.E.M.M. would be a way to assess S.E.M.M.’s true implementation viability and potential as part of a truly prospective approach on machine ethics. Due to the nature and scope of S.E.M.M. an empirical test of the sort just proposed would need to run hand-in-hand with a test as to its viability as a basis for policies regulating technological production, etc. Hence, S.E.M.M.’s “tech policy potential” would need to be tested.

The work to evaluate S.E.M.M.’s viability – theoretically, empirically, and policy-wise: to consider these ways of testing at the very least – is really at its infancy. The possible ways forward beyond the initial “proof of concept” testing herein mentioned in the previous paragraph are really only the beginning. With the benefit of further research and development, much more could be both said and done so as to evaluate S.E.M.M.

4.0 Conclusion

In summary, the aim of this project is to establish ethics as an internal feature of autonomous artificial intelligence systems, and to do so in such way so as to show that they are performing some type of ethical analysis in virtue of an internal set of instructions and architecture and by means of ethical design norms in addition to whatever engineering design norm requirements that need to be satisfied as well as to provide an explicit characterization of an ethically prospective approach to ethics of artificial intelligence, instead of an ethically retrospective *ad hoc* “troubleshooting” approach. The author has attempted to pursue this aim by

means of providing a conceptual framework and model whereby and through which this can be done. The union of the conceptual framework and model serve as a theoretical value basis and means of filtering and selecting for ethical values that can be implemented in the aforementioned technical system. The conceptual framework and model also provide a value basis for the optimization of regulation of the technology lifecycle of the aforementioned technical systems embedding an ethically prospective approach at all relevant stages – design, development, and deployment – details for all of which having been provided in the foregoing. Furthermore, the author has attempted rigorously and meticulously to argue in favor of his position, using primarily ethical analysis and philosophical analysis more broadly construed. The justification for the central position taken up in this discussion also benefited from a measure of mathematical analysis where appropriate. The benefits of the overall project can, it is hoped, be appreciated from the following considerations.

Generally, the added value the project presents is a systematic way of explicitly incorporating moral values as an internal feature of “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems. This is important, as much of the efforts towards ethical regulation of the relevant technical systems focus on external means of doing so, which is not a problem in and of itself. Yet, such efforts would benefit from the efforts geared towards ethical regulation that is internal in nature. The latter promises to work in a complementary fashion so as to buttress the efforts of the former. This, in turn, promises to assist in creation of an overall broad-based-all-encompassing approach that is thorough-going, systematic, and prospective. Additionally, such an approach would, should it be adopted, put in place certain features that can optimize ethical guidance of the production and use of “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems in society.

Specifically, it provides a basis and means that promises to aid in guiding extension of our moral concepts, *et cetera*, to such technical systems in a thoughtful and self-critical manner: filtering out large swabs of bankrupt moral values, in favor of incorporation of a small set of viable moral values. This promises to improve our self-understanding as to the sorts of values we really want embedded in “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems, upon which they are based, or that are prioritized in their ethical regulation; or so it is hoped. This is important, because a lack of critical self-reflection aimed at value discernment and a way to systematically concretize the results of such discernment is, at least partly, why certain moral issues arise surrounding “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems, e.g., prioritization of profit, convenience, and a myopic push for “advancement” unrestricted by concrete well-reasoned values. Moreover, the value basis provided by the union of the conceptual framework and model can inform the content of policy recommendations, thereby strengthening the ethical rigor and robustness of such recommendations for the governance of current and foreseeable “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems (e.g., in the latter case: AGI) and that selection mechanism provided by the model (of course not apart from its conceptual framework) can serve as an enhanced heuristic usable not only in the technology lifecycle of “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems, and technology more generally, but also to shore up the strategies and practices of policy recommendation for the regulation of such technical systems.

Regarding selection of moral values and a discerning extension(s) of our moral concepts, *et cetera*, to include the relevant technical systems, one additional point, respectively, is noteworthy. In regards to the selection of moral values by means of axiological filtering and the like (see the foregoing), the author responds to a critical inquiry concerning his position herein presented. The author is rather grateful to have had the opportunity to present a PowerPoint

presentation of this book project at *SPT 2023*, a biennial international conference that took place this past summer in Tokyo, Japan. This conference featured many illuminating and exciting discussions on many aspects of technology and society relevant for the theme of “Technology and Mobility”.¹⁷⁴ Within the context of the author’s presentation, during the Q&A session, many enlightening questions and discussions were had, including opportunities to field critical questions and comments. One such critical question that bears repeating was, ‘How does the author’s position handle value conflict?’. In response, the author indicated, and this remains the case herein, that the parameters of the ethical module, for example, are selected on the basis of broad-based rational considerations that have wide cross-cultural appeal. Moreover, these considerations are both sufficiently general and of a small complement. All of this adds to both the robustness and flexibility of the ethical module without detracting from its ability to provide a general basis and way to select for more specific values. These virtues of the ethical module are meant to work in concert so as to minimize value conflict. Nonetheless, some measure of value conflict is unavoidable. In fact, the author questions just how much of a problem this would really represent for the approach presented within this overall discussion and for the union of the conceptual framework and model. For by means of the very act of selecting, one risks selecting values that are incompatible with certain other values. Is this really a problem though or a trivial by-product of having picked something? If the latter, which the author believes is the case, what substantive challenge does this pose for the author’s position herein that wouldn’t simply be a challenge to any position presented that would offer a specific way forward distinct from other ways of proceeding? Therefrom, the author concludes that value conflict presents no substantive challenge, but rather is a trivial by-product of positing any way forward at all for the relevant subject matter.

¹⁷⁴ In this regard, please see: <https://www.spt2023.org/>.

In regards to discernment in extending our moral concepts, *et cetera*, to include “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems, moral responsibility must be disentangled from moral accountability such that the latter is attributable to such technical systems due their relationship to human agency, namely: being mind-dependent and inherently moral, whereas the former is not attributable to such technical systems due to fact that they lack certain capacities peculiar to human agency that makes it not possible for them to be a respondent. Yet, as mind dependent, they can still be evaluated for a certain type of moral accountability that aids in tracking human agents’ morally responsible for their creation and behavior. The benefit here is that this, in turn, aids in narrowing down the stakeholders that can be morally responsible when things come apart; that is, this aids in directly addressing the intuitive question which kicked off the overall investigation of this book, namely: When behavior of an “autonomous” artificial intelligence system(s) leads to harm or death of someone, who is responsible? This being: the value-based experts – whether they be ethicists, engineers, technicians, *et cetera* – directly involved in the relevant technical system's creation. Details pending, and this would need to be worked out based on the particulars of the case, this moral responsibility may extend to stakeholders who are indirectly involved as well. Nevertheless, moral responsibility can never be attributed to the technical artifacts no matter how sophisticated such systems may be or how much operational independence they are given.

Along with highlighting some of the benefits of the author’s position articulated within this book as well as defending some of its merits, certain additional considerations are in order. Accordingly, we begin with the following:

Recently, there has been a resurgence of interest in general, comprehensive models of human cognition that aim to explain higher-order cognitive faculties, such as deliberation and planning. Moral decision making is arguably one of the most challenging tasks for computational approaches to higher-order cognition. We argue that this challenge can be fruitfully pursued in the context of a comprehensive computational model of human cognition (Allen & Wallach 2014, 60).

The author of this book is concerned with the sort of confidence expressed by the authors' views expressed in the passage above. This concern is based on the following considerations. Simply because some aspects of human higher-order cognition have been successfully modeled; thus, demonstrating that it is possible, this does not mean that all aspects are amenable to such modeling. Moreover, even if this confidence were justified based on a measure of *prima facie* success, it is difficult to see how it wouldn't leave out important aspects of moral capacities. There is a whole lot more to being a creature for whom value matters, especially moral values, than just deliberation, planning, and reasoning capacities or what the authors refer to as "higher-order cognition" (Allen & Wallach 2014, 60). What of moral sentiments, moral emotions, moral affective, moral discernment and intuition, moral skills learned best, and perhaps, only through doing, much as one learns an instrument through playing one – what of these things? In this latter case, how many of these 'coping skills' are really amenable to computational analysis and model building (Dreyfus 2016)? Additionally, what the author finds strange about such professions of faith or confidence, *et cetera*, is that they express a confidence that outstrips the very methodology (approach) and practices that engender it: scientific methodology, causal model building, predictive analysis, and the like. Of course, such activities

involve generating hypotheses, but this sort of confidence goes beyond mere hypothesis generation and the like. This seems more on the order of a faith in a type of scientific-techno-manifest destiny.¹⁷⁵ Insofar as it does, though these considerations are not decisive, it smacks of the type of manifest destiny belief bubble that was prominent in North America in the 19th century (Mountjoy 2009). But that is just a narrative, so too may be the confidence invested in computational modeling of ‘higher-order features of cognition’, especially those associated with certain aspects of moral reasoning, moral discernment, moral intuitions, and the like.

In this same article the authors also write:

Systems with very limited autonomy and sensitivity [to morally relevant facts] have only “operational morality”, meaning that their moral significance is entirely in the hands of designers and users. As machines become more sophisticated, a kind of “functional morality” is possible, where the machines themselves have the capacity for assessing and responding to moral challenges (Allen & Wallach 2014, 60).

The author finds the views expressed in the passage above problematic for two reasons. First, the views seem a bit hand-wavy; that is, they don’t really explain how growing sophistication, vaguely articulated, would thereby be sufficient for assessing and responding to moral challenges. How exactly would that be? One defense of such comments may be the following: it is hard to articulate exactly how because of the constraints of the present technology. Yet, that needn’t stop us from making progress in the relevant direction. In response to such a possible

¹⁷⁵ For sake of transparency, the author first mentioned the phrase, “scientific-techno-manifest destiny”, to another researcher at the *Societas Ethica* annual meeting of 2022.

defense, the present author asks: What good reason do we have to believe that the situation would change? The author guesses that this presumption is based on the success of certain machines in processing natural language as well as solving certain other tasks along with similar successes in areas deemed relevant. But those domains of operation are likely not as elusive as the domain of value. Yet, such comments evidenced in the passage in question, again, bespeak of a certain trust in technological development. But outside of that narrative, what strong reasons have we to believe that this is a viable prospect for the future? The author is not claiming the presumption is false or the narrative is bankrupt, *per se*, but rather that sufficient reason has not been provided to believe that the promised sophistication of such systems can make it that these machines can assess and respond to moral challenges. Second, regarding this concept of “functional morality”: Is functional morality such that were “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems to have it, would they thereby understand these “moral challenges” and make assessments *qua* being moral? What the present author is asking is: Can they really understand the category of value such that they can understand moral problems *as moral problems*, not as practical problems, engineering or otherwise? These questions draw their import from the fact that humans, for example, have the capacity to understand a problem *qua* its category. But can the ever-increasing sophistication of “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems afford for this capacity? That is, would that growing sophistication unto even an AGI be sufficient for the possession of such a capacity? These questions remain without answers, and professions of confidence, however appealing, are not in and of themselves arguments for the relevant sufficiency.

All of that having been said, the present author does not intend pessimism, though he understands that his views are vulnerable to such interpretations. Be that as it may, the author has

hope for the future of technological development of “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems along stronger moral footing. If he didn't, what would be the point of the considerations provided within the parameters of the overall discussion of this book? He just thinks that this hope should be grounded in a stronger basis than hopeful narratives. Hence, the solutions and ways forward proposed herein.

Admittedly, the present author notes that there are two remaining items worth considering. The first is that of an outstanding critical observation concerning his project. This being whether moral values are the sorts of things that are multiply realizable(Bickle 2020): If the point of the project is to establish moral values as an internal feature of “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems, then it would have to be a necessary condition that moral values would be multiply realizable? But are they the sorts of things that can be realized in non-human entities? If one takes a functionalist view(Levin 2023) , then it could be, and that might be able to work in a way that is not unlike the way one would take a functionalist view of consciousness (Van Gulick 2022), and then thereby account for - depending on the details of the functionalist view - how it can be multiply realizable. The upshot of this final objection to the overall project being: just as we can inquire as to whether consciousness is multiply realizable, we can also inquire as to whether moral values are multiply realizable. There is, of course, one way to generate a positive answer to this query, namely: to take a functionalist view. But doing so would raise the question, namely: Is the functionalist view of moral values correct, just as one would ask the same of the functionalist view of consciousness? Nevertheless, just as there is not an uncontroversial answer to that question with respect to the functionalist view of consciousness, so too, there is not an uncontroversial answer to that question with respect to the functionalist view of moral values. This objection remains as a significant hurdle which has been largely

ignored. For much like a mathematical proof, the current project is operating on the supposition that it can be, and based on that supposition attempting to articulate and justify, through a proof by construction, how that might work. Nonetheless, the author realizes that this is not tantamount to an independent argument in favor of the supposition, and that the objection really demands provision of independent arguments in favor of that supposition. This has not been done here. Yet, in defense of the current project, one could say that these sorts of ontological questions are necessary to answer in order to get a working model (along with its conceptual framework) that is practicable in terms of regulating our “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems “from the inside” (so to speak). This, of course, is one way to ameliorate the sting of such an outstanding objection, yet the objection remains as something to be addressed. Although this does not in and of itself refute the position of the present author, it does highlight limits on the scope of application of the author’s central position.

The second is that there are some fruitful avenues of research that can be pursued as a follow up to the project of this book. One such is development of an extant normative framework for policy recommendations aimed at regulating technological development of such technical systems based on the union of the conceptual framework and model herein presented. The benefits of this would be to demonstrate specifically how the theoretical value basis can aid in determining policy recommendations towards an optimized ethically prospective take on regulating “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems. Another such fruitful avenue is development of a computational model from the theoretical value basis (or portion thereof, e.g., the ethical module) to be implemented in “autonomous” artificial intelligence systems. The benefit of this pursuit is that it can demonstrate in a concrete way how, for example, the ethical module is implementable and how it can be implemented in an “autonomous” artificial

intelligence system. It is noteworthy that these possible fruitful avenues are consistent with the dual purpose the theoretical value basis (i.e., the conceptual framework and model) is intended to serve. Nonetheless, perhaps the second avenue is the best immediate follow up. This way the first avenue would have a concrete technical artifact over which to provide governance and regulatory recommendations.

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